

CATALOGUE OF CROP VARIETIES RELEASED & REGISTERED IN GHANA

2019

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CROP VARIETIES
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REGISTERED**

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2019

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FOREWORD

Catalogue of Crop Varieties Released and Registered in Ghana

The ECOWAS Agricultural Policy (ECOWAP) aligns with the Africa Union - Comprehensive Africa Agricultural Development Programme (UA-CAADP) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in providing policy direction for agricultural development in West Africa. Ghana has adopted these global and regional policies through the Ghana Shared Growth & Development Agenda II (GSGDA II); Food and Agriculture Sector Development Policy (FASDEP) and the Investing for Food and Jobs (IFJ) : an agenda for transforming Ghana's Agriculture.

Recognizing the important role that seeds and crop genetic materials play in achieving the objectives of these policies, the regional seed Regulation, which harmonizes the rules governing Quality Control, Certification and Marketing of Plant Seeds and Seedlings, has been adopted by Regional authorities CILSS, ECOWAS and UEMOA. The harmonized Regulation focuses on three mutually reinforcing thrusts: (i) Plant Variety Registration in the national and regional catalogues, (ii) Seed Quality Control and Certification, including Accreditation and (iii) Seed Import/Export, including Quarantine.

The Regulation ensures that: (i) local production of quality seeds is facilitated, (ii) the seed marketing within the sub-region is increased; (iii) farmers' timely access to quality seeds is enhanced, (iv) favorable policy environment for the emergence of a strong private sector is created, (v) farmers' choice of new plant varieties is widened, and (vi) the public-private partnership in the delivery of quality seeds is strengthened.

To facilitate the implementation of the Regulation, the ECOWAS Commission has relegated to CORAF the following responsibilities: (a) the coordination and strengthening of the National Seed Committees (NSCs) in the 17 ECOWAS-UEMOA-CILSS Member States and (b) the management of the Secretariat of the West Africa Seed Committee's (WASC/COASem-CRSU). The Regulation is thus being implemented in all the 17 ECOWAS-UEMOA-CILSS Member States (Benin, Burkina Faso, Chad, Cote d'Ivoire, the Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone and Togo).

It is clear from the Regulation that the effective use of newly tested and released resilient plant genetic materials

is essential for achieving improved agricultural productivity in realizing food security and high incomes across the region where 65% of the population (387.5 million) depends on agriculture for livelihood improvement. The National and Regional Plant Variety Catalogues contain the released superior genetic materials of priority crops (cereals, legumes, roots and tubers, horticultural crop species, etc.) that are the key drivers for socio-economic development. The National Catalogue of Crop Varieties Released and Registered, which feeds into the Regional catalogue, provides crop morphological and agronomic characteristics from the DUS (Distinct, Uniformity and Stability) test.

In addition, the performance of varieties for specific agro-ecological zones through the test of agronomic, yield and utilization traits, using the VCU (Value for Cultivation and Use) test, are captured. The catalogue provides a common clearing house to facilitate quick access and use of these highly productive genetic materials across the country and in the region to increase crop yields. In managing the catalogue's software for entering and updating data regularly, capacities of key national and regional ICT Specialists and Plant Breeders have been strengthened. It is expected that the effective use of the catalogue will contribute immensely to agricultural productivity improvement in the country and in the region to achieve the set policy and strategic objectives. As in other countries in ECOWAS, the National Catalogue of Crop Varieties Released and Registered is the lynchpin of the seed certification programme in Ghana, ensuring the legitimacy and credibility of the variety claims and establishing the early basis for release, registration and seed inspection.

May I take opportunity of the outdooing of the 2019 Catalogue of crop varieties released and registered to commend Ghana's wide array of plant breeders, varietal researchers and crop scientists, whose resourcefulness, innovations and dedication to the national cause, have maintained Ghana's enviable record in variety development since independence. And may all, especially our hard working farmers, who will have need to use this catalogue, reap from it abundantly.

Josiah Wobil
Chairman, National Seed Council

ACRONYMS

BNARI	Biotechnology and Nuclear Agriculture Research Institute
CILSS	The Permanent Interstate Committee for Drought Control in the Sahel
CIP	International Potato Centre
CMV	Cassava Mosaic Virus
CRI	Crops Research Institute
CSIR	Council for Scientific and Industrial Research
CYMMYT	International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center
DAP	Days After Planting
DCS	Directorate of Crop Services
DM	Dry Matter
DUS	Distinctiveness, Uniformity and Stability
ECOWAS	Economic Community of West African States
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
GAEC	Ghana Atomic Energy Commission
ICRISAT	International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics
IITA	International Institute for Tropical Agriculture
IRRI	International Rice Research Institute
KNUST	Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology
MAP	Months After Planting
MESTI	Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology and Innovation
MOFA	Ministry of Food and Agriculture
NSC	National Seed Council
NVRRC	National Variety Release and Registration Committee
OPV	Open Pollinated Variety
QPM	Quality Protein Maize
SARI	Savanna Agricultural Research Institute
SAPIP	Savannah Zone Agricultural Productivity Improvement Project
SIREC	Soil and Irrigation Research Centre
UCC	University of Cape Coast
UEMOA	West Africa Economic and Monetary Union
UG	University of Ghana
VCU	Value for Cultivation and Use
WAAPP	West Africa Agricultural Productivity Programme
WACCI	West Africa Centre for Crop Improvement
WACPSV	West African Catalogue of Plant Species and Varieties (WACPSV)

CEREALS

MAIZE

SPECIES: *Zea mays* L.

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/Source	Breeder (s)/Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Golden Crystal	GH/Zm/001/15	CSIR-CRI/CIMMYT	M. K. Akposoe	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	It is yellow dent/flint. It has a maturity period ranging from 105-110 days	Suitable for poultry and livestock feed	All agro-ecologies in Ghana	OPV	1972	2015
Obatanpa	GH/Zm/002/15	CSIR-CRI/CIMMYT	S.Twumasi-Afriyie, P.Y.K. Sallah, B.Badu-Apraku, K. Obeng-Antwi, K. Ahenkora, E.A Asiedu, P.P Frimpong-Manso, O. Yeboah, S. Apau, A. Mensah-Ansah; W. Haag, B.D. Dzah, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: OPV; Maturity: 110 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 4.6; Seed colour: white; Days to 50% silk: 55; Plant height (cm): 175; Ear height (cm): 80; Tassel colour: cream purple; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate; Silk colour: cream purple; Stem colour: Green with purple shade; Cob length (cm): 15.2; Cob diameter (cm): 4.8; Kernel depth (cm): 1.3; Kernel arrangement: straight; Kernel type: dent	Quality Protein Maize (QPM). Excellent for enhanced nutrition and health of humans, poultry and livestock	All agro-ecologies in Ghana	OPV	1992	2015
Mamaba	GH/Zm/003/15	CSIR-CRI/CIMMYT	S.Twumasi-Afriyie, P.Y.K. Sallah, B.Badu-Apraku, K. Obeng-Antwi, K. Ahenkora, E.A Asiedu, P.P Frimpong-Manso, O. Yeboah, S. Apau, A. Mensah-Ansah; W. Haag, B.D. Dzah, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: three way cross hybrid; Maturity: 110 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 6.5; Seed colour: White; Days to 50% silk: 51; Plant height (cm): 187; Ear height (cm): 89; Tassel colour: Cream with purple shade; Tassel arrangement: mid-open and alternate; Silk colour: purple; Stem colour: Green; Cob length (cm): 18.9; Cob diameter (cm): 4.5; Kernel depth (cm): 1.2; Kernel arrangement: straight; Kernel type: Flint	QPM. Excellent for enhanced nutrition and health of humans; Drought tolerant	All agro-ecologies in Ghana	Hybrid	1997	2015
Dadaba	GH/Zm/004/15	CSIR-CRI/CIMMYT	S.Twumasi-Afriyie, P.Y.K. Sallah, B.Badu-Apraku, K. Obeng-Antwi, K. Ahenkora, E.A Asiedu; P.P Frimpong-Manso, O. Yeboah, S. Apau, A. Mensah-Ansah, W. Haag, B.D. Dzah, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: three way cross hybrid; Maturity: 110 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 6.5; Seed colour: White; Days to 50% silk: 51; Plant height (cm): 187; Ear height (cm): 89; Tassel colour: Cream with purple shade; Tassel arrangement: mid-open and alternate; Silk colour: purple; Stem colour: Green; Cob length (cm): 18.9; Cob diameter (cm): 4.5; Kernel arrangement: straight; Kernel type: Flint	QPM. Excellent for enhanced nutrition and health of humans Drought tolerant	All agro-ecologies in Ghana	Hybrid	1997	2015
Cida-ba	GH/Zm/005/15	CSIR-CRI/CIMMYT	S.Twumasi-Afriyie, P.Y.K. Sallah, B.Badu-Apraku, K. Obeng-Antwi, K. Ahenkora, E.A Asiedu, P.P Frimpong-Manso, O. Yeboah, S. Apau, A. Mensah-Ansah, W. Haag, K. Boa Amponsem, K. Ahenkora, A. Agyemang, E.K. Lampoh, B.D. Dzah, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: three way cross hybrid; Maturity: 110 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 6.5; Seed colour: White; Days to 50% silk: 54; Plant height (cm): 182; Ear height (cm): 80; Tassel colour: Cream purple; Tassel arrangement: very compact and alternate; Silk colour: purple; Stem colour: Green; Cob length (cm): 16.6; Cob diameter (cm): 4.5; Kernel arrangement: straight; Kernel type: Flint	QPM. Excellent for enhanced nutrition and health of humans	All agro-ecologies in Ghana	Hybrid	1997	2015

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Dodzi	GH/Zm/006/15	CSIR-CRI/ IITA	S.Twumasi-Afriyie, P.Y.K. Sallah, B.Badu-Apraku, K. Obeng-Antwi, K. Ahenkora, E.A Asiedu, P.P Frimpong-Manso, O. Yeboah, S. Apau, A. Mensah-Ansah, W. Haag, K. Boa Amponsem, K. Ahenkora, A. Agyemang, E.K. Lampoh, B.D. Dzah, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: open pollinated; Maturity: 85 days; Potential yield: 3.3 t/ha; Seed colour: white; Days to 50% silk: 48; Plant height (cm): 150; Ear height:68; Tassel colour: cream purple; Tassel arrangement: open and alternate; Silk colour: cream purple; Stem colour: green with purple shade; Cob length (cm): 14.1; Cob diameter (cm): 4.1; Kernel depth (cm): 1.1; Kernel arrangement: straight; Kernel type: Flint/dent	Useful to break hunger gap before main harvest	Guinea and Sudan Savannah	OPV	1997	2015
CSIR-Golden Jubilee	GH/Zm/007/15	CSIR-CRI/ CIMMYT	M.B. Ewool, P.Y.K Sallah, K. Obeng-Antwi; CSIR-CRI; M.S. Abdulai, CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: OPV; Maturity: 110 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 5.0; Seed colour: yellow; Days to 50% silk: 57; Plant height (cm): 198; Ear height (cm): 100; Tassel colour: cream purple shade; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate; Silk colour: purple; Stem colour: Green with purple shade; Cob length (cm): 16.4; Cob diameter (cm): 3.4; Kernel depth (cm): 1.1; Kernel arrangement: straight; Kernel type: dent	Quality Protein Maize (QPM). Suitable for poultry and livestock production (increased growth, high carotene imparts yellow colour to egg yolk, reduction in fish meal when added to feed). Excellent for enhanced nutrition and health of humans.	Forest and Forest Transition zones	OPV	2007	2015
CSIR-Aziga	GH/Zm/008/15	CSIR-CRI/ CIMMYT	M.B. Ewool, P.Y.K Sallah, K. Obeng-Antwi; CSIR-CRI; M.S. Abdulai, CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: OPV; Maturity: 110 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 5.0; Seed colour: yellow; Days to 50% silk: 57; Plant height (cm): 189; Ear height (cm): 96; Tassel colour: cream purple shade; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate; Silk colour: purple; Stem colour: Green with purple shade; Cob length (cm): 15.6; Cob diameter (cm): 3.4; Kernel depth (cm): 1.0; Kernel arrangement: straight; Kernel type: Flint	Quality Protein Maize (QPM). Suitable for poultry and livestock production (increased growth, high carotene imparts yellow colour to egg yolk, reduction in fish meal when added to feed). Excellent for enhanced nutrition and health of humans.	Most suitable for the Forest and Forest Transition zones	OPV	2007	2015
CSIR-Akposoe	GH/Zm/009/15	CSIR-CRI/ IITA	M.B. Ewool, P.Y.K Sallah, K. Obeng-Antwi; CSIR-CRI; M.S. Abdulai, CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: open pollinated; Maturity: 85 days; Potential yield: 3.5 t/ ha; Seed colour: white; Days to 50% silk: 51; Plant height (cm): 177; Ear height: 90; Tassel colour: cream purple; Tassel arrangement: open and alternate; Silk colour: cream purple; Stem colour: green with purple shade; Cob length (cm): 14.2; Cob diameter (cm): 4.0; Kernel depth (cm): 1.2; Kernel arrangement: straight; Kernel type: Flint/dent	QPM. Useful to break hunger gap before main harvest	Most suitable for the Forest and Forest Transition zones	OPV	2007	2015

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
CSIR-Etubi	GH/Zm/010/15	CSIR-CRI/ CIMMYT	M.B. Ewool, P.Y.K Sallah, K. Obeng-Antwi, CSIR-CRI; M.S. Abdulai, CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: three way cross hybrid; Maturity: 110 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 6.5; Seed colour: White; Days to 50% silk: 54; Plant height (cm): 188; Ear height (cm): 95; Tassel colour: Cream; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate; Silk colour: purple; Stem colour: Green; Cob length (cm): 15.8; Cob diameter (cm): 4.0; Kernel depth (cm): 1.2; Kernel arrangement: straight; Kernel type: Flint	QPM. Excellent for enhanced nutrition and health of humans. Drought and Lodging resistant. Good Synchronization between single cross parent and inbred line	Most suitable for the Forest and Forest Transition zones	Hybrid	2010	2015
CSIR-Enii-Pibi	GH/Zm/011/15	CSIR-CRI/ CIMMYT	M.B. Ewool, P.Y.K Sallah, K. Obeng-Antwi, CSIR-CRI; G. Adu-Boakyewaa, M.S. Abdulai, CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: three way cross hybrid; Maturity: 110 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 5.5; Seed colour: White; Days to 50% silk: 54; Plant height (cm): 181; Ear height (cm): 92; Tassel colour: Cream purple; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate; Silk colour: purple; Stem colour: Green; Cob length (cm): 15.1; Cob diameter (cm): 4.9; Kernel depth (cm): 1.5; Kernel arrangement: straight; Kernel type: Flint	High Quality Protein Maize (QPM). yield of about 5.5t/ha. Yield is about 5.5t/ha.	Most suitable for Forest and Forest transition zones	Hybrid	2010	2015
CSIR-Omankwa	GH/Zm/012/15	CSIR-CRI/ IITA	M.B. Ewool, P.Y.K Sallah, K. Obeng-Antwi, CSIR-CRI; G. Adu-Boakyewaa, M.S. Abdulai, CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: OPV; Maturity: 90days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 5.0; Seed colour: White; Days to 50% silk: 54; Plant height (cm): 182; Ear height (cm): 91; Tassel colour: purple shade; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate; Silk colour: purple; Stem colour: Green with purple shade; Cob length (cm): 15.7; Cob diameter (cm): 4.5; Kernel depth (cm): 1.2; Kernel arrangement: straight; Kernel type: Flint/dent	QPM white. Yield is about 5t/ha.	Most suitable for the coastal savannah zone	OPV	2010	2015
CSIR-Aburohema	GH/Zm/013/15	CSIR-CRI/ IITA	M.B. Ewool, P.Y.K Sallah, K. Obeng-Antwi, CSIR-CRI; G. Adu-Boakyewaa, M.S. Abdulai, CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: OPV; Maturity: 90days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 5.0; Seed colour: White; Days to 50% silk: 54; Plant height (cm): 164; Ear height (cm): 83; Tassel colour: cream purple shade; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate; Silk colour: purple; Stem colour: Green with purple shade; Cob length (cm): 12.7; Cob diameter (cm): 4.2; Kernel depth (cm): 1.5; Kernel arrangement: straight; Kernel type: Flint/dent	QPM white. Yield is about 5.5t/ha.	Most suitable for the Forest and Sudan savannah zones	OPV	2010	2015
CSIR-Abontem	GH/Zm/013/15	IITA, Ibadan	M.B. Ewool, K. Obeng-Antwi, M.S. Abdulai, G. B. Adu, CSIR-CRI/SARI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: OPV; Maturity: 75-80 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 4.7; Seed colour: yellow; Days to 50% silk: 54; Plant height (cm): 162; Ear height (cm): 82; Tassel colour: cream purple shade; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate; Silk colour: purple; Stem colour: Green with purple shade; Cob length (cm): 15.5; Cob diameter (cm): 4.4; Kernel depth (cm): 1.1; Kernel arrangement: straight; Kernel type: Flint/dent	QPM yellow. Good for poultry and livestock.	Most suitable for Guinea and Sudan savannah Zones	OPV	2010	2015

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Aseda	GH/Zm/014/15	Landrace/ Ghana	Manfred Ewool <i>et al.</i> / CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: 3-way cross hybrid; Potential yield (tons/ha): 6.7; Seed colour: White; Days to 50% silk: 59; Plant height (cm): 177; Ear height (cm): 91; Tassel colour: Cream; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate; Silk colour: cream purple; Stem colour: Green with purple shade; Cob length (cm): 16.2; Cob diameter (cm): 4.9; Kernel depth (cm): 0.8; Kernel arrangement (cm): Straight; Kernel type: Flint	Moderately tolerant to drought; Very good for domestic purposes; Maturity: 110-115 days; Protein %: 7.4; Fibre %: 1.3; Fat%: 4.5; Ash%: 1.3; Carbohydrate%: 76.7; Water binding capacity%: 327.9; Solubility%: 18.2; Swelling power%: 9.8	Forest and Forest Transition	9071/ 1368xHlx 4269-1x 1368- 7-2-B-B-B-B/161	2012	2015
CSIR-CRI Opeaburo	GH/Zm/015/15	Landrace/ Ghana	Manfred Ewool <i>et al.</i> / CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: Top cross hybrid; Maturity: 110-115 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 7.5; Seed colour: White; Days to 50% silk: 56; Plant height (cm): 180; Ear height (cm): 90; Tassel colour: Cream with purple shade; Tassel arrangement: Mid-Open and alternate; Silk colour: Cream purple; Stem colour: Green with purple shade; Cob length (cm): 16.7; Cob diameter (cm): 4.9; Kernel depth (cm): 0.9; Kernel arrangement: straight; Kernel type: Flint	Moderately tolerant to drought; Very good for domestic purposes; Moisture %: 11.1; Protein %: 9.5; Fibre %: 1.4; Fat%: 4.8; Ash%: 1.5; Carbohydrate%: 74.6; Water binding capacity%: 307.9; Solubility%: 16.9; Swelling power%: 8.9	Forest and Forest Transition	DT-SR-W CO/1/1368x ICAL 224-1x1368-3-1-B-B-B-B-B-B	2012	2015
CSIR-CRI Tintim	GH/Zm/016/15	Landrace/ Ghana	Manfred Ewool <i>et al.</i> / CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: Top cross hybrid; Maturity: 110-115 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 7.9; Seed colour: White; Days to 50% silk: 55; Plant height (cm): 170; Ear height (cm): 86; Tassel colour: Purple; Tassel arrangement: Mid-open and alternate; Silk colour: Purple; Stem colour: Purple; Cob length (cm): 17.2; Cob diameter (cm): 4.5; Kernel depth (cm): 0.8; Kernel arrangement (cm): Straight; Kernel type: Flint	Moderately tolerant to drought; Very good for domestic purposes; Moisture %: 12.1; Protein %: 8.8; Fibre %: 1.5; Fat%: 5.2; Ash%: 1.4; Carbohydrate%: 74.1; Water binding capacity%: 318.3; Solubility%: 16.9; Swelling power%: 7.2	Forest and Forest Transition	DT-SR-WC/ DTPL-W-C7-S2-7-1-1-1-1-B-2-B-B	2012	2015
CSIR-Sanzal-sima	GH/Zm/017/15	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	M.S. Abdulai, A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI; K. Obeng-Antwi, M. B. Ewool, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50% Anthesis: 60; Days to 50% silking: 61; Days to physiological maturity: 110 days; Silk colour: predominantly cream with light purple shade; Plant height: 167 cm; Ear height: 77 cm; Tassel shape: Mid Open and alternate; Tassel colour: predominantly Purple Grain colour: White; Grain type: Flint-Dent	Potential yield: 5.4 t/ha; Medium maturity; drought tolerant; tolerant to lodging; tolerant to rust, blight; streak and curvularia; Ash: 2.0 %; Fat: 1.9 %; Protein: 13.0%; Carbohydrate: 71.3%;	Guinea savannah, Sudan savannah, Forest-savannah transition and Forest	DT SYN 1 W	2012	2015

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
CSIR-Ewul-boyu	GH/Zm/018/15	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	M.S. Abdulai, A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI; K. Obeng-Antwi, M. B. Ewool, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50% Anthesis: 60; Days to 50% silking: 62; Days to physiological maturity: 110 days; Silk colour: predominantly cream; Plant height: 163 cm; Ear height: 70 cm; Tassel shape: Mid Open and alternate; Tassel colour: predominantly cream; Grain colour: White; Grain type: Flint-Dent	Potential yield: 5.6 t/ha; Medium maturity, drought tolerant; tolerant to lodging, streak and curvularia; Ash: 1.2 %; Fat: 4.1 %; Protein: 12.8%; Carbohydrate: 70.5%	Guinea savannah, Sudan savannah, Forest-savannah transition and Forest	IWD C3 SYN F2	2012	2015
CSIR-Wang-dataa	GH/Zm/019/15	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	M.S. Abdulai, A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI; K. Obeng-Antwi, M. B. Ewool, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50% Anthesis: 55; Days to 50% silking: 57; Days to physiological maturity: 90; Silk colour: predominantly purple; Plant height: 161 cm; Ear height: 73cm; Tassel shape: Open and alternate; Tassel colour: predominantly purple; Grain colour: White; Grain type: Flint-Dent	Potential yield: 4.7 t/ha; Early maturity, Striga and drought tolerant; tolerant to lodging, streak and curvularia; Ash: 1.0 %; Fat: 5.0 %; Protein: 8.6%; Carbohydrate: 68.1%	Most suitable for the striga hermonthica infested fields of the Guinea and Sudan savannah, and Forest-savannah transition	TZE-W DT STR C4	2012	2015
CSIR-Bihlifa	GH/Zm/020/15	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	M.S. Abdulai, A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI; K. Obeng-Antwi, M. B. Ewool, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50% Anthesis: 52; Days to 50% silking: 55; Days to physiological maturity: 90; Silk colour: predominantly purple; Plant height: 165 cm; Ear height: 78 cm; Tassel shape: Mid Open and alternate; Tassel colour: predominantly purple; Grain colour: Yellow; Grain type: Flint-Dent	Potential yield: 4.6 t/ha; Early maturity, Striga and drought tolerant; tolerant to lodging, streak and curvularia; Ash: 2.9 %; Fat: 4.4 %; Protein: 11.1%; Carbohydrate: 62.2%	Most suitable for the striga hermonthica infested fields of the Guinea and Sudan savanna, and Forest-savannah transition	TZE-Y DT STR C4	2012	2015
Tigli	GH/Zm/021/15	Landrace/ CSIR-SARI	M.S. Abdulai, A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI; K. Obeng-Antwi, M. B. Ewool, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50% Anthesis: 63; Days to 50% silking: 65; maturity:120 days, Silk colour: Purple with cream at base; Tassel colour: Purple; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate ; Plant height: 218 cm; Kernel colour: Yellow; Kernel type: Flint/Dent	Tolerant: lodging; Tolerant: rust, blight, streak and curvularia; Potential yield: 5.2t/ha	Guinea savannahs, transitional and forest zones	OPV	2012	2015
CSIR Sika Aburo	GH/Zm/022/15	Pannar/ CSIR-SARI	M.S. Abdulai, A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI; K. Obeng-Antwi, M. B. Ewool, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50% Anthesis (56); Days to 50% silking (57); maturity (105-110 days), Silk colour (Purple with cream at base); Plant height (229 cm), ear height: 102cm; leaf number: 14; Tassel colour: cream with purple shade; Seed colour: purple with cream base; Tassel shape: open and alternate; cop length: 21.1; cop diameter: 4.8; Kernel type: (Flint/Dent)	High yielding; Ash: 1.4 %; Fat: 4.8 %; Protein: 8.6%; Carbohydrate: 74.2%; Fibre: 2.2%	All agro-ecologies in Ghana	A19XA45/A55	2015	2015

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CSIR-Kunjor Wari	GH/Zm/023/15	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	A. Haruna, M.S. Abdulai, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI; K. Obeng-Antwi, Manfred Ewool, CSIR-CRI	CSIR- Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50% Anthesis: 48; Days to 50% silking: 50; Days to physiological maturity: 90 days; Silk colour: cream with purple shade; Plant height: 175 cm; Ear height: 78 cm; Tassel shape: Open and alternate; Tassel colour: purple; Grain colour: Yellow; Grain type: Flint-dent	Potential yield: 5.7 t/ ha; Top-cross hybrid; Early maturity, drought and Striga tolerant; good for poultry feed; tolerant to lodging, rust, blight, streak and curvularia; Ash: 2.9 %; Fat: 4.4 %; Protein: 12.1%; Carbohydrate: 62.2%	Guinea savannah, Sudan savannah, Forest-savannah transition and Forest	TZE-Y POP DT STR C4 x TZEI 17	2015	2015
CSIR-Suhudoo	GH/Zm/024/15	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	A. Haruna, M.S. Abdulai, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI; K. Obeng-Antwi, M. B. Ewool, CSIR-CRI	CSIR- Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50% Anthesis: 52; Days to 50% silking: 54; Days to physiological maturity: 90 days; Silk colour: purple with cream base ; Plant height: 179 cm; Ear height: 89 cm; Tassel colour: Purple Tassel shape: Open and alternate; Grain colour: White; Grain type: Flint-Dent	Potential yield: 5.8 t/ ha; Early maturity, drought and Striga tolerant; tolerant to lodging, rust, blight, streak and curvularia; Ash: 1.0 %; Fat: 5.0 %; Protein: 10.6%; Carbohydrate: 68.0%	Guinea savannah, Sudan savannah, Forest-savannah transition and Forest	TZE-W Pop DTSTR C4 x TZEI 7)	2015	2015
CSIR-Warikamana	GH/Zm/025/15	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	A. Haruna, M.S. Abdulai, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI; K. Obeng-Antwi, Manfred Ewool, CSIR-CRI	CSIR- Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50% Anthesis: 59; Days to 50% silking: 61; Days to physiological maturity: 110 days; Silk colour: cream with light purple shade; Plant height: 190 cm; Ear height: 95 cm; Tassel shape: Open and alternate; Tassel colour: Purple Grain colour: White; Grain type: Flint-Dent	Potential yield: 6.9 t/ha; Medium maturity, drought/ striga tolerant; tolerant to lodging, tolerant to rust, blight, streak and curvularia; Ash: 2.0 %; Fat: 1.9 %; Protein: 10.0%; Carbohydrate: 71.3%	Guinea savannah, Sudan savannah, Forest-savannah transition and Forest	M1126-2	2015	2015
CSIR-Kpari-faako	GH/Zm/026/15	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	A. Haruna, M.S. Abdulai, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI; K. Obeng-Antwi, Manfred Ewool, CSIR-CRI	CSIR- Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50% Anthesis: 58; Days to 50% silking: 60; Days to physiological maturity: 110 days; Silk colour: Cream; Plant height: 198 cm; Ear height: 98 cm; Tassel colour: Light purple; Tassel shape: Open and alternate; Grain colour: White; Grain type: Flint-Dent	Potential yield: 6.7 t/ha; Medium maturity, drought/ striga tolerant; tolerant to lodging, tolerant to rust, blight, streak and curvularia; Ash: 1.9 %; Fat: 3.2 %; Protein: 11.9%; Carbohydrate: 69.4%	Guinea savannah, Sudan savannah, Forest-savannah transition and Forest	M0926-8	2015	2015

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CRI Afriyie	GH/Zm/001/16	CSIR-CRI/ IITA	K. Obeng-Antwi, M. B. Ewool, M. Tengan, A. Opong, CSIR-CRI; M. S. Abdullai, A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI;	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Single cross hybrid; Seed colour: White; Days to 50% silk: 50; Plant height (cm): 212; Ear height (cm): 112; Tassel colour: Purple; Tassel arrangement: Mid-open; Silk colour: cream purple; Stem colour: Cream with intense anthocyanin coloration; Cob length (cm): 15.2; Cob diameter (cm): 4.0; Kernel depth (cm): 1.1; Kernel arrangement: Straight; Kernel type: Flint	Drought tolerant, suitable for human, poultry and livestock consumption. Maturity: 80-85 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 6.8; Excellent for industrial preparations such as grits; Very good for domestic purposes; Moisture %: 11.0; Protein %: 12.5; Fibre %: 2.3; Fat%: 4.6; Ash %: 1.0; Carbohydrate% :68.2; Water binding capacity:77.7 %; Solubility %: 18.0; Swelling power %: 9.4	Forest, Forest Transition & Guinea Savannah	TZEE-W SR BC5 x 1368 STR S7 Inb. 100) X (TZEE-W SR BC5x 1368 STR S7 Inb. 85	2015	2016
CRI Obotantim	GH/Zm/002/16	CSIR-CRI/ IITA	K. Obeng-Antwi, M. B. Ewool, M. Tengan, A. Opong, CSIR-CRI; M. S. Abdullai, A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI;	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Single cross hybrid; Seed colour: White; Days to 50% silk: 50; Plant height (cm): 198; Ear height (cm): 102; Tassel colour: Purple cream; Tassel arrangement: Mid-Open; Silk colour: Purple; Stem colour: Green with intense Anthocyanin coloration; Cob length (cm): 17.1	Drought tolerant, suitable for human, poultry and livestock consumption Maturity: 80-85 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 6.5; Excellent for industrial preparations such as grits; Very good for domestic purposes; Moisture %: 10.9; Protein %: 12.3; Fibre %:2.2; Fat%: 5.5; Ash%:0.7; Carbohydrate%:68.4; Water binding capacity%:79.7	Forest, Forest Transition & Guinea Savannah	TZEE-W Pop x LD S6 (Set A) Inb. 44) X (TZEE-W SR BC5 x 1368 STR S6 Inb. 229B	2015	2016
CRI Nkabom	GH/Zm/003/16	CSIR-CRI/ IITA	K. Obeng-Antwi, M. B. Ewool, M. Tengan, A. Opong, CSIR-CRI; M. S. Abdullai, A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI;	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Top cross hybrid; Seed colour: Yellow; Days to 50% silk: 51; Plant height (cm): 150; Ear height (cm): 67; Tassel colour: Purple; Tassel arrangement: Open and Alternate; Silk colour: Deep purple ; Stem colour: Green with intense Anthocyanin coloration; Cob length (cm): 17.0; Cob diameter (cm): 4.3; Kernel depth (cm): 1.1; Kernel arrangement (cm): Straight; Kernel type: Flint	Drought tolerant, suitable for human, poultry and livestock consumption; Maturity: 80-85 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 4.6; Very good for domestic purposes; Moisture %: 10.7; Protein %: 12.1; Fibre %: 1.6; Fat%: 3.9; Ash%: 1.5; Carbohydrate%:70.3; Water binding capacity%:72.2; Solubility%: 16.0; Swelling power%: 8.2	Forest, Forest Transition & Guinea Savannah	(TZEE-Y Pop STR C5) X (TZEE-Y SR BC1 x 9450 STR S6 Inb 10B)	2015	2016

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CRI Dzifo	GH/Zm/004/16	CSIR-CRI/ IITA	K. Obeng-Antwi, M. B. Ewool, M. Tengan, A. Oppong, CSIR-CRI; M. S. Abdullai, A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI;	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety : Three-way cross hybrid; Maturity: 110-115 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 6.1; Seed colour: orange; Days to 50% silk: 58; Plant height (cm): 178; Ear height (cm): 88; Tassel colour: Cream; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate; Silk colour: Cream with light purple base; Stem colour: Green; Cob length (cm):14.3; Cob diameter (cm): 4.1; Kernel depth (cm): 0.70; Kernel arrangement : Straight; Kernel type: Flint	Source of Pro-vitamin A; Suitable for human, poultry and livestock consumption;Excellent for industrialpreparations; such as grits and kenkey; Moisture %: 11.7;Protein %: 13.4; Fibre %: 1.8; Fat%: 3.7; Ash%:1.3; Carbohydrate%:68.2; Water binding 75.4; Solubility%:16.7; Swelling power%:8.3; Pro-vitamin A (µg/g): 11.3	Forest, Forest Transition & Guinea Savannah	SRC/ ACR91Suwan1-SRC1-6X(MP420x4001xMP420)-3-1-3-1-B) S2-10-BBB/ (Pop66SR/ ACR91Suwan1-SRC1/ ACR91Suwan1-SRC1 -6X (MP420x4001xMP420) -3-1-3-1-B)S2-5-B*-5	2015	2016
CRI Ahoofe	GH/Zm/005/16	CSIR-CRI/ IITA	M. B. Ewool, K. Obeng-Antwi, M. Tengan, A. Oppong, CSIR-CRI; M. S. Abdullai, A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Three way cross hybrid; Seed colour: Orange; Days to 50% silk: 58; Plant height (cm): 178; Ear height (cm): 85; Tassel colour: Cream; Tassel arrangement: Mid-open and alternate; Silk colour: Cream purple; Stem colour: Green with purple shade; Cob length (cm): 16.4; Cob diameter (cm): 4.9; Kernel depth (cm): 0.9; Kernel arrangement : Straight; Kernel type: Flint	Source of Pro-vitamin A for improved nutrition and health Suitable for human, poultry and livestock consumption. Maturity: 110-115 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 6.0; Excellent for industrial preparations such as grits and kenkey; Moisture %: 11.1; Protein %: 12.1; Fibre %: 2.2; Fat%: 3.8; Ash%: 1.3; Carbohydrate%: 69.6; Water binding capacity%: 74.9, Solubility%:18.3; Swelling power%:9.9; Pro-vitamin A (µg/g): 9.2	Forest, Forest Transition & Guinea Savannah	(KU1409/ KU1414-SR/ KV13) -S2-5-1-BBB/9450x K121-3-1-1-2-1-B*5/ (Pop66SR/ ACR91 Suwan1-SRC1/ ACR91Suwan1-SRC1-6X(MP420x4001xMP420) -3-1-3-1-B) S2-5-B*-5	2015	2016
CRI Ahoadzɔn	GH/Zm/006/16	CSIR-CRI/ IITA	M. B. Ewool, K. Obeng-Antwi, M. Tengan, A. Oppong, CSIR-CRI; M. S. Abdullai, A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Seed colour: Orange; Days to 50% silk: 57; Plant height (cm): 168; Ear height (cm): 86; Tassel colour: Purple; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate; Silk colour: Purple; Stem colour: Green; Cob length (cm): 16.1; Cob diameter (cm): 4.1; Kernel depth (cm): 0.9; Kernel arrangement : Straight; Kernel type: Flint	Source of Pro-vitamin A for improved nutrition and health for improved nutrition and health; Suitable for human, poultry and livestock consumption; Maturity: 110-115 days;Potential yield (tons/ha):4.0; Excellent for industrial preparations such as grits and kenkey;Moisture %:11.2;Protein%:5.0;Fibre %: 2.5;Fat%:3.4;Ash%: 2.3; Carbohydrate%:75.6, Water binding capacity%: 55.0;Solubility%:21.0; Swelling power%:6.6; Pro-vitamin A (µg/g):9.3	Forest, Forest Transition & Guinea Savannah	OPV	2015	2016

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CRI-Nkunim	GH/Zm/007/16	Pannar/ CSIR-CRI	K. Obeng-Antwi, M. B. Ewool, M. Tengan, A. Oppong, CSIR-CRI; M. S. Abdullai, A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI; Wienco	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Three way hybrid; Seed colour: Yellow; Days to 50% silk: 59; Plant height (cm): 205; Ear height (cm): 105; Tassel colour: Cream; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate. Silk colour: cream with light purple base, Stem colour: Green,; Cob length (cm): 17.1; Cob diameter (cm): 5.1; Kernel depth (cm): 1.3. Kernel arrangement: Straight; Kernel type: Flint	Drought tolerant; suitable for human; poultry and livestock consumption. Maturity: 105-110 days; Potential yield (8 tons/ha); Excellent for industrial preparations such as grits; Very good for domestic purposes; Moisture %: 9.5; Protein %: 4.3; Fibre %: 1.4; Fat %: 1.7; Ash %: 1.9; Carbohydrate %: 81.1; Water binding capacity: 73.9%; Solubility %: 14.0; Swelling power: 7.4	Forest, Forest Transition & Guinea Savannah	Proprietary	2015	2016
SC719, Gyemedi	GH/Zm/008/16	SeedCo International	E. Tembo, SEEDCo; K. Obeng-Antwi, A. Oppong, P.F Ribeiro, M. B. Ewool, CSIR-CRI; A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI.	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Stem anthocyanin coloration of internodes: Green; Leaf habit: slightly recurved; Plant height: 210 cm; Ear height: 100 cm; Tassel colour: Medium anthocyanin; Grain type: Semi dent; Grain colour: White; Non tillering, plant height (210 cm), medium ear placement, excellent husk cover, pointed leaf tip, clear brace roots.	Days to Maturity: 115 - 120 days; Potential Grain yield: 12.8 t/ha; Pest/ Disease Tolerance: Tolerant to rust (<i>Puccinia polysora</i>), southern leaf blight (<i>E. turcicum</i>), Grey Leaf spot, Maize Streak Virus (MSV); High grain yield, large grain size; Nutrient Content: Oil 3.56%, Starch 55.99%, Protein 8.44%, Fibre 3.29%; Very good for Ga Kenkey, and good for Fanta Kenkey and Banku	Southern Guinea Savannah and Northern Guinea Savannah.	Proprietary	2016	2016
CSIR-CRI Honampa	GH/Zm/001/19	IITA	M. B. Ewool, K. Obeng-Antwi, M. Tengan, F. C. Danso, CSIR-CRI; A. Haruna, A. S. Mashark, CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Seed colour: Orange; Days to 50% silk: 56; Plant height (cm): 171; Ear height (cm): 91; Tassel colour: Purple; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate; Silk colour: Purple; Stem colour: Green with purple shade; Cob length (cm): 15.8; Cob diameter (cm): 4.3; Kernel depth (cm): 1.0; Kernel arrangement: Straight; Kernel type: Flint	Source of Pro-vitamin A for improved nutrition and health for improved nutrition and health; Suitable for human, poultry and livestock consumption; Maturity: 110-115 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 5.2; Excellent for industrial preparations such as grits and kenkey; Moisture %: 13.1; Protein %: 10.7; Fibre %: 1.1; Fat %: 4.4; Ash %: 1.3; Carbohydrate %: 71.9; Water binding capacity %: 311.2; Solubility %: 17.8; Swelling power %: 9.6; Pro-vitamin A ($\mu\text{g/g}$): 7.0	Forest, Forest Transition & Guinea Savannah	OPV	2012	2019

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CSIR-CRI ɔnwanwa	GH/Zm/002/19	IITA	M. B. Ewool, K. Obeng-Antwi, M. Tengan, F. C. Danso, CSIR-CRI; A. Haruna, A. S. Mashark, CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Seed colour: Orange; Days to 50% silk: 55; Plant height (cm): 173; Ear height (cm): 88; Tassel colour: Deep Purple; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate; Silk colour: Deep Purple; Stem colour: Deep purple; Cob length (cm): 18.5; Cob diameter (cm): 4.5; Kernel depth (cm): 1.0; Kernel arrangement: Straight; Kernel type: Flint	Potential orange maize for improved nutrition and health; Suitable for human, poultry and livestock consumption; Maturity: 110-115 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 7.9; Excellent for industrial preparations such as grits and kenkey; Moisture %: 11.8; Protein %: 12.1; Fibre %: 1.1; Fat %: 5.7; Ash %: 1.4; Carbohydrate %: 71.6; Water binding capacity %: 319.7; Solubility %: 17.1; Swelling power %: 9.6; Pro-vitamin A (µg/g): 6.0	Forest, Forest Transition & Guinea Savannah	Single cross hybrid	2012	2019
CSIR-CRI ɔdomfo	GH/Zm/003/19	IITA	M. B. Ewool, K. Obeng-Antwi, M. Tengan, F. C. Danso, CSIR-CRI; A. Haruna, A. S. Mashark, CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Seed colour: Orange; Days to 50% silk: 57; Plant height (cm): 181; Ear height (cm): 105; Tassel colour: Cream; Tassel arrangement: Mid- Open and alternate; Silk colour: Cream Purple; Stem colour: Green with purple; Cob length (cm): 16.4; Cob diameter (cm): 4.9; Kernel depth (cm): 0.9; Kernel arrangement: Straight; Kernel type: Flint	Potential orange maize for improved nutrition and health; Suitable for human, poultry and livestock consumption; Maturity: 110-115 days; Potential yield (tons/ha): 6.5; Excellent for industrial preparations such as grits and kenkey; Moisture %: 14.3; Protein %: 13.0; Fibre %: 1.3; Fat %: 4.4; Ash %: 1.3; Carbohydrate %: 68.1; Water binding capacity %: 316.0; Solubility %: 17.1; Swelling power %: 9.8; Pro-vitamin A (µg/g): 6.0	Forest, Forest Transition & Guinea Savannah	Single cross hybrid	2012	2019
RMG-Obaapa	GH/Zm/004/19	South Africa	Dr. M. Barrow Lake Agriculture, South Africa	RMG Ghana Limited	Slightly re-curved Tassel: attitude of lateral branches; Presence of anthocyanin coloration of silks; Dark green leaf colour, Long Ear length (without husk); Flint-like type of grain (in middle third of ear); White color of top of grain; Red Margin of First Leaf; Silk colour: Cream base with purple shade; Tassel colour: Cream and purple shade; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate.	Drought tolerant, Hard grain for better weevil resistance. Sweet flavor for roasting. Good husk cover and cob hang (reduces cob rots), Stay green (leaves stay green and healthy until cob matures) Potential yield (9.0 t/ha); Tolerant to pests and diseases such as Maize Streak Virus, Grey Leaf Spot (GLS), Rust, Northern Corn Leaf Blight (NCLB) and Diplodia	Forest, Guinea Savannah and Transition zones	Proprietary material	2019	2019

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Abesfo Aburo	GH/Zm/005/19	CIMMYT/ IITA/IRAD	P.B. Tongoona, B. E. Ifie, E. Y. Danquah WACCI-University of Ghana	WACCI-UG	Type of variety: single-cross; Anthocyanin intensity of silks: medium; Ear /cob length: 22 cm; Ear-cob diameter: 18 cm; Number of rows of grains: 16; Days to 50% anthesis: 50; Days to 50% silking: 52; Days to maturity: 90-95; Plant height: 224 cm; Ear height: 126 cm; Kernel type: Semi dent; Ear shape: Conico-cylindrical; Colour of grain: white	Potential yield: 10 t/ha; Maturity: Early maturing (90-95); Fairly resistant to maize streak virus disease (MSVD); Moisture: 9.7%; Ash: 1.41%; Fat: 3.8%; Protein: 10.57%; Carbohydrate including Fibre: 74.52%; Energy: 374.56 cal/100g Suitable for food, feed and industrial purposes	Coastal savannah, Transitional and Guinea savannah	WACCI- M-1205	2019	2019
Aburo Legon	GH/Zm/006/19	CIMMYT/ IITA/IRAD	P.B. Tongoona, B. E. Ifie, E. Y. Danquah University of Ghana - WACCI	WACCI-UG	Type of variety: single-cross; Anthocyanin intensity of silks: medium; Ear /cob length: 22 cm; Ear-cob diameter: 16 cm; Number of rows of grains: 14; Days to 50% anthesis: 50; Days to 50% silking: 52; Days to maturity: 95; Plant height: 189 cm; Ear height: 100 cm; Ear type: flint; Ear shape: conico-cylindrical Kernel type: white	Potential yield: 10 t/ha; Early maturing, Fairly resistant to maize streak virus disease (MSVD), Moisture: 8.7%; Ash: 1.32%; Fat: 4.3%; Protein: 12.6%; Carbohydrate including fibre: 73.08% Energy: 381.42 cal/100g Suitable for food, feed and industrial purposes	Coastal savannah, Transitional and Guinea savannah	WACCI- M-1210	2019	2019
Akuafo Aburo	GH/Zm/007/19	CIMMYT/ IITA/IRAD	P.B. Tongoona, B. E. Ifie, E. Y. Danquah WACCI-University of Ghana	WACCI-UG	Type of variety: single-cross; Anthocyanin intensity of silks: dense; Ear /cob length: 19 cm; Ear-cob diameter: 16 cm; Number of rows of grains: 16; Days to 50% anthesis: 45; Days to 50% silking: 46; Days to maturity: 80-85; Plant height: 193 cm; Ear height: 110 cm; Ear type: flint; Ear shape: conico-cylindrical; Kernel type: white	Potential yield: 6 t/ha; Extra-early maturing, Fairly resistant to maize streak virus disease (MSVD), Moisture: 9.5%; Ash: 11.34%; Fat: 5.1%; Protein: 12.46%; Carbohydrate including Fibre: 73.08%; Energy: 382.14 cal/100g Suitable for food, feed and industrial purposes	Coastal savannah, Transitional and Guinea savannah	WACCI- M-1218	2019	2019

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
CSIR-Kpariyura	GH/Zm/008/19	CSIR-SARI/ CIMMYT	A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, M. S. Abdulai CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50% anthesis: 59; Days to 50% silking: 62; Silk colour: Purple with cream base; Plant height: 187 cm, Ear height: 95 cm; Tassel colour: Purple shade; Tassel shape: open and alternate; Grain colour: White; Kernel type: Intermediate (Flint-Dent)	Three-way cross hybrid; Potential yield: 9.0 t/ha; Days to physiological maturity: 110 (medium); Tolerant to lodging; Tolerant to rust, blight, streak and curvularia leaf spot diseases; Ash: 1.4 %; Fat: 2.0 %; Protein: 8.1%; Carbohydrate: 79.1%; Fibre: 2.0%;	Guinea Savannah, Coastal Savannah, and Forest-Savannah Transition	MS1	2019	2019
CSIR SARIMAZ 1	GH/Zm/009/19	CSIR-SARI/ CIMMYT	A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, M. S. Abdulai CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50% Anthesis: 59; Days to 50% silking: 61; Silk colour: Purple with cream base; Plant height: 178 cm; Ear height: 86 cm; Tassel colour: purple shade; Tassel shape: Open and alternate; Grain colour: White; Kernel type : Intermediate (Flint-Dent)	Three-way hybrid; Potential yield: 8.5 t/ha. Days to physiological maturity: 110 (medium); Tolerant to lodging; Tolerant to rust, blight, streak and curvularia leaf spot diseases; Ash: 1.4%; Fat: 1.1 %; Protein: 10.9%; Carbohydrate: 80.0%; Fibre: 2.3%	Guinea Savannah, Coastal Savannah, and Forest-Savannah Transition	MH1466	2019	2019
CSIR-Salin-Kawana	GH/Zm/010/19	CSIR-SARI/ CIMMYT	A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, M. S. Abdulai CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50% Anthesis: 58; Days to 50% silking: 60; Silk colour: Purple with cream base; Plant height: 177 cm, Ear height: 81 cm; Tassel colour: Purple shade; Tassel shape: open and alternate; Grain colour : Yellow; Kernel type: Intermediate (Flint-Dent)	Potential yield: 10 t/ha; Early maturing; Fairly resistant to maize streak virus disease (MSVD); Moisture: 8.7%; Ash: 1.32%; Fat: 4.3%; Protein: 12.6%; Carbohydrate including fibre: 73.08% Energy: 381.42 cal/100g Suitable for food, feed and industrial purposes	Guinea Savannah, Coastal Savannah, and Forest-Savannah Transition	MH1463	2019	2019
CSIR-Denbea	GH/Zm/011/19	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	G. B. Adu, A. Haruna, M. S. Abdulai, CSIR-SARI; K. Obeng-Antwi, A. Oppong, P. Francisco-Ribeiro, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50 % Anthesis: 54; Days to 50 % silking: 56; Silk colour: Purple with cream base; Plant height: 187 cm; Ear height: 69.4 cm; Tassel shape: Open and alternate; Grain colour: Yellow; Kernel type: Intermediate (Flint-Dent)	Potential yield: 6 t/ha; Extra-early maturing; fairly resistant to maize streak virus disease (MSVD); Moisture: 9.5%; Ash: 11.34%; Fat: 5.1%; Protein: 12.46%; Carbohydrate including Fibre: 73.08%; Energy: 382.14 cal/100g; Suitable for food, feed and industrial purposes	Guinea, Sudan, and Coastal Savannah, Forest-Savannah Transition, Forest	EYH-29	2019	2019

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
CSIR-Kum-Naaya	GH/Zm/012/19	CSIR-SARI/IITA	G. B. Adu, A. Haruna, M. S. Abdulai, CSIR-SARI; K. Obeng-Antwi, A. Oppong, P. Francisco-Ribeiro, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50% Anthesis: 47; Days to 50% silking: 49; Silk colour: Purple with cream base; Plant height: 150 cm; Ear height: 77 cm; Tassel shape: Open and alternate; Grain colour: White; Kernel type: Intermediate (Flint-Dent)	Top-cross hybrid; Potential yield: 5.5 t/ha; Days to physiological maturity: 85 (Extra-early); Tolerant to drought and Striga; Tolerant to lodging; Tolerant to rust, blight, streak and curvularia leaf spot diseases; Ash: 1.1 %; Fat: 3.0 %; Protein: 9.4%; carbohydrate:73.0%; Fibre: 1.0%	Guinea, Sudan, and Coastal Savannah, Forest-Savannah Transition, Forest	EEWH-17	2019	2019
CSIR-Wang-Basig	GH/Zm/013/19	CSIR-SARI/IITA	G. B. Adu, A. Haruna, M. S. Abdulai, CSIR-SARI; K. Obeng-Antwi, A. Oppong, P. Francisco-Ribeiro, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50 % Anthesis: 52; Days to 50 % silking: 54; Silk colour: Purple with cream base; Plant height: 140 cm; Ear height: 78 cm; Tassel shape: Open and alternate; Grain colour: White; Kernel type: Intermediate (Flint-Dent)	Top-cross hybrid; Potential yield: 5.5 t/ha; Days to physiological maturity: 85 (Extra-early); Tolerant to drought and Striga; Tolerant to lodging; Tolerant to rust, blight, streak and curvularia leaf spot diseases; Ash: 1.0 %; Fat: 2.9 %; Protein: 9.6%; Carbohydrate: 72.9%; Fibre: 1.3%	Guinea, Sudan, and Coastal Savannah, Forest-Savannah Transition, Forest	EEWH-13	2019	2019
CSIR-Similenu	GH/Zm/014/19	CSIR-SARI/IITA	G. B. Adu, A. Haruna, M. S. Abdulai, CSIR-SARI; K. Obeng-Antwi, A. Oppong, P. Francisco-Ribeiro, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Days to 50 % Anthesis: 51; Days to 50 % silking: 53; Silk colour: Purple with cream base; Plant height: 180 cm; Ear height: 83.0 cm; Tassel shape: Open and alternate; Grain colour: White; Kernel type: Intermediate (Flint-Dent)	Single cross hybrids; Potential yield: 6.0 t/ha; Days to physiological maturity: 90; Drought and striga tolerant; Tolerant to lodging; Tolerant to rust, blight, streak and curvularia leaf spot diseases; Ash: 1.1 %; Fat: 4.2 %; Protein: 9.5%; Carbohydrate: 74.2%; Fibre: 1.9%;rust, blight, streak and curvularia leaf spot diseases; Ash: 1.1 %; Fat: 4.2 %; Protein: 9.5%; Carbohydrate: 74.2%; Fibre: 1.9%	Guinea, Sudan, and Coastal Savannah, Forest-Savannah Transition, Forest	EW-29	2019	2019

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
CRI-Nkomo	GH/Zm/015/19	CSIR-CRI/ CIMMYT	A. Opong, M. B Ewool, P.F. Ribeiro, F. C. Danso	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: Single cross hybrid; Leaf orientation: Pendant; Days to 50% pollination: 51; Days to 50% silking: 54; Plant height: 179cm; Ear height: 98cm; Kernel colour: White; Tassel colour: Cream; Silk colour: Pink; Stem colour: Green; Kernel type: Semi-dent; Kernel row arrangement: Regular	Potential Yield : 6.5 t/ha; Maturity: intermediate maturing; (100 - 105 days after planting); MSVD: highly tolerant; Suitable for Human, poultry and livestock consumption; Excellent for industrial preparations: grits; Fat content: 7%; Carbohydrate content: 64.77%; Protein content: 13.75%; Fibre content: 1.78%; Ash content: 2.0%; Moisture content: 12.20%; Starch content: 7.9%; Solubility: 1.76%; Swelling power: 4.59%; Water binding capacity: 300%.	Forest, Transition, Coastal Savannah, Guinea Savannah and Sudan Savannah	LA03x CML202	2019	2019
CRI-Akomapa	GH/Zm/016/19	CSIR-CRI/ CIMMYT	A. Opong, M. B Ewool, P.F. Ribeiro, F. C. Danso	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: Single cross hybrid; Leaf Orientation: Pendant; Days to tasseling: 51; Days to silking: 53; Plant height: 180cm; Ear height: 101cm; Silk colour: Pink; Tassel colour: Cream; Stem colour: Green; Kernel colour: White; Kernel type: Semi-dent; Kernel row arrangement: Regular	Potential Yield: 7 t/ha; Maturity: Intermediate maturing; (100- 105 days after planting); MSVD: highly tolerant; Suitable for Human, poultry and livestock consumption; Excellent for industrial preparations: grits; Fat content: 7%; Carbohydrate content: 66.82%; Protein content: 12.88%; Fibre content 1.17%; Ash content 2.20%; Moisture content 10.20%; Starch content 7.52%; Solubility 5%; Swelling power, 14.47%; Water binding capacity 110.4%.	Forest, Transition, Coastal Savannah, Guinea Savannah and Sudan Savannah	LA80x CML444	2019	2019

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
SC649-Hwefo	GH/Zm/017/19	SeedCo International	E. Tembo, African Seed Company Ghana Limited; A. Oppong, K. Obeng-Antwi, P.F. Ribeiro, CSIR-CRI; G. B. Adu, A. Haruna, M. S. Abdulai, CSIR-SARI.	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: Three way cross hybrid; Structure: erect; Days to 50% pollination: 55; Days to 50% silking: 56; Plant height: 190 cm; Ear height: 100 cm; Kernel colour: White	Potential yield: 8.0 t/ha; Maturity: 105 - 115 days; Tolerance: Leaf blight and lowland rust; Suitable: Human, poultry and livestock consumption; Excellent for industrial preparation: grits Fat content: 0.67%; Carbohydrate content: 87.65%; Protein content: 10.34%; Crude Fibre content: 1.95%; Ash content: 1.3%; Moisture content 10.53%; Nitrogen Free Extract (NFE) content: 85.72%	Forest, Transition, Guinea Savannah, and Coastal Savannah	Proprietary	2019	2019
CRI-Nkwagye	GH/Zm/018/19	CSIR-CRI/ IITA	M. B. Ewool, A. Oppong, P.F. Ribeiro, F. C. Danso; CSIR-CRI; A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: Three way cross hybrid; Seed colour: Orange; Days to 50% silk: 58; Plant height: 167 cm; Ear height: 90 cm; Tassel colour: Cream; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate; Silk colour: Cream with light purple base; Stem colour: Green with no Anthocyanin; Kernel arrangement: Straight; Kernel type: Flint.	Potential Yield: 6.0t/ha; Maturity: 110-115 days; Source of Provitamin A; Suitable for Human, poultry and livestock consumption; Excellent for industrial preparation: grits; Provitamin A content: 15.0 µg/g; Moisture content: 11.7%; Protein: 8.7%; Fibre: 2.1%; Fat: 6.3%; Ash: 1.9%; Carbohydrate: 69.4%; Starch: 3.7%; Water binding capacity: 445.0%; Solubility: 4.5%; Swelling power: 6.0%; Pro-vitamin A content: 15.0 µg/g	All major agro-ecological zones	LY 1501-5	2019	2019

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
CRI-Abebe	GH/Zm/019/19	CSIR-CRI/ IITA	M. B. Ewool, A. Oppong, P.F. Ribeiro, F. C. Danso, CSIR-CRI; A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI;	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of variety: Single cross hybrid; Grain colour: Orange; Days to 50% silk: 58; Plant height: 175 cm; Ear height: 95 cm; Tassel colour: Cream; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate; Silk colour: Cream with light purple base; Stem colour: Green with no anthocyanin; Kernel arrangement : Straight; Kernel type: Flint	Potential yield : 6.3 t/ha; Maturity: 110-115 days; Source of Pro-vitamin A; Suitable for: Human, poultry and livestock consumption; Excellent for industrial preparation: grits; Pro-vitamin A content: 14.0 µg/g; Moisture :10.2%; Protein: 12.0%;Fibre: 2.2%; Fat: 6.0% Ash: 2.6%; Carbohydrate: 67.0%; Starch: 24.2%; Water binding capacity: 183.3%; Solubility: 3.0%; Swelling power: 5.3%; Pro-vitamin A content: 14.0 µg/g	All major agro-ecological zones	LY 1501-9	2019	2019
CRI-Apraku	GH/Zm/020/19	IITA/CSIR-CRI	P.F. Ribeiro, M. B. Ewool, A. Oppong F. C. Danso, CSIR-CRI; A. Haruna, G. B. Adu, CSIR-SARI;	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Type of hybrid: Single cross hybrid; Grain colour: White; Days to 50% anthesis: 41; Days to 50% silking: 44; Plant height: 198 cm; Tassel colour: Cream; Tassel arrangement: Open and alternate; Silk colour: Cream; Stem colour: Green with no anthocyanin; Kernel type: Flint-Dent	Potential yield of 5.5 t/ha; Days to maturity: 80-85; Low N and Striga tolerant; Suitable for: Human, poultry and livestock consumption Moisture: 10.2 %; Ash: 2.3 %; Fat: 5.0 %; Protein: 10.9%; Carbohydrate: 69.3%; Fibre: 2.2%; Starch content: 55%	Most suitable for Forest, Forest Transition, Sudan and Guinea Savannah	EEWH-21	2019	2019

PEARL MILLET

SPECIES: *Pennisetum glaucum* (L.) R. Br.

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Akad-kom	GH/Pg/001/15	Landrace/ Ghana	D. Afribeh, P.A. Asungre, R.A.L Kanton, S.K. Nutsugah; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Panicle length: Very short (<15cm); Seed colour: Grey; Panicle density: Compact; Panicle Shape: Globose; Pysiological maturity: 70 days after sowing.	Potential yield: 2.0 tons/ha; Drought tolerant; Average Protien content: 9.35g/100g; Average Energy Content: 370 kcal; Average Carbohydrate: 74.87; Excellent for porridge and Foroforo; Rich in grain Fe and Zn; Tolerant to Downy mildew disease	Guinea and Sudan savannahs	OPV (Bongo Short-Head)	2015	2015
Kaanati	GH/Pg/002/15	Landrace/ Ghana	D. Afribeh, P.A. Asungre, R.A.L Kanton, S.K. Nutsugah; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Average Panicle length: 27 cm; Seed colour: Ivory; Panicle density: Semi-compact; Panicle Shape: Cylindrical; Pysiological maturity: 70 days after sowing.	Potential yield: 2.0 tons/ha; Average Protien content: 7.9g/100g; Average Energy Content: 373 kcal; Avarege Carbohydrate: 76.00; Rich in grain Fe and Zn; Excellent for Porridge, Foroforo; cakes and T-Z; Tolerant to Downy mildew disease.	Guinea and Sudan savannahs	OPV (Arrow Head)	2015	2015
Naad-kohblug	GH/Pg/003/15	Landrace/ Ghana	D. Afribeh, P.A. Asungre, R.A.L Kanton, S.K. Nutsugah; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Average Panicle length: 31 cm; Seed colour: Deep grey; Panicle density: Loose; Panicle Shape: Candle; Pysiological maturity : 75 days after sowing; Presence of Bristles on panicles.	Potential yield: 2.0 tons/ha.; Average Protien content: 11g/100g; Average Energy Content: 370 kcal; Average Carbohydrate: 74; Rich in grain Fe and Zn; Drought tolerant; Tolerant to bird and insect damage; Tolerant to Downy mildew disease; Excellent for Porridge and Foroforo.	Guinea and Sudan savannahs	OPV (Bristled Head)	2015	2015
WAAPP-Naara	GH/Pg/004/15	CSIR-SARI/ ICRISAT	D. Afribeh, P.A. Asungre, R.A.L Kanton, S.K. Nutsugah; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Average Panicle length: 23 cm; Seed colour: Grey; Panicle density: compact; Panicle Shape: Conical; Pysiological maturity : 80 days after sowing.	Potential yield: 2.1 tons/ha; Avearge Protien content: 10g/100g; Average Energy Content: 370 kcal; Carbohydrate: 74; Rich in grain Fe and Zn; Dual purpose (Fodder, grain and fuel wood); Resistance to Downy mildew Disease.	Guinea and Sudan savannahs	So x Sat (Introduction from ICRISAT-SC)	2015	2015
Afribeh Naara	GH/Pg/005/15	Landrace/ Ghana	D. Afribeh, P.A. Asungre, R.A.L Kanton, S.K. Nutsugah; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Average Panicle length: 21 cm; Seed colour: Yellow; Panicle density: Semi-compact; Panicle Shape: Cylindrical; Pysiological maturity : 70 days after sowing.	Potential yield: 1.90 tons/ha.; Average Protien content: 9g/100g; Average Energy Content: 370 kcal; Carbohydrate: 75; Rich in grain Fe and Zn; Excellent for Foroforo; Tolerant to Downy mildew disease.	Guinea and Sudan savannahs	OPV (Tongo Yellow)	2015	2015

RICE

SPECIES: *Oryza sativa* L.

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
FARO 15	GH/Os/001/15	IRRI	MoFA/Ghana German Agricultural Development Project	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Maturity period 145-150 days. Long and bold grain, non-aromatic.	Yield potential of 5.0 MT/ha. The most preferred variety for the deep lowlands. Milling rate 65%. Average cooking quality. Preferred by artisanal processors due to high milling rate. Good for Waakye, Jollof and Omutuo. Good resistance to common pests and diseases	Deep lowland	Pure line Introduced from Nigeria with a name FARO 15	1980	2015
GR 18 (GRUG 7)	GH/Os/002/15	IRRI	Irrigation Development Authority of MoFA	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Matures in 132 days. Medium and bold grain, non-aromatic.	Yield potential of 6.5MT/ha. Milling rate 65%. Good cooking quality. High consumer acceptability for Waakye, Jollof and Omutuo. Good resistance to common pests and diseases	Lowland & irrigated	Introduction from IRRI with a pedigree name of IET 2885 (LET 1996)	1983	2015
GR 19	GH/Os/003/15	IRRI	R. C. Dekuku; CRI/(NAES, CSIR-SARI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Matures in 125 days. Long and slender grain, non-aromatic, intermediate amylose content.	Yield potential of 5.5 MT/ha. Milling rate 62%. Good cooking quality. High consumer acceptability and good resistance to common pests and diseases	Lowland	Introduction from IRRI with a pedigree name of C-168	1986	2015
GR 20	GH/Os/004/15	IRRI	R. C. Dekuku; NAES, CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Matures in 125 days. Long and slender grain, non-aromatic, intermediate amylose content.	Yield potential of 4.5 MT/ha. Milling rate 62%. Good cooking quality. High consumer acceptability and good resistance to common pests and diseases	Lowland	Pure line Introduction from IRRI with a pedigree name IR1750	1986	2015
GR 21	GH/Os/005/15	IRRI	R. C. Dekuku; NAES, CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Matures in 125 days. Short and bold grain, non-aromatic, relatively high amylose content.	Yield potential of 4.5MT/ha. Milling rate 64%. Acceptable cooking quality especially for Waakye, Jollof and Omutuo. Good resistance to common pests and diseases	Lowland	Pure line Introduction from IRRI with a pedigree name of Tox 516-19	1986	2015
Sikamo	GH/Os/006/15	IRRI	R. Barn, E. Otoo, J.Ofori M. D. Asante, G. Acheampong, E. Annan Aful, P.K. A. Dartey - CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Days to 50% flowering: 90 – 95; Maturity (days): 120 – 125.	Potential yield: 6.0MT/ha. Resistance to blast: Tolerant; Resistance to lodging: Tolerant; Grain shape: High N use efficiency; Caryopsis color: Long and slender; White rice % (Milling yield): 68.4; Cooking quality: Good; non-sticky; high expansion ratio	Lowland/ Hydromorphic		1997	2015
Digang	GH/Os/007/15	IRRI	W. Dogbe; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Matures in 115 days. Long and slender grain, non-aromatic. Amylose content- 23-25%; Alkaline spreading value- 6	Yield potential of 4.8 MT/ha. Very plastic (Can be grown across ecologies), adapted to low input systems. Milling rate is 65%. Acceptable cooking quality especially for Waakye, Jollof and Omutuo. Tolerant RYMV and blast	Hydromorphic & lowland	Pure line Introduced from IRRI, Philippines with a pedigree name of IR 12979-24-1-1	2003	2015
Gbewaa Rice	GH/Os/008/15	IRRI	W. Dogbe, I.D.K Atokple; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Maturity period 110-115 days. Long and slender grain, aromatic intermediate amylose content.	Yield potential of 5-6 MT/ha. Milling rate is 62%. Excellent cooking quality. Very high consumer acceptability and good resistance to common pests and diseases	Lowland & irrigated	Pure line Introduced from USA with a name Jasmine 85	2009	2015
Nabogo Rice	GH/Os/009/15	IRRI	W. Dogbe, I.D.K Atokple; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Matures in 120-130 days. Long and slender grain, non-aromatic intermediate amylose content.	Yield potential of 6-7 MT/ha. Milling rate is 60%. Very good cooking quality. High consumer acceptability and good resistance to common pests and diseases	Lowland & irrigated	Pure line Introduced from WRADA/AfricaRice Nigeria with a pedigree name Tox 3233-31-6-2-3-1	2009	2015
Katanga Rice	GH/Os/010/15	IRRI	W. Dogbe, I.D.K Atokple; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Matures in 130-140 days. Long and slender grain, aromatic intermediate amylose content	Yield potential of 6-8 MT/ha. Milling rate 62%. Excellent cooking quality. High consumer acceptability and good resistance to common pests and diseases	Deep Lowland	Pure line Introduced from WRADA/AfricaRice Nigeria with a pedigree name Tox 3972-10-1-2-1-1-3-2	2009	2015

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
NERICA 1	GH/Os/011/15	AfricaRice	W. Dogbe, I.D.K Atokple, CSIR-SARI; P.K.A. Dartey CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Matures in 90-95 days. Drought tolerant, medium grain size, aromatic	Yield potential of 3-4 MT/ha, high amylose, average consumer acceptability	Upland	Pure line Introduced from WARDA/ AfricaRice, Cote d'Ivoire with a name NERICA 1	2009	2015
NERICA 2	GH/Os/012/15	AfricaRice	W. Dogbe, I.D.K Atokple, CSIR-SARI; P.K.A. Dartey CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Matures in 95-100 days. Drought tolerant, long and slender grain size, non-aromatic	Yield potential of 3-4 MT/ha, high amylose, average consumer acceptability	Upland	Pure line Introduced from WARDA/ AfricaRice, Cote d'Ivoire with a name NERICA 2	2009	2015
Mmo teaa	GH/Os/013/15	AfricaRice	P.K. A. Dartey, R. Barn, M. D. Asante, G. Acheampong, E. Annan Aful - CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Days to 50% flowering: 75-80; Maturity (days): 110 – 115; Grain shape: long and slender	Potential yield: 4.8 t/ha; Resistant to blast: tolerant; Resistant to lodging: good; Cooking quality: Good; Amylose content: 21%; Alkaline spreading value: 5.0	Upland	IDSA 85	2009	2015
Otoo mmo	GH/Os/014/15	AfricaRice	P.K. A. Dartey, R. Barn, M. D. Asante, G. Acheampong, E. Annan Aful - CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Days to 50% flowering: 80 – 85; Maturity (days): 115 – 120; Grain shape: Long And Slender; Caryopsis color: White	Potential yield: 5.6 t/ha; Resistant to blast: tolerant; Resistant to lodging: good; Cooking quality: Good; Amylose content: 16.5%; Alkaline spreading value: 3.3; Resistance to blast: Resistant; Resistance to lodging: Good; White rice % (Milling yield): 66; Cooking quality: Good; Aroma: Absent	Upland	TOXX 3377	2009	2015
CRI-Amankwatia	GH/Os/015/15	IRRI	R. Barn, M. D. Asante, G. Acheampong, E. Annan Aful, P.K. A. Dartey - CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Days to 50% flowering: 80 – 85; Maturity (days): 115 – 120; Grain shape: Long and Slender; Caryopsis color: White	Potential yield: 8.0 t/ha; Resistant to blast: tolerant; Resistant to lodging: good; White rice % (Milling yield): 70.4%; Cooking quality: Good; Aromatic; Amylose content: 22.5%; Alkaline spreading value: 3.7; Resistance to blast: Tolerant; Resistance to lodging: Good; White rice % (Milling yield): 70.4; Cooking quality: Good; Aroma: Present	Lowland	Pureline selection from Togo Marshal	2010	2015
Wakatsuki	GH/Os/016/15	AfricaRice	R. Barn, M. D. Asante, G. Acheampong, E. Annan Aful, P.K. A. Dartey - CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Days to 50% flowering: 93-98; Maturity (days): 125 – 130; Resistance to blast: Tolerant; Resistance to lodging: Good; Grain shape: Long And Slender; Caryopsis color: White	Potential yield: 8.0 t/ha; Resistant to blast: tolerant; Resistant to lodging: good; Cooking quality: Good; Culm strength: intermediate; Amylose content: 23.9%; Alkaline spreading value: 7.0; White rice % (Milling yield): 66; Cooking quality: Good; Aroma: Absent	Lowland	Bouake 189	2010	2015
Bodia	GH/Os/017/15	IITA, Ibadan	R. Barn, M. D. Asante, G. Acheampong, E. Annan Aful, P.K. A. Dartey - CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Days to 50% flowering: 90-95; Maturity (days): 120 – 125; Grain shape: Bold; Caryopsis color: White.	Potential yield: 8.0 t/ha; Resistant to blast: tolerant; Resistant to lodging: good; Cooking quality: Good; Culm strength: strong; Amylose content: 23.5%; Alkaline spreading value: 6.0; Resistance to blast: Tolerant; Resistance to lodging: Good; White rice % (Milling yield): 66; Cooking quality: Good; Aroma: Absent	Lowland	ITA 320	2010	2015

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Sakai	GH/Os/018/15	IITA, Ibadan	R. Barn, M. D. Asante, G. Acheampong, E. Annan Afful, P.K. A. Dartey - CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Days to 50% flowering: 95 – 100; Maturity (days): 135 – 140; Grain shape: Long And Slender; Caryopsis color: white	Potential yield: 8.0 t/ha; Resistant to blast: tolerant; Resistant to lodging: good; Cooking quality: Good; Amylose content: 18.6%; Alkaline spreading value: 3.0; Resistance to blast: Tolerant; Resistance to lodging: Good; White rice %(Milling yield):66; Cooking quality: Good; Aroma: Absent	Lowland	ITA 324	2010	2015
AGRA Rice	GH/Os/019/15	IRRI	P.K.A Dartey; CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Day to 50% flowering: 90-98 days; Day to maturity: 125-130 days; 1000 grain weight: 28.3 g; Grain shape: Long And Slender	Yield potetial: 8 t/ha; Resistant to blast: tolerant to iron toxicity: moderate; White rice % (Milling yield): 70.4; Cooking quality: Good; Amylose content: 16-18%; Alkaline spreading value: 7; Aroma: Stong aroma	Forest, Guinea savannah, Coastal savannah	IR841(IR262 X Khao Dawk Mali 105)	2013	2015
CRI-Dartey	GH/Os/001/19	CSIR-CRI, Ghana	M. D. Asante, K. Dartey, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Anthocyanin coloration of auricles on leaf: Absent; Anthocyanin coloration of apex on Lemma (early observation): Very weak; Time of heading (50% of plants with heads): Medium; Stem length (excluding panicle): Short; Distribution of awns: Panicle tip only; Panicle branching: spreading, 1000 Grain weight: 27.2 g	Potential Yield: 9.0 t/ha; Milling yeild: 68.8 %; Days to physiological maturity: 125; Grain length: long Plant Height: 120 cm; Amylose content: 20.1%; Disease Tolerance: Rice Blast, Rice Yellow Mottle Virus; Iron Toxicity: Tolerant Cooking quality: Soft and fluffy. Slightly aromatic;	Lowland, Irrigated	NIL2/IR841	2019	2019
CRI-Kantinka	GH/Os/002/19	AfricaRice	M. D. Asante, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Anthocyanin coloration of auricles on leaf: Present; Anthocyanin coloration of apex on Lemma (early observation): Very weak; Time of heading (50% of plants with heads): Medium; Non-prostrate varieties only: Stem length (excluding panicle): Short; Distribution of awns: Panicle on tip only; Panicle branching: Semi-erect; 1000 Grain weight: 27.2 g	Potential yield: 8.5 t/ha; Milling yield: 68.8 %; Grain Length: Long; Days to physiological maturity: 125; Plant Height: 120 cm; Seed Length: 9.68mm; Seed Width: 2.62mm; Amylose content: 19.8%; Non-aromatic	Lowland, Irrigated	TOG 5681 / 4*IR 64	2019	2019
CRI-Obofo	GH/Os/003/19	AfricaRice	M. D. Asante, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Anthocyanin coloration of auricles on leaf: Absent; Anthocyanin coloration of apex on Lemma (early observation): Very weak; Time of heading (50% of plants with heads): Medium; Stem length (excluding panicle): Short; Distribution of awns on panicle: None; Panicle branching: Semi-erect; 1000 Grain weight: 28.7 g.	Potential yield: 8.5 t/ha; Milling yield: 66%; Grain Length: Long; Days to physiological maturity: 135; Seed Length: 10.18mm; Seed Width: 2.47mm; Plant Height: 120 cm; Amylose content: 24.2%; Good cooking and processing qualities (baby foods); Non-aromatic	Lowland, Irrigated	T0g 6542 / TOX3056-28-1-1-1// IRAT126//WITA 1)	2019	2019

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
CRI-Eropa	GH/Os/004/19	CSIR-CRI, Ghana	M. D. Asante, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Anthocyanin coloration of auricles on leaf: Present; Anthocyanin coloration of apex on Lemma (early observation): Strong; Time of heading (50% of plants with heads): Medium; Stem length (excluding panicle): Medium; Distribution of awns on panicle: None; Panicle branching: Spreading	Potential yield: 8.0 t/ha; Milling yield: 70.4%; Grain Length: Long; Days to physiological maturity: 130; Seed Length: 9.59mm; Seed Width: 2.56mm; Amylose content: 20.1 %; Slightly aromatic; 1000 Grain weight: 27.4 g.	Lowland, Irrigated	Sikamo/Jasmine 85	2019	2019
CRI-Mpuntuo	GH/Os/005/19	CSIR-CRI, Ghana	M. D. Asante, K. Dartey, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Anthocyanin coloration of auricles on leaf: Absent; Anthocyanin coloration of apex on Lemma (early observation): Very weak; Time of heading (50% of plants with heads): Early; Stem length (excluding panicle): Short; Distribution of awns on panicle: None; Panicle branching: Semi-erect; 1000 Grain weight: 29.4 g	Potential yield: 8 t/ha; Milling Yield: 68.8%; Grain Length: Long; Days to physiological maturity: 120; Seed Length: 9.72 mm; Seed Width: 2.56 mm; Plant Height: 120 cm; Amylose content: 23.7 %; Slightly aromatic; Good cooking and processing qualities (baby foods)	Lowland, Irrigated	IR841/IWA10	2019	2019
CRI-Enapa	GH/Os/006/19	CSIR-CRI, Ghana	M. D. Asante, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Anthocyanin coloration of auricles on leaf: Present; Anthocyanin coloration of apex on Lemma (early observation): Strong; Time of heading (50% of plants with heads): Medium; Stem length (excluding panicle): Medium; Distribution of awns on panicle: None; Panicle branching: Semi-erect; 1000 seed weight: 27.6 g	Potential yield: 9.5 t/ha; Milling yield: 68.8%; Grain Length: Long; Days to physiological maturity: 130; Seed Length: 9.61 mm; Seed Width: 2.55 mm; Plant height: 135 cm; Amylose content: 19.9 %; Slightly aromatic	Lowland, Irrigated	Sikamo/Jasmine 85	2019	2019
Legon Rice 1	GH/Os/007/19	China	J. Ofori, University of Ghana	University of Ghana	Spikelet (color of Stigma): white; Flag leaf attitude (early observation): erect; Flag leaf attitude (late observation): horizontal; Leaf anthocyanin coloration of auricles: absent; Stem length excluding panicle: short; Lemma (anthocyanin coloration of apex): medium; Panicle (attitude in relation to stem): semi-upright; Panicle attitude of branches: semi-erect; Decorticated grain color: white; Decorticated grain shape: spindle shaped	Tolerant to Rice Yellow Mottle Virus disease; Resistant to blast disease; Excellent cooking quality, aromatic; Potential yield is 9t/ha; Amylose content: 18.3%	Lowland & irrigated (Rain forest, Semi-deciduous Forest, Forest-transition, Coastal Savannah and Savannah)	TV1 (Ex – Baika)	2019	2019

SORGHUM

SPECIES: *Sorghum bicolor* L. Moences

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Naga White	GH/Sb/001/15	Landrace/ Ghana	I.D.K. Atopkle, CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Improved variety of the Caudatum race; Early maturing (95days); Photo-period insensitive; Erect, closed panicle shape; Plant colour: Pigmented; Seed colour: Chalky with soft endosperm.	Potential yield: 5.0 MT/ha; Tolerant to drought; Resistant to most foliar diseases; Susceptible to head bug grain mould complex particularly if maturity coincides with heavy rainfall.	Sudan–north Guinean	Pure line	1971	2015
Kadaga	GH/Sb/002/15	Landrace/ Ghana	CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Improved local variety with of the Guinean race; Plant colour: Pigmented; Maturity: 100 – 110 days; Photo-period insensitive; Panicle shape: Loose and drooping; Seed colour: brown with black glumes.	Potential yield: 2.5MT/ha; Suitable for brewing pito and lager beer; Susceptible to shoot fly; Resistance to most leaf diseases.	Sudan–north Guinean	Pure line	1971	2015
Framida	GH/Sb/003/15	Landrace/ Ghana	CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Improved variety of the Caudatum race. Panicle shape: very closed and erect; Plant colour: pigmented; Seed colour: Red. Maturity: 100 to 110 days; Photo-period insensitive.	Potential yield:3.0 MT/ha; Tolerant to striga hermonthica; Suitable for brewing pito and lager beer; Susceptible to head bug grain mould complex particularly if maturity coincides with heavy rainfall.	Sudan–north Guinean	Pure line	1980	2015
Kapaala	GH/Sb/004/15	Landrace/ Ghana	CSIR-SARI/ ICRISAT	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Improved variety of the Caudatum race; Maturity: 100-110 days; Photo-period insensitive; Plant colour: Tan; panicle shape: Semi-compact and erect; Seed colour: white with colourless glumes.	Potential yield:4.0 MT/ha; Very good food, malting and brewing qualities; Susceptible to head bug grain mould complex particularly if maturity coincides with heavy rainfall.	Sudan–north Guinean savannahs	Pure line, developed from a three way cross and originally coded as (ICSV 111).	1996	2015
Dorado	GH/Sb/005/15	Landrace/ Ghana	CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Improved variety of the Caudatum race; Maturity: 110-115 days; Photo-period insensitive; Plant colour: Tan; Panicle shape: compact and erect; Seed colour: white with red glumes; Plant height: 1.3 – 1.5m.	Potential yield:3.50 MT/ha; Very good food, malting and brewing qualities; Susceptible to head bug grain mould complex particularly if maturity coincides with heavy rainfall.	Sudan–north Guinean	Pure line	1996	2015

LEGUMES

COMMON BEAN

SPECIES: *Phaseolus vulgaris*

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Crops- Adays	GH/Pv/001/19	CIAT-Uganda	J. Y. Asibuo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Seed coat colour: white; Seed shape: Oval; Seed coat patterns: Absent; Helium Colour: Absent; Colour of standard flower: White; Flower bud per inflorescence: 4; Hypocotyl pigmentation: Green; Colour of emerging hypocotyl: Very pale green; Leaf Persistence: Intermediate; Pod Colour: Normal green; Pod Curvature: Slightly curved; Pod Suture String: Few strings	Canning quality: good; Early maturing (60-65 days after sowing); Grain yield- 1.3 ton/ha.	Transition and Forest	(ICA BUNSI x SXB 405)	2016	2019
Crops- Ennepa	GH/Pv/002/19	CIAT-Uganda	J. Y. Asibuo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Seed coat colour: white; Seed shape: Kidney shape; Seed coat patterns: Absent Helium Colour: Absent; Colour of standard flower: White; Flower buds per inflorescence:3; Hypocotyl pigmentation: Green; Colour of Hypocotyl: Very pale green; Leaf Persistence: Intermediate; Pod Colour: Normal green; Pod Curvature: Slightly curved; Pod Suture String: Few strings	Canning quality: good; Early maturing (60-65 days after sowing); Grain yield-2.1 tons/ha	Transition and Forest	(ICA BUNSI x SXB 405)	2016	2019
Crops- Sernahya	GH/Pv/003/19	CIAT-Uganda	J. Y. Asibuo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Seed coat colour: Brown; Seed shape: Cuboid; Seed coat patterns: Absent ; Helium Colour: White with yellow circle; Colour of standard flower: White; Flower bud per inflorescence:3; Hypocotyl pigmentation: Green; Hypocotyl: Very pale green; Leaf Persistence: Intermediate; Pod Colour: Normal green; Pod Curvature: Curved; Pod Suture String: Stringless	Early maturing (60-65 days after sowing); High iron and zinc content (Iron :77 ppm and Zinc 37 ppm); Grain yield:1.9 ton/ha.	Transition and Forest		2016	2019
Crops- Nsoroma	GH/Pv/004/19	CIAT-Uganda	J. Y. Asibuo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Seed coat colour: Red; Seed shape: Kidney shaped; Seed coat patterns: Constant mottled; Helium Colour: White Colour of standard flower: White with lilac edge; Flower bud per inflorescence:3; Hypocotyl pigmentation: Purple; Hypocotyl: Red Leaf Persistence: All leaves dropped; Pod Colour: Pale red stripes on green; Pod Curvature: Slightly curved; Pod Suture String: Stringless	Early maturing (60-65 days after sowing) Tolerant to diseases; Grain yield: 1.3 ton/ha	Transition and Forest	(SXB743 X MIB499)	2016	2019

COWPEA

SPECIES: *Vigna unguiculata* L Walp.

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/Source	Breeder (s)/Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Vallenga	GH/Vu/001/15	Landrace/Ghana	K. O. Marfo <i>et al</i> ; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth habit: Erect; Growth pattern: semi-determinate and vinery; Flower colour: White with purple petals; Position of pods- above canopy; Pods per peduncle: two (2); Seed coat colour: red; Colour of helium : black.	High grain/fodder yields. Dual purpose.Early maturing (60 days after sowing)	Sahel, Sudan, derived, Guinea savannah zones	Pure line	1985	2015
Bengpla	GH/Vu/002/15	Landrace/Ghana	K. O. Marfo <i>et al</i> ; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth habit: Erect; Growth pattern : determinate; Flower colour : white with purple petals, Position of pods : within canopy; Number of pods per peduncle: two (2); Seed coat color : white; Colour of helium : black.	High grain/fodder yields but susceptible to cowpea stem rot; extra-early maturing (55-60 days after sowing)	Guinea savannah zones and humid areas	Pure line	1992	2015
Marfo-tuya	GH/Vu/003/15	Landrace/Ghana	K. O. Marfo, F. Padi and I.D.K. Atokple; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth habit: Erect; Growth pattern: semi-determinate; Flower colour : white with purple petals; Position of pods: within canopy; Number of pods per peduncle: two (2); Seed coat color: dull cream luster; Colour of helium : brown.	High fodder/grain yield in soils of low fertility, tolerant to heat during reproductive development and resistant to <i>S. gesnerioides</i> ; Medium maturing (66-70 days after sowing);100seed weight-17g.	Guinea and Sudan savannah zones.	Sumbrisogla/ 518-2	2004	2015
Apaagbala	GH/Vu/004/15	Landrace/Ghana	K. O. Marfo, F. Padi and I.D.K. Atokple; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth habit: Erect; Growth pattern: determinate; Position of pods: above the canopy; Number of pods per peduncle: three (3); Seed coat color: white; Colour of helium: black	High fodder/grain yield, susceptible to Striga and aphids; Matures in 64-67 days;100 seed weight-22.0g.	Sahel, Sudan, derived, Guinea savannah zones	Prima/TVU 4552//CBE	2004	2015
Padi-tuya	GH/Vu/005/15	Landrace/Ghana	I.D.K. Atokple and F. Padi; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth habit: erect; Flower colour: white with purple marks; Colour of mature pods: brown; Number of pods per peduncle: three (3); Position of pods: slightly above canopy; Seed shape: Globose to kidney; Seed coat colour: white; Colour of helium: black; Number of Seed per pod: 10.	It moderately resistant to insects, diseases and striga. The percent harvest in total yield (determinacy) is moderate about 72%; Matures in 64-67 days;100 seed weight as 22.0g.	Sahel, Sudan, derived, Guinea savannah zones and humid areas	SARC 3-122-2	2008	2015
Songotra	GH/Vu/006/15	Landrace/Ghana	I.D.K. Atokple and F. Padi; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth habit: erect; Flower colour: white with purple marks; Colour of mature pods: brown; Number of pods per peduncle: three (3); Position of pods: slightly above canopy; Seed shape: globose; Seed coat colour: creamy white; Colour of helium: black. Number of seeds per pod: 11.	While it is highly resistant to striga, it is moderately resistant to most insects, diseases and susceptible to aphids. The percent harvest in total yield (determinacy) is high about 85%;Matures in 62-65 days; 100 seed weight as 15.0g.	Sahel, Sudan and Savannah zones	Pure line IT97K-499-35	2008	2015

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Bawutawuta	GH/Wu/007/15	Landrace/ Ghana	I.D.K. Atokple and F. Padi; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth habit: erect; Flower colour: white with purple marks; Colour of mature pods: brown; Number of pods per peduncle: pods: 3.5. Position of pods: Mostly within canopy; Seed shape: Globose; Seed coat colour : Creamy white; Colour of helium: brown. Number of seeds per pod: 12.	While it is highly resistant to striga, it is moderately resistant to most insects, diseases and susceptible to aphids. The percent harvest in total yield (determinacy) is high about 85%; Medium matruing; 100 seed weight as 14.8g.	Sahel, Sudan, derived, Guinea savannah zones.	Pure line IT95K-193-2	2008	2015
Zaayura	GH/Wu/008/15	Landrace/ Ghana	N. N. Denwar et al; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth habit: erect; Flower colour: white with purple marks; Colour of mature pods: brown; Number of pods per peduncle: pods: three (3); Position of pods: Mostly slightly above canopy; Seed shape: Globose.; Seed coat colour: creamy white; Colour of helium : brown; Number of Seed per pod: 10	While it is highly resistant to aphids, it is moderately resistant to other insects, diseases and striga. The percent harvest in total yield (determinacy) is moderate about 65%;Matures in 64-67 days; 100 seed weight as 22.5g.	Sahel, Sudan, Guinea savannah zones.	SARC 4-75 Pure line	2008	2015
Hewale	GH/Wu/009/15	Landrace/ Ghana	H. Adu-Dapaah, S.N.T.T Addy; CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: Semi erect; Growth pattern: Semi-determinate; Raceme position: Mostly above canopy; Leaf colour: Pale Green Leaf texture; Membranous Flower colour: White; Pod attachment to peduncle: 30-90 degrees down from erect; Seed shape: Rhomboid; Testa texture: Smooth; rough; Eye Colour: Brown; Seed coat colour: White.	Reaction to diseases: Moderately tolerant to Cercospora leaf spot and other important diseases.; Reaction to insect-pests: Moderately; tolerant to insect- pests especially thrips; Market premium: High; Nodule score: 2.9; Days of flowering: 40 – 46 days; Days to maturity: (64-72 days); Grain Yield (potential):3130 kg/ha	Forest Transition Coastal Savannah		2012	2015
Videza	GH/Wu/009/15	Landrace/ Ghana	H. Adu-Dapaah, S.N.T.T Addy; CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: Semi erect; Growth pattern: Semi-determinate; Terminal leaflet shape: Sub-globose; Raceme position: Mostly above canopy; Leaf colour: Intermediate green; Leaf texture: Membranous; Flower colour: White; Pod attachment to peduncle: 30°-90° down from erect; Seed shape: Ovoid; Testa texture: Smooth; Eye Colour: Black; Seed coat colour: White	Days of flowering: 43 to 47 days; Days to maturity: 68-77 days; Grain Yield (potential): 3043kg/ha; Market premium: High; Reaction to diseases: Moderately tolerant to Cercospora leaf spot and other important diseases.; Reaction to insect-pests: Moderately tolerant to insect- pests especially thrips; Nodule Score: 3; Biomass: 3.5 t/ha (Dual-purpose)	Forest, Transition & Coastal savannah		2012	2015

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Asomdwee	GH/Vu/010/15	Landrace/ Ghana	H. Adu-Dapaah, S.N.T.T Addy; CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: Semi erect; Growth pattern: Semi-determinate; Terminal leaflet shape: Globose; Raceme position: In upper canopy; Leaf colour: Intermediate green; Leaf texture: Membranous; Flower colour: White; Pod attachment to peduncle: 30-90° down from erect; Seed shape: Globose; Testa texture: Smooth; Eye Colour: Black; Seed coat colour: White	Reaction to diseases: Moderately tolerant to Cercospora leaf spot and other important diseases.; Reaction to insect-pests: Moderately tolerant to insect- pests especially thrips; Threshing %: 66.8%; Biomass: 2.2; Nodule score:2.8; Market premium: Medium high; Days of flowering: 40 to 46 days; Days to maturity: 65-72 days; Grain Yield (potential): 2863 kg/ha	Forest & Savannah, Coastal savannah		2012	2015
Crops - Hans Adua	GH/Vu/001/16	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	S. Amoah, S.N.T.T Addy, J.Y. Asibuo, H. Adu-Dapaah; CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: Intermediate; Plant height: 36cm. Raceme position: Mostly within upper canopy; Leaf colour: intermediate green; Terminal leaf shape : globose with average length of 5.3cm (six weeks after planting). Seed shape: kidney; Seed coat texture : smooth; Seed coat colour: white; Colour of helium: tan brown; Seed size : 237.12 cm ³	The genotype CRI-11(8)-1 is early maturing. It flowers in 38-40 days after planting and matures in 65-67 days. It is resistant/ tolerant to most insect pests of cowpea especially Thrips. It is high yielding with yield potential of 3500 kg/ha (3.5t/ha) which is approximately 10% higher than the highest yielding improved variety (Hewale). It is tolerant to most cowpea diseases especially Cercospora Leaf spot disease and Anthracnose	Forest-Savannah Transition zone, Guinea Savannah zone, Forest zone and the coastal savannah zone	Marfo Tuya x Nhyira	2015	2016
Crops- Agyenkwa	GH/Vu/002/16	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	S. Amoah, S.N.T.T Addy, J.Y. Asibuo, H. Adu-Dapaah; CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: semi-erect. Plant height: 30cm. Raceme position: mostly above canopy. Twining tendency: slight; Leaf colour: dark green with conspicuous markings; Leaf texture: intermediate; Terminal Leaflet shape: sub hastate (5.0cm in length six weeks after planting); Seed shape : ovoid; Seed coat texture: smooth; Seed coat colour: white; Colour of helium.	Genotype CRI-11(9)-2 is and early maturing genotype (62-64 days). It flowers from 34 to 38 days after planting. The earliness is a good adaptation strategy to drought stress. It is tolerant to most cowpea pests including Thrips, Aphids and Maruca. It is resistant/ tolerant to Cercospora Leaf spot disease and has yield potential of 3300 kg/ha. It is fairly tolerant to drought and well adapted to the transition agro-ecological zone in Ghana. It is good to taste and has high market premium.	Forest-Savannah Transition zone, Guinea Savannah zone, Forest zone and the coastal savannah zone	Sanzisanbili x Asetenapa	2015	2016

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Nketewada	GH/Vu/003/16	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	S. Amoah, S.N.T.T Addy, J.Y. Asibuo, H. Adu-Dapaah; CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: semi-erect; Plant height: 27.4cm. Twining tendency: slight; Raceme position: mostly above canopy; Leaf colour: dark green with conspicuous markings; Terminal leaf shape : sub hastate with average length of 5.14 six weeks after planting; Seed shape: rhomboid; Seed coat texture: smooth to rough; Seed coat colour: white; Colour of helium: black; seed size: 230mm ³	The genotype CRI-11 (9)-3 was preferred by farmers due to its taste. It is early maturing and resistant/ tolerant to most cowpea pests. It flowers from 35-42 days after planting and matures in 62-65 days. It is tolerant to most cowpea diseases especially Cercospora Leaf spot disease and Antracnose. It has a potential yield of 3200kg/ha. It has the highest	Forest-Savanna Transition zone, Guinea Savannah zone, Forest zone and the coastal savannah zone	Sanzisanbili x Asetenapa	2015	2016
Zamzam	GH/Vu/004/16	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	S. Amoah, S.N.T.T Addy, J.Y. Asibuo, H. Adu-Dapaah; CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: semi-erect; twinning tendency: intermediate; Plant height: 31.2cm; Position of racemes: mostly above canopy; leaf colour: dark green with conspicuous markings; terminal leaf shape : sub hastate (4.77cm in length); petiole pigmentation: purple coloration at the base; seed shape: rhomboid; Seed coat texture: smooth; seed coat colour : white; Helium colour: tan brown; seed size: 301.9mm ³	The genotypes is well adapted to the transition zone. It flowers in 38-40 days and matures in 64-67 days. It is moderately tolerant to cercospora leaf spot and anthracnose. It has high iron content and is resistant/tolerant to most cowpea pests especially thrips and maruca.	Forest-Savannah Transition zone, Guinea Savannah zone, Forest zone and the coastal savannah zone	Marfo Tuja x Nhyira	2015	2016
Soo-Sima (Sweet cowpea)	GH/Vu/005/16	Ghana	F. Kusi, F. Padi, M. Haruna, I.D.K Atokple, E.Y Owusu, R.Y. Agyare (CSIR-SARI); S.N.T.T. Addy (CSIR-CRI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Plant habit: erect with few vines; Growth pattern: determinate; Leaf type: medium size thick leaves; Flowers colour: violet; Position of pods: Mostly slightly above canopy; Number of pods per peduncle: 3; Colour of matured pods: brown; Pod shape: slightly curved; Number of seed per pod: 11; Seed coat colour: creamy white; Helium colour: brown; Seed shape: ovoid; Seed texture: rough; Seed size: medium	Potential grain yield: 2.0 t/ha; Potential biomass yield: 4.2 t/ha; Days to physiological maturity: (67-70 DAP); Highly resistant to Aphis craccivora; Tolerant to Striga gesnerioides; Highly tolerant to drought; Resistant to Macrophormina diseases; Protein content: 20.05 g/100g; Iron: 5.2 mg/100g; 100 seed weight - 14g	Guinea, Sudan savannah, Transitional, Coastal Savanna and Forest zones	Nhyira X SARC 1-57-2	2016	2016

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Diffeele (Good Soup – as leafy vegetable)	GH/Vu/006/16	Ghana	F. Kusi, F. Padi, M. Haruna, I.D.K Atokple, E.Y Owusu, R.Y. Agyare. (CSIR-SARI); S. N.T.T Addy (CSIR-CRI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth habit : erect; Growth pattern : determinate; Leaf type : medium size thick leaves; Flower colour- whitish cream; Physiological maturity : medium maturing (67-70 DAP); Position of pods : majority are slightly above canopy; Mean number of pods : 3; Colour of matured pods : brown; Shape of pod : slightly curved; Mean number of seed/ pod : 11; Seed coat colour : white; Helium colour : back; Seed shape : ovoid; Seed texture : rough; Seed size : medium; Mean 100 seed weight : 16 g	Potential grain yield: 2.2 t/ ha; Potential biomass yield: 5.1 t/ha; Good as leafy vegetable; Highly resistant to <i>Aphis craccivora</i> ; Tolerant to <i>Striga gesnerioides</i> ; Highly tolerant to drought; Protein content : 22.46 g/100g; Iron: 4.9 mg/100g	Guinea, Sudan savannah, Transitional, Coastal Savannah and Forest zones	Asetenapa X SARC 1-57-2	2016	2016
Wang Kae (No Striga)	GH/Vu/007/16	Ghana	F. Kusi, F. Padi, M. Haruna, I.D.K Atokple, E.Y Owusu, R.Y. Agyare(CSIR-SARI),	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth habit: erect with few vines (Semi spreading); Growth pattern: determinate; Leaf type: small trifoliolate; Flower colour: white; Position of pods: majority are slightly above canopy; Mean number of pods: 3 pods per peduncle; Colour of matured pods: brown; Mean number of seed/ pod: 16; Seed coat colour: white; Helium colour: brown; Seed shape: kidney; Seed texture: rough; Seed size: medium	Potential grain yield: 2.4 t ha ⁻¹ ; Potential biomass yield: 4.0 t/ha; Physiological maturity: early maturing (65 DAP); Highly resistant to <i>Aphis craccivora</i> ; Resistant to <i>Striga gesnerioides</i> ; Moderately tolerant to drought and Macrophomina disease; Protein content: 23.11 g/100g; Iron: 2.53 mg/100g; Mean 100 seed weight: 18.5 g	Guinea, Sudan savannah, Transitional, Coastal Savannah and Forest zones	IT99K-573- 1-1 X SARC 1-57-2	2016	2016
Kirkhouse Benga -1	GH/Vu/008/16	Ghana	F. Kusi, F. Padi, M. Haruna, I.D.K Atokple, E.Y Owusu, R.Y. Agyare (CSIR-SARI),	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth habit: erect with no vines; Growth pattern: determinate; Leaf type: small trifoliolate; Flower colour: white with purple marks; Position of pods: majority are slightly above canopy; Mean number of pods: 3 pods per peduncle; Colour of matured pods: brown; Mean number of seed/ pod:16; Seed coat colour: white; Helium colour: black; Seed shape: kidney; Seed texture: rough; Seed size: medium	Potential grain yield: 2.4 t/ ha; Potential biomass yield: 3.9 t/ha; Days to physiological Maturity: early (62- 65 DAP); Mean 100 seed weight:18.5 g; Highly resistant to <i>Aphis craccivora</i> ; Resistant to <i>Striga gesnerioides</i> ; Moderately tolerant to drought; Protein content: 23.88 g/100g; Iron content: 6.08 mg/100g	Guinea, Sudan savannah, Transitional, Coastal Savannah and Forest zones	IT99K-573- 2-1 X SARC 1-57-2	2016	2016

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/Source	Breeder (s)/Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Yor-kpitio	GH/Vu/001/19	Ghana	A. T. Asare, E. Asare-Bediako, I.K.A. Galyuon (University of Cape Coast); F. Kusi (CSIR-SARI); F. Padi (CRIG); L. M. Aboagye (CSIR-PGRRI)	University of Cape Coast, Ghana	Growth habit: Intermediate; Growth pattern: Determinate; Plant: Anthocyanin pigmentation present at nodes, base and tip of petiole; Foliage colour: Pale green; Flower colour: White; Seed shape: Rhomboid; Seed coat colour: white; Plant photosensitivity: neutral; Receme position: mostly above canopy, moderately uniform drying pods	Potential grain yield: 4.8 t/ha Physiological Maturity: 59 days (early). Plant height: 25.5cm. Days to 50 % flowering- 43 days (early); Dual purpose (grain and fodder production). Protein content: 25.9 %. Selenium: 67.0 mg100g-1 Zinc: 16.6 mg100g-1 100:seed weight: 17.1g, Good cooking characteristics: preparing gari and beans, waakye, koose, agawu, and stew, gable, nyonbeeka, tubani, gora, and nagbechingie. Disease : tolerant to Rust and Cowpea mosaic disease) Drought : highly tolerant	Coastal savannah, Forest-Savannah Transition, Semi-deciduous forest	IT97K-499-35 x Apagbaala	2019	2019
Asare-moya	GH/Vu/002/19	Ghana	A. T. Asare, E. Asare-Bediako, I.K.A. Galyuon (University of Cape Coast); F. Kusi (CSIR-SARI); F. Padi (CRIG); L. M. Aboagye (CSIR-PGRRI)	University of Cape Coast, Ghana	Growth habit: Intermediate; Growth pattern: Indeterminate spreading; Plant: Anthocyanin pigmentation present at nodes, base and tip of petiole; Foliage colour: Pale green; Flower colour: Purple. Seedshape:Rhomboid; Seed coat colour: White; Plant photosensitivity: neutral; Receme position: mostly above canopy.	Potential grain yield: 2.0 t/ha; Physiological Maturity: 51 days (very early).Plant height: 30.0 cm; Days to 50% flowering: 37 days (very early) Dual purpose (grain and fodder production); Protein content: 26.6%; Carbohydrate-47.2%; Potassium: 300.8mg100g-1; Phosphorus: 6.2mg100-1; Sodium: 101.6mg100g-1; Magnesium-139.4;mg100g-1; Selenium: 21.1mg100g-1; Zinc: 15.6 mg100g-1; Calcium: 6.7mg100g-1; Copper: 12.7mg100g-1; Iron: 10.0mg100g-1; 100: seed weight: 17.2 g; Resistant to multiple races of Striga gesnerioides; Resistant to root rot; Diseases and pest: tolerant; Drought: Highly tolerant.	Sudan savannah, Guinea savannah, Coastal savannah	IT97K-499-35 x SARC-LO2	2019	2019

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Aduapa	GH/Vu/003/19	Ghana	A. T. Asare, E. Asare-Bediako, I.K.A. Galyuon (University of Cape Coast); F. Kusi (CSIR-SARI); F. Padi (CRIG); L. M. Aboagye (CSIR-PGRRI)	University of Cape Coast, Ghana	Growth habit: intermediate; Growth pattern: determinate; Plant: Anthocyanin pigmentation present at nodes, base and tip of petiole; Foliage colour: Intermediate green; Flower colour: White; Seed shape: Kidney; Seed coat colour: White; Plant photosensitivity: neutral; Receme position: mostly within canopy, continuous flowering and fruiting.	Potential grain yield- 4.5 t/ha; Physiological Maturity: 58 days (early); Days to 50% flowering: 42 days (early); Plant height: 31.6 cm; Dual purpose (grain and fodder); Protein content: 24.9 %; Carbohydrate: 54 %; Potassium:300.8mg100g-1; Sodium: 85.4mg100g-1; Magnesium:140.7mg100g-1; Selenium: 22.0mg100g-1; Zinc: 13.9 mg100g-1; Calcium: 7.9mg100g-1; Copper: 9.7 mg100g-1; Iron: 12.6mg100g-1; 100: seed weight: 16.6g; Good cooking characteristics: preparing gari and beans, waakye, koose, agawu, and stew,gable, nyonbeeka, tubani, gora, and nagbechinge. Diseases and pest tolerant; Drought: highly tolerant.	Coastal savannah and Forest-Savannah Transition.	IT97K-499-35 x Apagbaala	2019	2019
UCC-Early	GH/Vu/004/19	Ghana	A. T. Asare, E. Asare-Bediako I.K.A. Galyuon J.P.Tetteh (University of Cape Coast); F. Kusi (CSIR-SARI); L. M. Aboagye (CSIR-PGRRI)	University of Cape Coast, Ghana	Days to 50 % flowering: 35 days (very early); Physiological Maturity: 52 days (very early); Plant: Anthocyanin pigmentation present at nodes, base and tip of petiole; Foliage colour: Intermediate green; Flower colour: Purple; Seed shape: Rhomboid; Seed coat colour: Golden brown Plant photosensitivity: neutral; Receme position: Mostly above canopy, uniform drying of pod.	Potential grain yield: 4.1 t/ha; Plant height: 37.7 cm; Protein content: 23.6 %; Carbohydrate: 58.0 %; Potassium: 305.7 mg100g-1; Sodium: 97.6 mg100g-1; Magnesium: 143.3mg100g-1; Selenium: 42.2mg100g-1; Zinc- 216 mg100g-1; Calcium: 10.7mg100g-1; Copper: 16.7 mg100g-1; Iron: 6.1mg100g-1; 100: seed weight: 14.0g; Good cooking characteristics: preparing gari and beans, waakye, koose, agawu, and stew, gable, nyonbeeka, tubani, gora, and nagbechinge. Diseases and pest tolerant. Drought: Tolerant.	Coastal savannah, Forest-Savannah Transition, Semi-deciduous forest	Induced landrace	2019	2019

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/Source	Breeder (s)/Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Aluba-kpole	GH/Vu/005/19	IITA	A. T. Asare, E. Asare-Bediako I.K.A. Galyuon (University of Cape Coast); F. Kusi (CSIR-SARI); F. Padi (CRIG); L. M. Aboagye (CSIR-PGRRI)	University of Cape Coast, Ghana	Growth habit: Indeterminate; Growth pattern: determinate; Anthocyanin pigmentation: present at nodes, base and tip of petiole; Foliage colour: Pale green; Flower colour: Purple; Seed shape: Kidney; Seed coat colour: Reddish brown; Plant photosensitivity: neutral; Receme position: mostly above canopy.	Potential grain yield: 3.3 t/ha; Plant height: 33.0 cm; Days to 50 % flowering: 41 days (very early); Physiological Maturity: 56 days; Dual purpose (grain and fodder production); Protein content; 31.9 %; Carbohydrate:47.0 %; Potassium-300.8mg100g-1; Phosphorus: 5.4mg100-1; Sodium: 93.5mg100g-1; Magnesium-142.0mg100g-1; Selenium- 55.0mg100g-1; Zinc: 20,5 mg100g-1; Calcium: 10.7mg100g-1; Copper: 16.7 mg100g-1; Iron: 11.1 mg100g-1; 100: seed weight: 21.3 g, Good cooking characteristics: preparing gari and beans, waakye, koose, agawu, and stew, gable, nyonbeeka, Resistant to Striga gesnerioides; Diseases and pest tolerant; Drought: moderately tolerant.	Coastal savannah, Forest-Savannah Transition, Semi-deciduous forest	IT10K-819-4	2019	2019
Saka-Buro	GH/Vu/006/19	Ghana	A. T. Asare, E. Asare-Bediako I.K.A. Galyuon (University of Cape Coast); F. Kusi (CSIR-SARI); F. Padi (CRIG); L. M. Aboagye (CSIR-PGRRI)	University of Cape Coast, Ghana	Growth habit: intermediate; Growth pattern: indeterminate; Anthocyanin pigmentation: present at nodes, base and tip of petiole; Foliage colour: Intermediate green; Flower colour: White; Seed shape: Kidney; Seed coat colour: White Plant photosensitivity: neutral; Receme position: mostly above canopy.	Potential grain yield:3.3t/ha; Plant height: 35.0 cm; Days to 50 % flowering: 42days (early); Physiological Maturity: 58 days (early); Dual purpose (grain and fodder production); Protein content: 27.5%; Carbohydrate: 49.6%; Potassium: 282.9mg100g-1; Phosphorus: 5.8 mg100-1; Sodium: 97.6mg100g-1; Magnesium:141.2mg100g-1; Selenium: 39.0mg100g-1; Zinc: 18.8 mg100g-1; Calcium: 14.1mg100g-1; Copper: 9.4 mg100g-1; 100: seed weight: 17.0 g; Good cooking characteristics: preparing gari and beans, waakye, koose, agawu, gable,nyonbeeka, tubani, gora, and nagbechinge. Resistant to multiple races of Striga gesnerioides; Resistant to root rot; Resistant to aphids; Diseases and pest tolerant; Drought: Highly tolerant.	Sudan savannah, Guinea savannah, Coastal savannah	IT97K-499-35 x SARC-L02	2019	2019

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Kum-Zoya	GH/Vu/007/19	Ghana	A. T. Asare, E. Asare-Bediako I.K.A. Galyuon (University of Cape Coast); F. Kusi (CSIR-SARI); F. Padi (CRIG); L. M. Aboagye (CSIR-PGRI)	University of Cape Coast, Ghana	Growth habit: intermediate; Growth pattern: indeterminate; Anthocyanin pigmentation present at nodes, base and tip of petiole; Foliage colour: Intermediate green; Flower colour: White; Seed shape: Rhomboid; Seed coat colour: White; Resistant to multiple races of Striga gesnerioides; Plant photosensitivity: photo-neutral; Receme position: mostly above canopy.	Potential grain yield: 2.3 t/ha; Plant height: 34.5 cm; Days to 50 % flowering: 40days (early); Physiological Maturity: 56days (early); Dual purpose (grain and fodder production); Protein content: 28.3%; Carbohydrate: 51.9%; Potassium: 317.1mg100g-1; Phosphorus: 5.0 mg100-1; Sodium: 85.4mg100g-1; Magnesium:138.4mg100g-1; Selenium: 48.0mg100g-1; Zinc: 17.4 mg100g-1; Calcium: 9.9mg100g-1; Copper: 10.4 mg100g-1; 100: seed weight: 16.8 g; Good cooking characteristics: preparing gari and beans, waakye, koose, agawu, gable,nyonbeeka, tubani, gora, and nagbechinge. Resistant to root rot; Diseases and pests tolerant; Drought: Highly tolerant.	Sudan savannah, Guinea savannah, Coastal savannah	IT97K-499-35 x SARC-L02	2019	2019

GROUND NUTS

SPECIES: *Arachis hypogaea* L.

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Chinese (Shi tao chi)	GH/Ah/001/15	ICRISAT	CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth habit: erect; branching pattern: sequential; lacks stem pigmentation with scarce hair. Leaves are typically light green and has an oblanceolate shape. Pods are two seeded without a constriction. Seed coat colour: tan; 100 seed weight: 38g; lacks fresh seed dormancy.	Early maturing. Suitable for soup and all confectionery products; Matures in 90 days. The seeds contain 35% oil.	Guinea and Sudan savannah ecologies of Ghana		1980	2015
Manipintar	GH/Ah/002/15	ICRISAT	CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Seed colour- red and white	High yielding and resistant to foliar diseases. Suitable for commercial oil extraction; Requires 120 days to mature; Kernels contain about 47% oil	Guinea and Sudan savannah ecologies of Ghana		1986	2015
F-mix	GH/Ah/003/15	ICRISAT	K.O. Marfo; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	The seed color is tan with white shades.	Days to maturity; 120; oil content; 49%; Pod yield; 2.5 t/ha; It has very high level of tolerance to foliar diseases, e.g. Prosette, Cercospora and rust, leaf spot that are the major yield reducing factors of groundnut.	Guinea and Sudan savannah ecologies of Ghana		1986	2015
Sinkarzei	GH/Ah/004/15	ICRISAT	CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Matures in 102 days.. The seeds are red in color and contain about 45% oil.	The potential yield is 2.2 t/ha; Suitable for cultivation in all ecologies. Acceptable table quality and suitable for oil extraction.	It is adapted to the Guinea and Sudan savannah ecologies of Ghana	ICGS-114	1989	2015
Nkatiesari	GH/Ah/005/15	CSIR-SARI	A. Frimpong, F.K. Padi, J. Kombiok, A. B. Salifu, K.O. Marfo CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	It is a virginia botanical type peanut cultivar possessing alternate branching pattern. It has an erect growth habit, and medium green leaves. It matures in 110 days. The pods are typically two-seeded, slightly beaked, and the constriction between the seeds is slight. 100 seed weight of 50 g; light tan testa color; Contains 46% oil.	It is medium maturing. Has a high kernel yield with good fresh seed dormancy. It is resistant to early and late leafspot infections caused by <i>Cercospora arachidicola</i> S. Hori and <i>Cercosporidium personatum</i> (Berk. & Curt.) Deighton, respectively. It is suitable for oil extraction and good for making confectionery products.	It is adapted to the Guinea and Sudan savannah ecologies of Ghana	F5-derived line selected from a cross between 'F-mix' as the female parent and ICG(FDRS)-20 as the male parent.	2005	2015
Edorkpo-Munikpa	GH/Ah/006/15	CSIR-SARI	A. Frimpong, F.K. Padi, J. Kombiok, A. B. Salifu, K.O. Marfo CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Virginia botanical cultivar possessing alternate branching habit. It has a spreading-bunch growth habit with medium green leaves. Matures in 90 days. Yield approximately 2.0 t/ha The pods are typically two-seeded, slightly beaked, and the constriction between the seeds is slight with a 100 seed weight of 65 g. The seeds are medium sized with a dark tan testa color. Contains 48% oil.	Early maturity and suitable for all ecologies in northern Ghana. Suitable for oil extraction and confectionary products. Moderately resistant to early and late leaf spot infections caused by <i>Cercospora arachidicola</i> S. Hori and <i>Cercosporidium personatum</i> (Berk. & Curt.) Deighton, respectively.	Guinea and Sudan savannah ecologies of Ghana	F5-derived line selected from a cross between 'F-mix' as the female parent and ICGS 66 as the male parent.	2005	2015
Kpanieli	GH/Ah/007/15	ICRISAT	A. Frimpong, F.K. Padi, J. Kombiok, A. B. Salifu, K.O. Marfo CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Requires 120 days to mature. It has an alternate branching pattern. Pods are two-seeded and moderately beaked with a deep constriction between the kernels. Kernels have red testa color and a 100 seed weight of 67 g. The seed is composed of 51% oil.	High kernel yields (2.5 t/ha). Suitable for commercial oil extraction. Resistant to early and late leaf spot.	Guinea savannah ecology	ICGV 90084	2005	2015
Gusie-Balin	GH/Ah/008/15	ICRISAT	A. Frimpong, F.K. Padi, J. Kombiok, A. B. Salifu, K.O. Marfo CSIR-SARI	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Branching pattern; Alternate; Seeds/ Pod; 2; Beakness; Slight; Pod constriction; None; Seed color; Tan;	Early maturing. Resistant to leaf spot infections. 1000 seed weight: 700 g; High yielding (2.0 t/ha). Suitable for a range of confectionery products; Oil content; 46%.		ICGV 92099	2005	2015

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CRI-Nkosour	GH/Ah/009/15	ICRISAT	H.K. Adu-Dapaah, J.Y. Asibuo, S. Amoah, B. Asafo Agyei (CSIR- CRI)	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: semi-erect; Pubescence: on both stem and leaf. Flower colour: Orange: yellow; Pods/plant: 40; Plant height: 18.1cm; Leaf colour: dark green; Leaf shape: elliptic; Seeds/Pod: two; Beakness: moderate (2.9 cm X 1.4 cm); Pod constricted: moderate; Seed colour: Tan; Seed length: 14.06 mm; Seed width: 7.82 mm.	Confectionery. Protein (%): 27.53±0.01; Fat (%): 48.84±0.32, Ash (%): 2.50±0.02, Carbohydrates (%): 21.13±0.40, Energy (Kcal/100g): 591.12; Phosphorus (mg/100g): 267.2±6.4; Calcium (mg/100g): 402.6±8.2; Iron (mg/100g): 2.62±0.06; 1000 seed weight: 473.1 g; Pod yield: 2.3 t/ha	All agro-ecologies in Ghana	M578-79	2005	2015
CRI-Adepa	GH/Ah/010/15	ICRISAT	J. Y. Asibuo, H.K. Adu-Dapaah, S. Amoah (CSIR-CRI)	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: semi-erect; Pubescence: some have pubescence on both the stem and the leaf. Flower colour: orange: yellow; Pods/plant: 47; Plant height: 17.0cm. Leaf colour: dark green; Leaf shape: Obovate narrow; Seeds/pod: two (2); Beakness: moderate (2.8 cm x 1.3 cm); Pod constriction: slight; Seed colour: light brown, Seed length: 14.01 ± 0.86, Seed width: 8.54 ± 0.75.	High Oil Protein (%): 26.28±0.14, Fat (%): 49.86±0.44, Ash (%): 2.78±0.23, Carbohydrates (%): 21.07±0.89, Energy (Kcal/100g): 595.12; Phosphorus (mg/100g): 361.8±2.8; Calcium (mg/100g): 371.9±6.6; Iron (mg/100g): 2.09±0.02; 1000 seed weight: 503.9 g; Pod yield: 2.4 t/ha	Forest and Coastal Savannah zones	M576-79	2005	2015
CRI-Azivivi	GH/Ah/011/15	ICRISAT	H.K. Adu-Dapaah, J.Y. Asibuo, S. Amoah, B. Asafo Agyei (CSIR- CRI)	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: semi-erect; Pubescence: some pubescence on both the stem and the leaf; Flower colour: orange-yellow; Pods/plant: 45; Plant height:15.7 cm; Leaf colour: dark green; Leaf shape: orbicular; Seeds/pod: two (2); Beakness: moderate (2.8 cm x 1.2 cm); Pod constriction: moderate; Seed colour: light brown; Seed length: 13.36 ± 0.80, mm Seed width: 8.72 ± 0.92 mm	Confectionery. Protein (%): 28.31±0.11, Fat (%): 46.41±0.08, Ash (%): 2.90±0.04, Carbohydrates (%): 22.37±0.42, Energy (Kcal/100g): 578.45; Phosphorus (mg/100g): 259.1±2.8; Calcium (mg/100g): 265.5±8.5; Iron (mg/100g): 4.22±0.04; 1000 seed weight: 505.0 g; Pod yield: 2.9 t/ha	All agro-ecologies in Ghana	RMP 12	2005	2015
CRI-Jenkaar	GH/Ah/012/15	ICRISAT	H.K. Adu-Dapaah, J.Y. Asibuo, S. Amoah, B. Asafo Agyei (CSIR- CRI)	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: semi-erect; Pubescence: present on both stem and leaf. Flower colour: orange: yellow. Pods/plant: 43; Plant height: 19.1 cm. Leaf colour-dark green; Leaf shape: oblong: elliptic; Seeds/pod: 2 Beakness: moderate (3.1cm x1.3cm); Pod constriction: moderate; Seed colour: tan; Seed length: 13.54± 1.13, Seed width: 8.03 ± 0.55	High Oil. Protein (%): 27.82±0.18, Fat (%): 51.13±0.17, Ash (%): 2.96±0.01, Carbohydrates (%): 18.08±0.40, Energy (Kcal/100g): 599.24; Phosphorus (mg/100g): 434.5±1.3; Calcium (mg/100g): 296.6±8.0; Iron (mg/100g): 2.13±0.06; 1000 seed weight: 469.1 g; Pod yield: 2.5 t/ha	Forest-Savannah Transition zone	MDR-8-19	2005	2015
Obolo	GH/Ah/013/15	ICRISAT	J. Y. Asibuo, H.K. Adu-Dapaah, S. Amoah, S.N.T.T Addy (CSIR- CRI)	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: semi-erect; Market type-Spanish; Leaf colour-Light green; Days to 50% flowering: 25; Flowering pattern : Sequential; Kernel lacks dormancy; Leaf shape: Cuneate; Pod diameter:1.8 cm; Pod length: 3.8 cm; Seed colour: tan; Seeds/pod: 2; Seed length:1.9; Seed diameter- 0.9; Pod width : 3.8 cm; Seed length :1.9cm; Seed width: 0.9 cm; Pod beak: Slight; Pod constriction-Moderate; Shelling percentage: 70	Zinc 2.79 (mg/100g); Iron 5.11 (mg/100g); Phosphorus 933.29(mg/100g); Calcium 384.77(mg/100g); Magnesium 777.73(mg/100g); % Moisture 5.3; % Ash 2.74; % Protein 28.6; % Fat 48.06; % Fibre 6.99; % Carbohydrate 8.3; % WBC 237.82; % Solubility 62.3; Swelling power 10.9; pH-6.61; 1000 seed weight -808g;; Pod yield-2.7 tons/ha;	Savannah, forest-savannah transition, semi deciduous forest	ICGV 97049	2012	2015
Yenyawoso	GH/Ah/014/15	ICRISAT	J. Y. Asibuo, H.K. Adu-Dapaah, S. Amoah, S.N.T.T Addy, M.K Owusu-Akyaw, M.B. Mochiah (CSIR-CRI); A. Mumuni (CSIR-SARI)	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: Semi-erect; Kernel lacks dormancy; Market type: Spanish; Leaf shape: Obovate; Leaf colour: Light green; Resistant to rust; Days to 50% flowering: 23; Pod length:3.0 cm; Pod diameter:1.3 cm; Seeds/pod:2; Seed colour: Dark Red; Pod beak-Slight; Pod constriction: Slight	% Moisture 5.6; % Ash 2.43; % Protein 29.85; % Fat 49.92; % Fibre 5.28; % Carbohydrate 6.92; % WBC 227.22; % Solubility 66.36; Swelling power 10.06; pH 6.81; Early maturity: 90 days; Zinc 3.52 (mg/100g); Iron 3.17 (mg/100g); Phosphorus 809.01 (mg/100g); Calcium 513.02 (mg/100g); Magnesium 972.16 (mg/100g); Oil content: 50%;1000 seed weight: 416g; Pod yield: 2.7 tons/ha	Savannah, forest-savannah transition, semi deciduous forest	ICG (X) SM 87057	2012	2015

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Oboshie	GH/Ah/015/15	ICRISAT	J. Y. Asibuo, H.K. Adu-Dapaah, S. Amoah, S.N.T.T Addy (CSIR-CRI)	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: Semi-erect; Leaf colour: Light green; Terminal leaf shape: Elliptic; Flowers on main stem; Flower pattern: sequential; Variety with monochrome testa only; Kernel: lack of dormancy; Market types: (Spanish); Leaf colour: Light green; Seed colour: brown; Days to 50% flowering: 26; Days to maturity:105-110; Pod length: 3.98cm; Pod width:1.85cm; Seed length: 2.09; seed diameter:1.20cm; Seeds/pod: 2; Pod beak: Slight; Pod constriction: Moderate; Shelling percentage: 67	Good flavour; Sweet taste; Confectionery; Zinc:2.56(mg/100g); Iron: 3.62(mg/100g); Phosphorus: 848.88(mg/100g); Calcium: 448.9(mg/100g); Magnesium: 330.53(mg/100g); % Moisture: 5.99; % Ash :2.48; % Protein: 34.13; % Fat: 46.49; % Fibre: 4.54; % Carbohydrate: 6.78; % WBC :266.15; % Solubility :61.09; Swelling power: 14.95; pH: 6.52; 1000 seed weight: 856 g; Pod yield: 2.6 tons/ha	Savannah, forest-savannah transition, semi deciduous forest	ICGV 98412	2012	2015
Otuhia	GH/Ah/016/15	ICRISAT	J. Y. Asibuo, H.K. Adu-Dapaah, S. Amoah, S.N.T.T Addy, M.K Owusu-Akyaw, M.B. Mochiah (CSIR-CRI); A. Mumuni (CSIR-SARI)	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: Spreading; Flowering pattern: Alternate; Kernel: dormancy; Market type: Virginia; Leaf shape:Obovate; Leaf colour:Dark green; Pod length: 27 mm; Pod diameter:12 mm; Seeds/pod :2; Seed colour: Tan; Resistant to: nematodes, rosette, rust, early leaf spot, late leaf spot; Days to 50% flowering: 27; Days to maturity:115-120.	Dual-purpose (seed and fodder); Zinc: 2.66(mg/100g); Iron: 3.2(mg/100g); Phosphorus: 809.01(mg/100g); Calcium: 513.02(mg/100g); Magnesium: 972.16(mg/100g); % Moisture: 5.42; % Ash :2.47; % Protein: 30.28; % Fat :49.44; % Fibre: 4.99; % Carbohydrate: 7.41; % WBC: 230.6; % Solubility:63.68; Swelling power:12.36; pH: 6.8; 1000 seed weight :724 g; Pod yield: 2.4 tons/ha	Savannah, forest-savannah transition, semi deciduous forest	ICGV 88709	2012	2015
SARINUT 1	GH/Ah/001/19	Texas A&M University and CSIR-SARI	N. N. Denwar and R. Oteng-Frimpong (CSIR-SARI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth habit : erect with sequential branching; Leaflet shape : Cuneate; Leaf colour : green; Peg pigmentation: pigmented; Pod constriction: very deep; Pod reticulation : moderate; Number of seeds per pod : two; Prominence of beak : slight; Seed coat color : deep red; Seed dormancy : present; Shelling percentage : 66%; 100 seed weight : 42.5 g.	Yield potential : 2.6 t/ha; Haulm yield: high; Days to maturity: 120; Disease resistance: resistance to early and late leaf spot; Oil content of kernel: 51%; Protein content : 25 %; Oil quality : High oleic; Uses : Confectionery and oil extraction; Crude Protein content in leaves: 12.2%; Shelling percentage: 66%	Guinea and Sudan savannah	"GAF 1723 GAF 1723 is an F5-derived progeny of crosses between a BC3 derivative of TxAG-6 and a high oleic peanut variety: Tamrun OLO2 x 43-09-03-02	2019	2019
SARINUT 2	GH/Ah/002/19	ICRISAT	N. N. Denwar and R. Oteng-Frimpong (CSIR-SARI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth habit : Erect with sequential branching; Leaflet shape : Oblanceolate; Leaf colour: light green; Peg pigmentation : pigmented; Pod constriction - Slight; Pod reticulation : moderate; Number of seeds per pod : two; Prominence of beak : absent; Seed coat colour : light tan; Seed dormancy : absent; Shelling percentage : 69%; 100 seed weight : 40.1 g.	Yield potential : 2.4 t/ha; Haulm yield : high; Days to maturity : 92; Disease tolerance : tolerant to early and late leaf spot; Oil content of kernel : 45%; Protein content : 36%; Uses: Confectionery; Crude Protein content in leaves : 11.3%; Shelling percentage : 69%	Guinea and Sudan savannah	Pure line	2019	2019
Crops-PION	GH/Ah/003/19	CSIR-CRI	J. Y. Asibuo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: Semi Erect; Flowering pattern: Sequential; Market type: Spanish; Leaf colour: Light green; Pod constriction: Shallow; Pod surface texture: Medium; Seeds/ Pod: 2 ; Beakness: Inconspicuous; Pod beak shape: Curved; Pod length: 28.10mm; Pod width: 13.40 mm; Kernel colour: Tan; Kernel shape: Spherical; Kernel size: Medium; Kernel dormancy: Absent; Kernel Length:13 mm; Kernel Width: 8 mm;	% Moisture: 5.94; % Ash: 2.09; % Protein: 33.32; % Fat: 44.52; % Fibre: 1.8; % Carbohydrate: 12.33; 1000 Seed weight: 464g; Pod yield: 2.8 t/ha; Maturity: Early (90 days)	Savannah, forest-Savannah transition, semi deciduous forest, Coastal Savannah	Aprewa x Azivivi	2019	2019

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Crops - Abakan	GH/Ah/004/19	CSIR-CRI	J. Y. Asibuo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: Semi-erect; Flowering: general pattern: Sequential, Flowering pattern main stem: Sequential; Market type: Spanish; Growth habit: Semi-erect; Plant branching: Medium; Maturity: Early (90-95 days); Leaflet size: Medium; Leaflet colour: Light green; Pod constrictions: Shallow; Pod surface texture: Medium; Pod Kernel Number: Few(2 or less); Pod Beak Prominence: Medium Prominent; Pod beak shape: Curved; Pod length: 31.00mm; Pod width: 12.70mm; Kernel colour: Monochrome(Red); Kernel shape: Cylindrical; Kernel size: Medium; Kernel dormancy: Absent; Kernel Length: 14.30mm; Kernel Width: 8.50mm; 100 kernel weight: 46.00g; 1000 Kernel weight: 456.00g	% Moisture: 5.57%; % Ash: 2.24%; % Protein: 30.37%; Fat: 48.83; % Fibre: 2.24%; Carbohydrate: 10.59; High Oil content	Savannah, forest-savannah transition, semi deciduous forest, Coastal Savannah	Nkatepa x Nkosour	2019	2019
Crops - Agbeyeye	GH/Ah/005/19	CSIR-CRI	J. Y. Asibuo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Flowering: general pattern: Sequential Flowering pattern main stem: Sequential; Market type: Spanish; Growth habit: Semi-erect; Plant branching: Medium; Maturity: Early (90-95 days); Leaflet size: Medium; Leaflet colour: Light green; Pod constrictions: Medium; Pod surface texture: Medium; Pod Kernel Number: Medium(Mostly 2), Pod Beak Prominence: Medium Prominent; Pod beak shape: Curved, Pod length: 28.10mm; Pod width: 13.40mm; Kernel colour: Monochrome(brown); Kernel shape: Spherical; Kernel size: Medium; Kernel dormancy: Absent; Kernel Length: 13.40mm; Kernel Width: 8.00mm; 100 kernel weight: 48.20g; 1000 Kernel weight: 451.00g	% Moisture: 6.63%; Ash: 2.12%; Protein: 32.68%; Fat: 47.75%; Fibre: 1.59%; Carbohydrate: 9.23; Pod yield: 2.3 t/ha; High Biomass: 4.2t/ha	Savannah, forest-savannah transition, semi deciduous forest, Coastal savannah	Chinese x Azivivi	2019	2019
Crops - Dehyee	GH/Ah/006/19	ICRISAT	J. Y. Asibuo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Flowering: general pattern- Sequential; Flowering pattern main stem: Sequential; Market type: Spanish; Growth habit: Semi-erect; Plant branching: Medium; Maturity: Early (85-90 days); Leaflet size: Medium; Leaflet colour: Light green; Pod constrictions: Shallow; Pod surface texture: Medium; Pod Kernel Number: Medium(Mostly 3); Pod Beak Prominence: Absent; Pod beak shape: Curved; Pod length: 22.30mm; Pod width: 13.00mm; Kernel colour: Monochrome(brown); Kernel shape: Spherical; Kernel size: Medium; Kernel dormancy: Absent; Kernel Length: 12.44mm; Kernel Width: 8.20mm; 100 kernel weight: 48.00g; 1000 Kernel weight: 447.00g	% Moisture: 5.82%; Ash: 2.24%; Protein: 35.37%; Fat: 50.53%; Fibre: 2.35%; Carbohydrate: 3.69; Pod yield: 2.9t/ha; Tolerant to Aflatoxins; Early maturity (85-90 days); High Oil content	Savannah, forest-savannah transtion, semi deciduous forest	Introduction from ICRISAT	2019	2019

SOYA BEAN

SPECIES: *Glycine max L. Merr.*

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Salintuya-I	GH/Gm/001/15	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	H. Quarshie, S. Akrofi (CSIR-SARI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth pattern: Determinate; flower colour: pink; Plant height: 45-55 cm; 1000 seed weight: 135 g; seed colour: cream.	Maturity:115 days; Days to 50% flowering: 50-55 days; Excellent seed quality; Tolerance to diseases: tolerant to bacterial pustule and Cercospora leaf spot; good trap-crop for S. hermonthica; yield (over 2.2 t/ha). Over 98% seed germination	Guinea & Sudan savannahs, transitional zone	Pure line	1985	2015
Salintuya-II	GH/Gm/002/15	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	H. Quarshie, S. Akrofi (CSIR-SARI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth pattern: Determinate flower colour: pink; plant height: 55-65 cm; 1000 seed weight:152 g; seed colour: cream.	Maturity: 130 days; Days to 50% flowering: 48-55 days; Excellent seed quality, high and stable yield across many environments; tolerant to common soybean pests and diseases; Potential yield: 3.2 t/ha; Over 98% seed germination,	Guinea & Sudan savannahs, transitional zone		1985	2015
Anidaso	GH/Gm/003/15	Landrace/ Ghana	B. Asafo Agyei (CSIR-CRI)	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Seed colour: cream; Hilium colour: light brown; 1000 seed weight: 96.08 + 8.2 g.	Medium maturing (105-115) yield: 1.2-2.8 ton/ha; NDFA 51-60; Protein(%)- 46.38±0.08; fat(%):16.45±0.07, Ash (%): 5.10±0.13; Carbohydrate(%): 32.07±0.32; Phosphorus (mg/100g): 596.9±14.1; Calcium (mg/100g):240.1±1.4; Iron(mg/100g): 11.67±0.28.	Guinea Savannah, Sudan Savannah, Transition and Coastal Savannah zones		1992	2015
Bengbie	GH/Gm/004/15	Landrace/ Ghana	B. Asafo Agyei (CSIR-CRI)	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Seed coat colour: Cream (with greenish tinge); hilium colour: light brown; 1000 seed weight: 94.05± 6.5.	Days to maturity: 100-110 days; yield: 1.2 -2.8 tons/ha; Moisture (%): 8.42±0.18, Protein (%): 40.85±0.13, Fat (%): 21.05±0.31, Ash (%): 5.54±0.14, Carbohydrates (%): 32.56±0.76, Energy (Kcal/100g): 450.1; Phosphorus (mg/100g): 618.0±2.8, Calcium (mg/100g): 220.6±4.2, Iron (mg/100g): 10.10±0.07.	Guinea Savannah, Sudan Savannah, Transition and Coastal Savannah zones		1992	2015
Jenguma	GH/Gm/005/15	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	N.N. Denwar, H. Quarshie (CSIR-SARI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth pattern: Determinate; Flower colour: purple; Plant height: 50-55 cm; 1000 seed weight: 140 g; seed colour: cream; Growth habit: erect; Pubescence: present on stems, leaves and pods; Pod position: along main stem; Hilium colour: light pink; Leaf type: trifoliolate.	Days to 50% flowering: 45-48; Days to maturity: 110-115; Yield potential: 2.5-2.8 t/ ha; Haulm yield: 1500-3000 kg/ha; Resistance to pod shattering: resistant; up to 3% shattering; Excellent seed quality; High and stable yield across many environments; tolerant to common soybean pests and diseases; relatively tolerant to low soil P; trap-crop for S. hermonthica; Protein content: 38%, Oil content: 14%; Carbohydrate content: 37%.	Guinea & Sudan savannahs, transitional and forest zones	TGX 824-18D x TGX 814-27D	2003	2015
Quarshie	GH/Gm/006/15	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	N.N. Denwar, H. Quarshie (CSIR-SARI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth pattern: Determinate; Flower colour: purple; plant height: 45-50 cm; 1000 seed weight: 127 g; Seed colour cream; Growth habit: erect; Pubescence: Present on stems, leaves and pods; Pod position: along main stem, Hilium colour: light pink; leaf type: trifoliolate.	Days to 50% flowering: 40-45; Days to maturity: 110-115; Yield potential: 2.0-2.4 t/ha; Haulm yield: 1300-2000 kg/ha; over 98% seed germination; Resistance to pod shattering: Susceptible (up to 30% shattering), excellent seed quality; good seed storability; high and stable yield across many environments; tolerant to common soybean pests (light infestation) and diseases; relatively tolerant to low soil P; trap-crop for S. hermonthica	Guinea & Sudan savannahs, transitional zone	TGX 824-18D x TGX 814-27D	2003	2015

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/Source	Breeder (s)/Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
CRI-Nangbaar	GH/Gm/007/15	Landrace/Ghana	H.K. Adu-Dapaah, J.Y. Asibuo, S. Amoah, B. Asafo Agyei. (CSIR-CRI)	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant height: height of 42cm; No of branches: up to six (6) branches/plant; Flower colour: purple; Number of seeds per pod: Two (2).	Moisture (%): 8.37±0.05, Protein (%): 43.00±0.18; Fat (%): 16.77±0.23, Ash (%): 5.73±0.01; Carbohydrates (%): 34.50±0.47, Energy (Kcal/100g): 429.4; Phosphorus (mg/100g): 721.9±6.4; Calcium (mg/100g): 372.1±19.1; Iron (mg/100g): 18.05±0.16; Seed yield: 2.1t/ha	Guinea Savannah, Sudan Savannah, Transition and Coastal Savannah zones	TGX 1830-20E	2005	2015
CRI-Ahoto	GH/Gm/008/15	Landrace/Ghana	H.K. Adu-Dapaah, J.Y. Asibuo, S. Amoah, B. Asafo Agyei. (CSIR-CRI)	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	The plant grows to a height of 48cm and bears an average of 4 branches/ plant. The flower is purple and the leaf light green in colour. Two to three seeds are borne per pod. The immature pod is green while the mature pod is light brown in colour.	Food uses Moisture (%): 9.64±0.08; Protein (%): 42.52±0.03; Fat (%): 19.46±0.42; Ash (%): 5.58±0.05; Carbohydrates (%): 32.45±0.58; Energy (Kcal/100g): 442.0; Phosphorus (mg/100g): 549.5±12.0; Calcium (mg/100g): 267.8±1.4; Iron (mg/100g): 11.62±0.28; Seed yield:2.4 t/ha	Guinea Savannah, Sudan Savannah, Transition and Coastal Savannah zones	TGX 1904-5F	2005	2015
Afayak	GH/Gm/009/15	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	N.N. Denwar (CSIR-SARI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth pattern: Determinate; Flower colour: purple; Plant height: 40-45 cm; 1000 seed weight: 125.6 g; Seed colour: cream; Stem colour at maturity: pink; Growth habit: erect; Pubescence: present on stems, pod and leaves; Pod position: along main stem; Hilium colour: light pink; Leaf type: trifoliolate	Days to 50% flowering: 40-45; Days to maturity: 110-115; over 98% seed germination; Yield potential: 2.0-2.4 t/ha; resistance to pod shattering: resistant up to 8%; Haulm yield: 1100-1400 kg/ha; Excellent seed quality; Good seed storability; High and stable yield across many environments; Above average tolerance to common soybean pests and diseases; Excellent trap-crop for S. hermonthica; Protein content: 38%; Oil content: 18%; Carbohydrate content: 36%	Guinea & Sudan savannahs, transitional zone	TGX 1834-5E	2012	2015
Songda	GH/Gm/010/15	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	N.N. Denwar (CSIR-SARI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth pattern: Determinate; Flower colour: purple; Plant height: 40-45 cm; 1000 seed weight: 123.4 g; Seed colour: cream; Stem colour at maturity: cream; Growth habit: erect; Pubescence: present on stems, pods and leaves; Pods position: along main stem; Hilium colour: light pink; Leaf type: trifoliolate	Days to 50% flowering: 40-45; Days to maturity: 110-115; Yield potential: 1.8-2.2 t/ha; Over 98% seed germination; Haulm yield: 1100-1200 kg/ha; Resistance to pod shattering: susceptible (over 50% shattering); Excellent seed quality; Good seed storability; High and stable yield across many environments; Average tolerance to common soybean pests and diseases; Excellent trap-crop for S. hermonthica	Guinea & Sudan savannahs, transitional zone	TGX 1445-3E	2012	2015
Suong-Pungun	GH/Gm/011/15	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	N.N. Denwar (CSIR-SARI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth pattern: Determinate; Flower colour: purple; Plant height: 45-50 cm; Over 98% seed germination, 1000 seed weight: 177.1 g; Seed colour: cream; Stem colour at maturity: pink; Growth habit: erect; Pubescence: present on stems, pods and leaves; Pods position: along main stem to very tip of stem; Hilium colour: light pink; Leaf type: trifoliolate.	Days to 50% flowering: 34-38; Days to maturity: 85-92; Yield potential: 1.5-1.8 t/ha; Haulm yield: 1200-1400 kg/ha; Resistance to pod shattering: Resistant (less than 5%); Excellent seed quality; Good seed storability; High and stable yield across many environment; Fairly tolerance to common soybean pests and diseases	Guinea & Sudan savannahs, transitional zone	TGX 1799-8F	2012	2015

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Gyidie	GH/Gm/001/16	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	S. Amoah (CSIR-CRI)	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth pattern: Determinate; Leaf type: trifoliolate; Pubescence colour: grey; Flower colour: purple; Corolla of the flower: white; Pods per peduncle: six (6); Three seeds per pod; Number of branches/plant: Three (3) on average; Matured pod colour: light brown; Pubescence type: Semi-appressed.	Days to maturity: 80-90; Tolerant to the soybean rust disease and other diseases; Moderately resistant to pod shattering, Nodulation ability: promiscuous; Yield potential: 3.2t/ha.	Savannah-Forest Transition, Forest, Coastal Savannah and Guinea Savannah	TGX 1835-10E	2016	2016
Latará	GH/Gm/002/16	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	S. Amoah (CSIR-CRI)	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth pattern: Determinate; Leaf type: trifoliolate; Leaf shape: Narrow; Pubescence: dense light brown; Pubescence type: erect; Flower colour: purple; Purple throat corolla; Matured pod colour: Yellowish brown; Pods per peduncle: six (6); Seeds per pod: 2-3; Seed coat colour: Yellow with light hilum.	Seed size: large; Tolerant to the soybean rust and other diseases of soybean; Moderately resistant to pod shattering; Nodulation ability: promiscuously with soil rhizobia; Yield potential: 3.2t/ha.	Savannah-Forest Transition, Forest, Coastal Savannah and Guinea Savannah	TGX 1903-7F	2016	2016
CSIR-Favour	GH/Gm/001/19	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	N. N. Denwar, F. Addae-Frimpomaah and R. Oteng-Frimpong (CSIR-SARI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Growth pattern: Determinate; Flower colour: purple; Plant height: 55-60 cm; Growth habit: erect; Pubescence: Present on stems, pods and leaves; Pods position: Along main stem; Hilum colour: light pinkish cream; Leaf type: trifoliolate; 1000 seed weight: 140.0 g; Seed colour: cream; Haulm yield: 2500-5000 kg/ha.	Days to 50% flowering: 45-48; Days to maturity: 115-118; Yield potential: 2.0 -3.5 t/ha; Resistance to pod shattering: Resistant (up to 5% shattering); Excellent seed quality for soymilk; High and stable yield across many environments; Fairly tolerant to common soybean pests and diseases; Fixes up to 100 kg/ha of biological N with artificial inoculants; High leaf output to smoulder weeds and increase organic matter of soil; Contains up 43% protein; 18 % oil content; Carbohydrate: 39.9%.	Guinea & Sudan savannahs, Transitional and Forest zones	TGX 1844-22E	2019	2019
Toondana	GH/Gm/002/19	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	S. Amoah, J.Y. Asibuo, S.N.T.T Addy, H. Adu-Dapaah (CSIR-CRI)	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth pattern: Indeterminate; Leaf type: trifoliolate; Pubescence: dense, light brown and erect; Corolla colour: white; Matured pod colour: brown; Number of pods per peduncle: seven (7); Number of seeds per pod: predominantly two (2); Branching: four (4) branches per plant on average; Seed coat colour: yellow.	Large seed size. It has desirable yield component traits such as high number of branches per plant, high number of pods per peduncle and large seed. It is resistant to lodging. It is resistant to the soybean rust disease and other diseases. It has promiscuous nodulation with soil rhizobia and a potential yield of 3.5t/ha.	Savannah-Forest Transition, Forest, Coastal Savannah	TGX 1989-20F	2019	2019
Anigye	GH/Gm/003/19	CSIR-SARI/ IITA	S. Amoah, J.Y. Asibuo, S.N.T.T Addy, H. Adu-Dapaah (CSIR-CRI)	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Growth habit: Indeterminate; Leaf type: trifoliolate; Pubescence colour: light brown; Throat corolla colour: purple; Flower colour: purple Matured pod colour: yellowish brown; Number of pods per peduncle: Five (5) on average; Seed coat colour: yellow with dark brown hilum; Number of seeds per pod: Three (3) on average; Branching: three branches per plant; Pubescence type: semi-appressed pubescence.	Matures in 101 days; resistant/ tolerant to the soybean rust disease and other diseases; It has good field emergence; Yield potential: 3.4t/ha; Pod shattering: moderately resistant; Nodulation: promiscuous nodulation.	Savannah-Forest Transition, Forest, Coastal Savannah	TGX 1909-3F	2019	2019

ROOTS & TUBERS

CASSAVA

SPECIES: *Manihot esculenta* Crantz.

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/Source	Breeder (s)/Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Afisiafi	GH/Me/001/15	IITA, Ibadan	J.A. Otoo, <i>et al.</i> ; CSIR-CRI	CSIR-CRI	Petiole colour: light green; mature leaf: green; branching: open branching; outer skin of root: pale redish brown; root spread: horizontal; cooking ability: not poundable; wider adaptation; young stem: light green; mature stem colour: greenish brown; tuber texture: rough; shape: cylindrical	Maturity period: 12-15 months; mean root yield: 28-35 t/ha; total root dry matter: 32%; is used for starch, flour and gari; tolerant to Cassava Mosaic Virus (CMV).	All agro-ecologies in Ghana	TMS 30572	1993	2015
Abasafitaa	GH/Me/002/15	IITA, Ibadan	J.A. Otoo, <i>et al.</i> ; CSIR-CRI	CSIR-CRI	Relatively short in height; low branching; wide open canopy; profuse flowering; colour of mature leaf: greyish green; root tuber: long horizontal; outer skin colour: dark greyish; inner skin colour: light greyish; petiole colour: light greyish; mature stem colour: greyish; interval between the branching: short	Maturity period: 12-15 months; mean root yield: 29-35 t/ha; total root dry matter: 35%; is used for starch, flour and gari; tolerant to Cassava Mosaic Virus (CMV).	Coastal Savannah, Forest, Forest-Savannah Transition	TMS 4(2)	1993	2015
Tek-Bankye	GH/Me/003/15	IITA, Ibadan	O. Safo-Kantanka, <i>et al.</i> ; KNUST	KNUST	Leaf colour: light green; mature leaf colour: dark green; petiole colour: green and purple; stem colour: light brown; level of branching: >3; root tuber: cream; texture: smooth; position: horizontal; neck length: long	Maturity period: 12-15 months; mean root yield: 30-40 t/ha; total root dry matter: 30%; is used for fufu, gari and 'ampesi; susceptible to Cassava Mosaic Virus (CMV).	Forest/Forest Savannah Transition	Mutant	1997	2015
Nyeri-Kobga	GH/Me/004/15	IITA, Ibadan	Cecil Osei, <i>et al.</i> ; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-SARI	Storage root surface texture - Rough	Potential root yields 17- 29 t/ha and have high yield at both 8 and 12 MAP; Dry matter content: 33 %; Roots are not poundable during the dry season; Uses: Tuo Zaafi, gari, flour and starch.	Guinea Savannah	91/02324	2003	2015
Eskamaye	GH/Me/005/15	IITA, Ibadan	Cecil Osei, <i>et al.</i> ; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-SARI	Storage root surface texture - Rough. Stem colour is greenish grey.	Potential root yield 16-23t/ha and have high yield at both 8 and 12 MAP; Dry Matter content: 33%; Gari swelling ability: High; Poundability: not poundable in the dry season; Uses: Tuo Zaafi, gari, flour and starch.	Guinea Savannah	91/02327	2003	2015
Fil-Ndiakong	GH/Me/006/15	IITA, Ibadan	Cecil Osei, <i>et al.</i> ; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-SARI	Storage root surface texture : Smooth with constrictions. Stem colour: Brownish grey.	Potential root yield: 16-19 t/ha and have high yield at 8 MAP; Maturity period: Early; Dry matter content: 36 %; Uses: Tuo Zaafi, gari, flour and starch; poundability: not poundable in the dry season; Taste (boiled): Sweet.	Guinea Savannah	92/0067	2003	2015
Nkabom	GH/Me/007/15	Ghana	O. Safo-Kantanka, <i>et al.</i> ; KNUST	KNUST	Young stem colour: green; petiole: purple; mature stem colour: silver green; branching habit: intermediate; tuber shape: conical (long); outer colour: dark brown	Maturity period: 12-15 months; mean root yield: 28-32 t/ha; total root dry matter: 32%; is used for starch and fufu; tolerant to Cassava Mosaic Virus (CMV).	Coastal Savannah, Forest, Forest-Savannah Transition	Landraces	2005	2015

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
IFAD	GH/Me/008/15	Ghana	O. Safo-Kantanka, <i>et al.</i> ; KNUST	KNUST	Young stem colour: green; petiole: purple; mature stem colour: silver green; branching habit: high; tuber shape: conical (long); outer colour: dark brown;	Maturity period: 12-15 months; mean root yield: 30-35 t/ha; total root dry matter: 30%; is used for starch and fufu; tolerant to Cassava Mosaic Virus (CMV).	Coastal Savannah, Forest, Forest-Savannah Transition	Landraces	2005	2015
CRI-Agbelifia	GH/Me/009/15	IITA, Ibadan	G. Ampong Mensah, <i>et al.</i> ; CRI, Kumasi	CSIR-CRI	Petiole colour: purple; Stem colour: greyish brown; Growth habit: no branching; Root skin colour: greyish yellow	Potential yield: 50.8 t/ha; 24.4% starch and good for starch and gari production.	Forest, coastal and forest-savannah transition.	97/ 4962	2005	2015
CRI-Essam Bankye	GH/Me/010/15	IITA, Ibadan	G. Ampong Mensah, <i>et al.</i> ; CRI, Kumasi	CSIR-CRI	Petiole colour: yellowish green; Stem colour: light brown; Branching habit: intermediate; Root skin colour: pale orange	Potential yield: 49 t/ha; 19.8% starch and good for flour.	Forest, coastal and forest-savannah transition.	97/ 3982	2005	2015
CRI-Bankye Hema	GH/Me/011/15	IITA, Ibadan	G. Ampong Mensah, <i>et al.</i> ; CRI, Kumasi	CSIR-CRI	Petiole colour: purple; Stem colour: brownish orange; Branching habit: low branching; Root skin colour: greyish orange	Potential yield: 48 t/ha; 21% starch and good for fufu and bakery products.	Forest, coastal and forest-savannah transition.	97/ 4414	2005	2015
CRI-Doku Duade	GH/Me/012/15	IITA, Ibadan	G. Ampong Mensah, <i>et al.</i> ; CRI, Kumasi	CSIR-CRI	Petiole colour: yellowish green; Stem colour: light brown; Branching habit: intermediate branching; Root skin colour: light orange	Potential yield: 45 t/ha; 24% starch and good starch production.	Forest, coastal and forest-savannah transition.	97/ 4489	2005	2015
Capevars Bankye	GH/Me/013/15	Central Region, Ghana	J.P. Tetteh <i>et al.</i> , Univ. of Cape Coast	University of Cape Coast, Ghana	Green young and old leaves; purplish petioles. 1-9 leaf lobes per petiole. Young stem is green with purplish stripes. Mature stem is light brown; and may produce 3-5 tiers of branches. Height of first branching may be 120cm and above. Roots: The skin is dark brown; the rind is light purple; and the flesh is white. Roots are relatively cylindrical in shape; with distinct neck. The plant grows vigorously and closes canopy within 3-4 months. It is also resistant to the Cassava Mosaic Virus (CMV).	Maturity: Quite early maturing, within 8-12 months, but can remain in the soil up to 18 months. High yielding (20-64 t/ha). Roots are mealy all year round. Besides it is relatively sweet, hence it is highly preferred for fufu and 'ampesi'. Starch yield is relatively high (above 25%). It is recommended for food uses (fufu, 'ampesi', gari, flour, 'agbelima') and for industrial starch production.	Savannah transitional, Deciduous forest, Evergreen rain forest	landrace	2005	2015

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/Source	Breeder (s)/Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Bankye Botan	GH/Me/014/15	Central Region, Ghana	J.P Tetteh <i>et al.</i> . Univ. of Cape Coast	University of Cape Coast, Ghana	The young leaves are purplish in colour; the older leaves are green; while the petioles are light green. There may be 1-9 leaf lobes per petiole. Young stem is light green; but the mature stem is greyish; and may produce up to 4 tiers of branches. Height of first branching is usually above 150 cm. Roots: The skin is dark grey; while the rind is light grey, and the flesh is white. Roots are relatively conical in shape; and they cluster around the base of the plant. The rind is quite thick; and may crack when harvesting is delayed beyond 15 months. It flowers and produces seeds profusely.	It matures within 9-12 months but can stay in the soil up to 15 months. Root yield is between 20 - 60 t/ha depending on the growing conditions. Roots are mealy only for a short period during the dry season. It is recommended for processing into gari, 'agbelima', flour for bread and pastries, kokonte, and for industrial starch production.	Savannah transitional, Deciduous forest, Evergreen rain forest	Selection from open-pollinated seed collected from Abasafitaa.	2005	2015
CRI-Ampong	GH/Me/015/15	IITA, Ibadan	J. Manu-Aduening; G. Ampong Mensah CRI, Kumasi	CSIR-CRI	Petiole colour: purple; Stem colour: greyish brown. Mean ht: 219.5 cm. Root skin colour: deep brown	Potential yield: 45 t/ha; Dry matter: 36%; Resistant to Cassava Mosaic Virus (CMV), good for flour, starch and poundable.	Forest, coastal and forest-savannah transition.	TMS 270	2010	2015
CRI-Broni Bankye	GH/Me/016/15	IITA, Ibadan	J. Manu-Aduening; G. Ampong Mensah CRI, Kumasi	CSIR-CRI	Petiole colour: yellowish green; Stem colour: light brown, Mean ht: 210.5 cm; Root skin colour: brown	Potential yield: 40 t/ha, Dry matter: 33%, tolerant to Cassava Mosaic Virus (CMV), good for flour, starch and bakery products	Forest, coastal and forest-savannah transition.	TMS 1	2010	2015
CRI-Sika Bankye	GH/Me/017/15	IITA, Ibadan	J. Manu-Aduening; G. Ampong Mensah CRI, Kumasi	CSIR-CRI	Petiole colour: yellowish green; Stem colour: greyish brown, Mean ht: 205 cm; Root skin colour: brown	Potential yield: 40 t/ha, Dry matter: 36%, tolerant to Cassava Mosaic Virus (CMV), good for flour and starch production	Forest, coastal and forest-savannah transition.	TMS 498	2010	2015
CRI-Otuhia	GH/Me/018/15	IITA, Ibadan	J. Manu-Aduening; G. Ampong Mensah. CRI, Kumasi	CSIR-CRI	Petiole colour: yellowish green; Stem colour: grey; Mean ht: 189 cm, Root skin colour: brown	Potential yield: 35 t/ha, Dry matter 39%, tolerant to Cassava Mosaic Virus (CMV), good for starch and flour production.	Forest, coastal and forest-savannah transition.	TMS 396	2010	2015
CRI-Duade Kpakpa	GH/Me/019/15	Landrace/Ghana	J. Manu-Aduening/CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Petiole colour: Red with green; Stem colour: light brown; Plant shape: Open; Root skin colour: light brown; Cortex colour: cream; Pulp colour: white	Potential Yield: 40-60T/ha; Dry matter: 37%; Resistant to CMD; Uses: Fufu (poundable), flour, starch, industrial alcohol	Coastal and Forest-Savannah Transition	12/0197	2015	2015
CRI-Amansan bankye	GH/Me/020/15	Landrace/Ghana	J. Manu-Aduening/CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Petiole colour: Purple; Stem colour: Light brown; Plant shape: Compact; Root skin colour: Light brown; Cortex colour: Cream; Pulp colour: Cream	Potential Yield: 40-57 T/ha; Dry matter: 38%; Resistant to CMD; Uses: Flour and bakery products	Forest, Coastal and Forest-Savannah Transition	12/0236	2015	2015
CRI-AGRA bankye	GH/Me/021/15	Landrace/Ghana	J. Manu-Aduening/CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Petiole colour: Purple; Stem colour: Light brown; Plant shape: Compact; Root skin colour: Light brown; Cortex colour: Cream; Pulp colour: Cream	Potential Yield: 35-60 T/ha; Dry matter: 32%; Resistant to CMD; Uses: starch and flour	Forest. Forest savannah transition and Coastal Savannah	12/0245	2015	2015
CRI-Dudzi	GH/Me/022/15	Landrace/Ghana	J. Manu-Aduening/CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Petiole colour: Reddish green; Stem colour: Dark brown; Plant shape: Umbrella; Root skin colour: Light brown; Cortex colour: Cream; Pulp colour: White	Potential Yield: 35-50 T/ha; Dry matter: 38%; Resistant to CMD; Uses: starch and flour	Forest ,Forest-savannah transition and Coastal Savannah	AW3/10/011	2015	2015

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
CRI-Abrabopa	GH/Me/023/15	Landrace/ Ghana	J. Manu-Aduening/ CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Petiole colour: Purple; Stem colour: dark brown; Plant shape: Compact; Root skin colour: Light brown; Cortex colour: Cream; Pulp colour: Cream	Potential Yield: 30-45 T/ha; Dry matter: 40%; Resistant to CMD; Uses: Hi-starch	Coastal, Forest and Forest-Savannah Transition	AW310/008	2015	2015
CRI-Lamesese	GH/Me/024/15	Landrace/ Ghana	J. Manu-Aduening/ CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Petiole colour: Purple; Stem colour: Dark brown; Plant shape: Umbrella; Root skin colour: Light brown; Cortex colour: Cream; Pulp colour: Yellow	Potential Yield: 40-50 T/ ha; Dry matter: 39%; Tolerant to CMD; Uses: Fufu (poundable), Flour and Beta-Carotene	Forest, Forest-Savannah Transition and Coastal Savannah	ANKA/10/003	2015	2015
CRI-Bediako	GH/Me/001/19	Landrace/ Ghana	J. Manu-Aduening/ CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Pubescence : absent; Apical leaf colour : deep green; Petiole colour : reddish green; Leaf shape: Elliptic lanceolate; Plant shape : compact; Stem colour : silver; Root colour: light brown; Colour of cortex : pink; Pulp colour	Resistant to Cassava Mosaic Disease; total dry matter is 33%; maturity period is 12 months; Potential root yield (T/ha) is 36 - 40. Uses: Fufu, Flour & starch	Forest, Coastal and Forest Savannah transition	GC 13/0016	2019	2019
Crops Research	GH/Me/002/19	Landrace/ Ghana	J. Manu-Aduening/ CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Apical leaf colour : light green; Petiole colour : red; Leaf shape - elliptic lanceolate; Plant shape: umbrella; Stem colour: orange; Root colour : light brown; Colour of cortex : pink; Pulp colour : cream	Tolerant to Cassava Mosaic Disease; total dry matter is 30 %; maturity period is 12 months; Potential root yield (T/ha) is 40-45; Uses: Fufu, Flour & starch	Forest, Coastal and Forest Savannah transition	GC 13/0021	2019	2019
Nyonku agbeli	GH/Me/003/19	IITA, Ibadan	G. Amenorpe, K.E. Danso (GAEC); E. Asare-Bediako, P.A. Asare, G. van der Puije, K. J. Taah, J.P. Tetteh (UCC); L.M. Aboagye (PGRRI- CSIR); E. Y. Parkes (IITA), B. B. Peprah (CSIR-CRI)	GAEC-BNARI & UCC	Root flesh colour : yellow; Apical leaf colour : light green; Petiole colour : yellowish green; Shape of the central leaf lobe: oblanceolate; Foliar scars : semi-prominence; Branching habit : dichotomous; Stem colour: silver green; Outer root colour : light brown; root constriction: few to none; Root shape: conical; Root colour (inner/cortex): white or cream; Pulp colour : yellowish	Maturity: 12 MAP; Potential root yield at 12 MAP: 23 T/ ha; Cassava mosaic disease (CMD) - tolerant; Dry matter: 26.06%; The rate of emergence: 99%; Cyanogenic potential: 36.75 ug g-1; Source of pro-Vitamin A - 9.6 µg g-1; Uses: flour, gari	Coastal savannah, Forest-savannah transition and Forest	GAEC14 / 1A1235	2019	2019
Kpornu agbeli	GH/Me/004/19	IITA, Ibadan	G. Amenorpe, K.E. Danso (GAEC); E. Asare-Bediako, P.A. Asare, G. van der Puije, K. J. Taah, J.P. Tetteh (UCC); L.M. Aboagye (PGRRI- CSIR); E. Y. Parkes (IITA), B. B. Peprah (CSIR-CRI)	GAEC-BNARI & UCC	Cassava mosaic disease: resistant; Root flesh colour: yellow; Apical leaf colour: light green; Petiole colour: yellowish green; Shape of the central leaf lobe: oblanceolate; Foliar scars : very-prominence; Branching habit : dichotomous; Stem colour : silver green; Outer root colour : white; Root constriction : few to none; Root shape : conical; Root colour (inner/cortex) : white or cream; Pulp colour : yellowish	Maturity: 12 MAP; the rate of emergence: 99%; Potential root yield: 24t/ha; Dry matter: 26.06%; Cyanogenic potential: 32.58µg g-1; Source of pro-Vitamin A (7.97 µg g-1); Uses: flour, gari	Coastal savannah, Forest-savannah transition and Forest	GAEC14 / 2B1368	2019	2019

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Tetteh bankye	GH/Me/005/19	IITA, Ibadan	G. Amenorpe, K.E. Danso (GAEC); E. Asare-Bediako, P.A. Asare, G. van der Puije, K. J. Taah, J.P Tetteh (UCC); L.M. Aboagye (PGRRI- CSIR); E. Y. Parkes (IITA), B. B. Pephrah (CSIR-CRI)	GAEC-BNARI & UCC	Cassava mosaic disease: resistant; Apical leaf colour: purplish green; Petiole colour : yellowish green; Shape of the central leaf lobe : oblanceolate; Foliar scars on the stem - semi-prominence; Branching habit : dichotomous; Stem colour : orange green; Outer root colour : light brown; Root constriction: few to none; Root shape: conical; Root colour (inner/cortex) : yellow; pulp colour : yellowish	Maturity: 12 MAP; the rate of emergence:100%; Potential root yield at 12 MAP: 19 t/ha; Dry matter: 21.2%; The cyanogenic potential: 31.91 ug g-1; Source of pro-Vitamin A (6.91µg g-1); Uses: flour, gari, fufu	Coastal savannah, Forest-savannah transition and Forest	GAEC14 / 5E1610	2019	2019
Fufuohene bankye	GH/Me/006/19	Volta Region, Ghana	G. Amenorpe, K.E. Danso (GAEC); E. Asare-Bediako, P.A. Asare, G. van der Puije, K. J. Taah, J.P Tetteh (UCC); L.M. Aboagye (PGRRI- CSIR); E. Y. Parkes (IITA), B. B. Pephrah (CSIR-CRI)	GAEC-BNARI & UCC	Cassava mosaic disease: resistant; Apical leaf colour: purplish green; Petiole colour : purple; Shape of the central leaf lobe : elliptical lanceolate; Foliar scars on the stem: semi-prominence; Branching habit : dichotomous; Stem colour: greenish yellow; Outer root colour : yellow; root constriction : some; Root shape : conical cylindrical; Root colour (inner/cortex) : white; Pulp colour : white	Maturity: 12 MAP; the rate of emergence - 98%; Potential root yield at 12 MAP: 25 t/ha; Dry matter- 41.9%; Cassava Mosaic Disease (CMD): resistant; cyanogenic potential: 32.8µg g-1; Uses include fufu starch, flour, gari	Coastal savannah, Forest-savannah transition and Forest	GAEC12 / 6FH0008001	2019	2019
Ampesi hema bankye	GH/Me/001/19	Volta Region, Ghana	G. Amenorpe, K.E. Danso (GAEC); E. Asare-Bediako, P.A. Asare, G. van der Puije, K. J. Taah, J.P Tetteh (UCC); L.M. Aboagye (PGRRI- CSIR); E. Y. Parkes (IITA), B. B. Pephrah (CSIR-CRI)	GAEC-BNARI & UCC	Cassava mosaic disease : resistant; root flesh colour: white; Apical leaf colour: purplish green; Petiole colour : purple; shape of the central leaf lobe : elliptical lanceolate; Foliar scars on the stem : semi-prominence; Branching habit : dichotomous; Stem colour : greenish yellow; Outer root colour : light brown; Root constriction: few to none; Root shape: cylindrical; Root colour (inner/cortex) : yellow; Pulp colour : white	Maturity: 12 MAP; the rate of emergence: 97%; Potential root yield at 12MAP: 22 t/ ha; Dry matter: 40.0%; Cassava Mosaic Disease (CMD): resistant; Cyanogenic potential: 34.71ug g-1; Uses: Ampesi fufu starch, flour	Coastal savannah, Forest-savannah transition and Forest agro-ecologies	GAEC12 / 7GH0008002	2019	2019

COCOYAM

SPECIES: *Xanthosoma Sagittifolium* (L) Schott

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/Source	Breeder (s)/Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
CRI-Akyede	GH/Xs/001/15	Ghana	E.L. Omenyo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Structure: erect; Leaf: Green; Purple leaf margin; Sagittate. Lamina: Ovoid; triangular basal lobe & deep sinus. Petiole: Deep green; Base of Petiole: Purple; Stem (corm): Purple; Colour of cormel skin: Purple; Colour of cormel flesh: Purple; Flowering: Rare, Maturity: Late maturing (12-15 months)	Potential Yield: 7.0 mt/Ha; Soft rot : tolerant; Minerals: Iron content : 7.06 mg/100g; Crude protein : 8.48%; Crude Fibre :1.19%; Ash : 2.67%; Dry Matter : 43.6%; Carbohydrate : 47.87%; Uses: Fufu, Ampesi, Eto, Nuhuu, Koliko, Chips.	Forest	Landrace (SW 011)	2012	2015
CRI-Ma ye Yie	GH/Xs/002/15	Ghana	E.L. Omenyo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Structure: Erect; Leaf: Green; Purple leaf margin; Lamina: Ovoid, triangular basal lobe & deep sinus; Petiole: Deep green; Base of petiole: white-cream; Stem (Corm): white-cream, Colour of cormel skin: white-cream, Colour of cormel flesh: white-cream; Flowering: Rare; Maturity: 12 months	Potential yield: 6.0 mt/ha; Soft rot : tolerant; Minerals: Rich in Phosphorus: 382.23 mg/100g; Dry matter content : 39.9%; Ash : 2.84%; Carbohydrate: 48.62%; Crude protein : 6.72%; Crude fibre : 1.17%; Uses: Ampesi, Nuhuu, Chips, Bread, Biscuit, Meat pie	Forest	Landrace (AGA 97/162)	2012	2015
CRI- Gye Me Di	GH/Xs/003/15	Ghana	E.L. Omenyo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Structure: Erect, Leaf: Green; Purple leaf margin; Sagittate, Lamina: Ovoid, triangular basal lobe & deep sinus; Petiole: Deep green; Base of Petiole: Purple, Stem (corm): Purple; Colour of cormel skin: Purple; Colour of cormel flesh: Purple; Flowering: Rare; Maturity: Late maturing (12-15 months)	Potential Yield: 8 mt/ha; Soft rot : tolerant; Minerals: Rich in Magnesium : 408 mg/100g; Dry matter content: 44.4%; Ash : 2.73%; Carbohydrate : 48.19%; Uses: Fufu, Ampesi, Eto, Koliko, Nuhuu, Chips.	Forest	Landrace (SCJ 98/005)	2012	2015

FRAFRA POTATO

SPECIES: *Solenostemon rotundifolius* Poir

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
WAAPP Plesa 1 (WAAPP Frafra potato)	GH/Sr/001/19	Ghana	F. Kusi, S.K. Nutsugah, R.A.L. Kanton, P.A. Asungre (CSIR-SARI), L.M. Aboagye (CSIR-PGRI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Plant stature: semi spread; Growth habit : multiple branches; Pigmentation: pronounced at margins of older leaves; Leaf colour: light yellowish green; Stem colour: light green; Flower colour: deep purple; Physiological maturity: 85 days; Tubers per plant : 269; Tuber shape: elliptical; Tuber skin colour: black; Resistance to diseases: tolerant; Dormancy period: 2 months after harvest; Drought tolerance: escape Average tuber weight: 3.18 g	Potential tuber yield: 19 t/ha; High resistance to Fusarium wilt, tuber rot and foliar diseases; Proximate composition: Moisture (g/100 g) : 72.77; Ash (g/100 g): 1.15; Fat (g/100 g) : 0.21; Protein (g/100g) :1.69; Carbohydrate (g/100 g) : 24.19;Energy (kcal/100 g) : 105.4; Excellent as flour substitute in koose and bread and also for the following local dishes: peeled with pepper and thick porridge.	Guinea Savannah, Sudan Savannah, Coastal Savannah and Forest zones	UE021	2019	2019
Manga-moya (Well done Manga station- Ayekoo Manga)	GH/Sr/002/19	Ghana	F. Kusi, K. Nutsugah, Roger A. L. Kanton, Peter A. Asungre (CSIR-SARI), Lawrence Aboagye (CSIR-PGRI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Plant stature: semi spread; Growth habit : multiple branches; Pigmentation: slightly at the margins of old leaves; Leaf colour: light yellowish green; Stem colour: light green Flower colour: deep purple Physiological maturity: 85 days; Tubers per plant : 143.3; Tuber shape- fairly round; Tuber skin colour: brown; Resistance to diseases: tolerant; Dormancy period: 2 months after harvest; Drought tolerance: escape Average tuber weight: 4.48 g	Potential tuber yield: 15.2 t/ha; High resistance to Fusarium wilt, tuber rot and foliar diseases; Proximate composition: Moisture (g/100 g): 77.52; Ash (g/100 g): 1.04; Fat (g/100 g):0.16; Protein (g/100 g):1.15; Carbohydrate (g/100 g): 20.15;Energy (kcal/100 g): 86.58; Excellent as flour substitute in koose and bread and also for the following local dishes: peeled with pepper and thick porridge	Guinea Savannah, Sudan Savannah, Coastal Savannah and forest zones	UE023	2019	2019
Maa-Lana (I can't believe how far I have made it- menamenie)	GH/Sr/003/19	Ghana	F. Kusi, K. Nutsugah, Roger A. L. Kanton, Peter A. Asungre (CSIR-SARI), Lawrence Aboagye (CSIR-PGRI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Plant stature: semi spread; Growth habit : Multiple stems; Pigmentation : slightly at the margins of old leaves; Leaf colour: light yellowish green; Stem colour: light green; Flower colour : light purple; Physiological maturity : 95 days; Tubers per plant : 202.3; Tuber shape: elliptical ; Tuber skin colour: brown; Resistance to diseases: tolerant; Dormancy period: 2 months after harvest; Drought tolerance: tolerant Average tuber weight: 3.47 g	Potential tuber yield: 23.6 t/ha; High resistance to Fusarium wilt, tuber rot and foliar diseases; Proximate composition: Moisture (g/100 g) : 75.62; Ash (g/100g):1.4; Fat (g/100 g) : 0.07; Protein (g/100 g):1.28; Carbohydrate (g/100 g): 21.9; Energy (kcal/100g): 93.3; Excellent in the preparation of the following local dishes: tuo-zaafi, thick porridge and peeled without pepper	Guinea Savannah, Sudan Savannah, Coastal Savannah and forest zones	UW020	2019	2019

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Naachem-Tiir (Hope for the youth)	GH/Sr/004/19	Ghana	F. Kusi, K. Nutsugah, Roger A. L. Kanton, Peter A. Asungre (CSIR-SARI); Lawrence Aboagye (CSIR-PGRRI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Plant stature: semi spread; Growth habit : Multiple stems; Pigmentation : slightly at the margins of old leaves; Leaf colour: light yellowish green; Stem colour: light green; Flower colour : light purple; Physiological maturity: 95 days; Tubers per plant : 117.7; Tuber shape- obovate; Tuber skin colour- brown; Resistance to diseases: tolerant; Dormancy period: 2 months after harvest; Drought tolerance: tolerant Average tuber weight: 3.39 g	Potential tuber yield: 20 t/ha; High resistance to Fusarium wilt, tuber rot and foliar diseases; Proximate composition: Moisture (g/100 g): 74.91; Ash (g/100 g): 1.03; Fat (g/100 g): 0.08; Protein (g/100 g): 1.23; Carbohydrate (g/100 g) : 22.86; Energy (kcal/100 g): 96.62; Excellent as flour substitute in the preparation of bread and the following local dishes tuo-zaafi, peeled with pepper and peeled without pepper	Guinea Savannah, Sudan Savannah, Coastal	UW022	2019	2019
Nutsugah Piesa (Nutsugah's Frafra potato)	GH/Sr/005/19	Ghana	F. Kusi, K. Nutsugah, Roger A. L. Kanton, Peter A. Asungre (CSIR-SARI); Lawrence Aboagye (CSIR-PGRRI)	CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute	Plant stature: semi spread; Growth habit : Multiple stems; Pigmentation : slightly at the margins of old leaves; Leaf colour: yellowish green; Stem colour: light green; Flower colour: purple; Physiological maturity: 95 days; Tubers per plant: 137.7; Tuber shape- oblong ; Tuber skin colour: light brown; Resistance to diseases: tolerant; Dormancy period: 4 months after harvest; Drought tolerance: tolerant Average tuber weight: 3.88 g	Potential tuber yield;17 t/ha; High resistance to Fusarium wilt, tuber rot and foliar diseases; Proximate composition: Moisture (g/100 g): 77.29; Ash (g/100 g): 0.94; Fat (g/100 g): 0.06; Protein (g/100 g): 0.93; Carbohydrate (g/100 g) : 20.79; Energy (kcal/100 g): 87.4; Excellent as flour substitute in koose in the preparation of thick porridge	Guinea Savannah, Sudan Savannah, Coastal Savannah and forest zones	ACC01022	2019	2019

SWEETPOTATO

SPECIES: *Ipomoea batatas* L.

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
Okumkom	GH/lb/001/15	Landrace/ Ghana	J. A. Otoo, CSIR - CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Spreading; Vine pigment: Green; Vine tip pubescence: Heavy; Foliage color: Mature leaf colour: Green; Petiole pigmentation: Green; Storage root shape: Round Elliptic; Storage root skin color: Pink; Storage root flesh color: White	Potential root Yield: 30 tons/ha; Starch: 65.9 %(DWT); Total sugars: 17.31; Sweetpotato weevil: Tolerant; SPVD: Tolerant; Storage root Dry Matter content: 30.7%. Uses: Ampesi	Guinea savannah, Forest-Savannah transition and coastal savannah	TIS 8266	1998	2015
Santom pona	GH/lb/002/15	Landrace/ Ghana	J. A. Otoo, CSIR - CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Spreading; Vine pigment: Green; Foliage color: Green; Petiole pigmentation: Green; Storage root shape: Long elliptic, round (variable); Storage root skin color: Predominant color , dark cream; Storage root flesh color: Pale yellow	Potential root yield: 17 tons/ha; early maturing; high foliage; starch: 70%(DWT); Total sugars: 12.95 %; Storage root Dry Matter content:34.4%; Storage root carotene content: 618µg/100g; Sweetpotato weevil: Tolerant; SPVD: Tolerant	Guinea savannah, Forest-Savannah transition and coastal savannah	TIS 84/0320	1998	2015
Sauti	GH/lb/003/15	Landrace/ Ghana	J. A. Otoo, CSIR - CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Semi- Erect; Vine pigment: Green with many dark purple spots; Mature leaf shape: Type of lobing: Deep; Foliage color: Immature leaf color: Green with purple edge; Petiole pigmentation: Green; Storage root shape: Long Irregular Or Curved; Storage root skin color: Cream	Potential root yield:19 tons/ha; less sugary; starch 69.26% (DWT); Total sugars: 12.71% (DWT); Sweetness: Less; Storage root Dry Matter content: 40.2%; Storage root nitrogen: 5.3; Storage root starch %age: 14.8; Storage root carotene content: 1171µg/100g; Uses: Ampesi and french fries; Sweetpotato Weevil (SPW): Susceptible; SPVD W): Tolerant	Guinea savannah, Forest-Savannah transition and coastal savannah	Not known	1998	2015
Faara	GH/lb/004/15	Landrace/ Ghana	J. A. Otoo, CSIR - CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Extremely Spreading; Foliage color: Mature leaf color: Green; Immature leaf color: Yellow Green; Petiole pigmentation: Green with purple throughout; Storage root shape: Long Elliptic; Storage root skin color: Storage root flesh color: White; Vine pigment: Green; Foliage color Mature leaf color: Green Immature leaf color: Green; Petiole pigmentation: Green; Storage root shape: Long elliptic, round (variable); Storage root skin color: dark cream; Storage root flesh color: Pale yellow	Potential root yield: 22 tons/ha; starch: 70.21 % (DWT); Total sugars: 13.90 %; Storage root Dry Matter content: 34.4%; Storage root carotene content: 618µg/100g; Sweetpotato Weevil: Tolerant; SPVD: Tolerant; Uses: Fried chips and Ampesi	Guinea savannah, Forest-Savannah transition and coastal savannah	TIS 3017	1998	2015
CRI-Otoo	GH/lb/005/15	CIP	H. K. Dapaah, K. Adofo CSIR - CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Spreading; Foliage color: Green; Petiole pigmentation: Green with purple at both ends; Storage root shape: Long-elliptic; Storage root skin color: Pale Cream; Storage root flesh color: Cream with interspersed Light orange	Potential root yield: 23 tons/ha; starch: 68.03 % (DWT); Total sugars 15.9 %; Storage root Dry Matter content: 32.2%; Starch content : 13.3%; Storage root carotene content: 545µg/100g; Sweetpotato Weevil: Tolerant; SPVD: Tolerant; Uses: High biomass production for livestock; French fries and flour products	Guinea savannah, Forest-Savannah transition and coastal savannah	Mogamba	2005	2015
CRI-Apomuden	GH/lb/006/15	CIP	H. K. Dapaah, K. Adofo CSIR - CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Spreading; Foliage color: Green; Petiole pigmentation: Green and pigmented close to the leaf; Storage root shape: Long Irregular Or Curved; Storage root skin color Predominant color: Purple-red with interspersed Cream; Storage root flesh color: Orange with yellow; Storage root shape variability: Moderately Variable; Storage root size variability: Moderately Variable	Excellent for baby: foods and fortification of dairy products (potaghurt); potential root yield 30 ton/ha; starch: 47.01% (DWT); Total sugars: 36.67%; Storage root Dry Matter content: 21.9%; Storage root starch content: 10%; Storage root beta: carotene content: 21846 : 40926µg/100g; Sweetpotato Weevil: Susceptible	Guinea savannah, Forest-Savannah transition and coastal savannah	Kamala sundari	2005	2015

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/Source	Breeder (s)/Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
CRI - Ogyefo	GH/lb/007/15	CIP	H. K. Dapaah, K. Adofo CSIR - CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Spreading; Foliage color: Green; Storage root shape: Long irregular or curved; Storage root surface defects: Absent; Storage root cortex thickness: Intermediate; Storage root skin color: Pink; Storage root flesh color: White	Excellent starch properties; potential root yield 20 tons/ha; starch: 74.13 % (DWT); Total sugars: 10.06 %; Storage root Dry Matter content: 40.1%; Starch content: 12.4%; SPVD: Tolerant	Guinea savannah, Forest-Savannah transition and coastal savannah	Not known	2005	2015
CRI - Hi-Starch	GH/lb/008/15	CIP	H. K. Dapaah, K. Adofo CSIR - CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Spreading; Foliage color: Green; Petiole pigmentation: Green; Storage root shape: Elliptic; Storage root skin color: Cream; Storage root skin color: Predominant color: Cream; Storage root flesh color: Cream	High quality sweetpotato starch for industrial uses; high starch yield; potential root yield: 18 tons/ha; starch: 75.15 % (DWT); Total sugars: 10.52 %; Storage root Dry Matter content: 47%; Starch content: 21%; Sweetpotato weevils: Tolerant; SPVD: Tolerant	Guinea savannah, Forest-Savannah transition and coastal savannah	Not known	2005	2015
CRI-Patron	GH/lb/009/15	CIP	J. N. Asafu Agyei, Kwadwo Adofo CSIR - CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Semi- Erect; Foliage color: Green; Petiole pigmentation: Green with purple at both ends; Storage root shape: Long-elliptic; Storage root skin color: Dark yellow; Storage root flesh color: dark yellow	High biomass production for livestock; excellent for "ampesi" (boiled) and deep fried chips and flour products; potential root yield 20 tons/ha; starch 69.4 % (DWT); Total sugars: 14.97 %; Storage root Dry Matter content: 34.4%; Starch content: 69.4%mg/100g (DWT); Storage root beta:carotene content: 2800µg/100g; Sweetpotato Weevil: Tolerant; SPVD: Tolerant; Maturity period: 4-5 months	Guinea savannah, Forest-Savannah transition and coastal savannah	Mohc	2012	2015
CRI-bohye	GH/lb/010/15	CIP	J. N. Asafu Agyei, Kwadwo Adofo CSIR - CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Semi-erect; Foliage color: Green; Petiole pigmentation: Green with purple near leaf; Storage root shape: Obvate; Storage root skin color: Purple; Storage root flesh color: Pale Orange	Potential root yield 22 tons/ha, starch 68 % mg/100g (DW); Total sugars: 15.21 %; Storage root Dry Matter content: 31%; Starch content: 68.1% mg/100g (DWT); Storage root beta-carotene content: 5500 µg/100g; Pest reaction: Sweetpotato Weevil: Tolerant; SPVD : Tolerant; Maturity period: 4-5 months; Uses: Ampesi, french fries and fried chunks chips and flour products	Guinea savannah, Forest-Savannah transition and coastal savannah	199062.1	2012	2015
CRI - dadanyuie	GH/lb/011/15	CIP	J. N. Asafu Agyei, Kwadwo Adofo CSIR - CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Spreading; Foliage color: Green; Petiole pigmentation: Green; Storage root shape: Round elliptic; Storage root surface defects: Absent; Predominant Storage root skin color: Dark purple; Storage root flesh color: White	Potential root yield 18 tons/ha; starch content 68% mg/100g (DW); Total sugars: 15.11%; Storage root Dry Matter content: 35%; Starch content: 68%(mg/100g) DWT; Sweetpotato weevil: Tolerant; SPVD: Tolerant; Maturity period: 4-5 months; Uses: Excellent starch properties for industrial applications , high quality sweetpotato flour	Guinea savannah, Forest-Savannah transition and coastal savannah	Kemb 37	2012	2015
CRI - Ligri	GH/lb/012/15	CIP	J. N. Asafu Agyei, Kwadwo Adofo CSIR - CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Spreading; Foliage color: Green; Petiole pigmentation: Green with purple at both ends; Storage root shape: Round; Storage root skin color: Cream; Storage root skin color: Predominant color: Cream; Storage root flesh color: Pale yellow	Potential root yield : 22 tons/ha; high dry matter: 35%; starch content: 69.53% (mg/100g) DWT; Total sugars: 14.69 %; Storage root Dry Matter content : 35 %; Starch content: 69.53 % (mg/100g) DWT; Sweetpotato weevils: Tolerant; SPVD : Tolerant; Maturity period: 4-5 months; Uses: High vine(biomass) yield, High quality sweetpotato starch for industrial uses,	Guinea savannah, Forest-Savannah transition and coastal savannah	Cemsa- 74-228	2012	2015

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
CRI-Yiedie	GH/lb/001/19	CIP	K. Adofo, E. Baafi, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Spreading; Vine pigment: Green with few purple spots; Vine tip pubescence: Absent; Foliage colour: Green with purple immature leaves; Petiole pigmentation: Green with purple stripes; Storage root shape:Ovate; Storage root skin colour: Red; Storage root flesh colour: Yellow;	Potential root yield:39.0 t/ha; Storage root Dry Matter content:36.5%; Starch content (mg/100g) DWT :70.33%; Total sugars (raw): 14.48%; Sweetpotato weevil Tolerant; Alcidodes sp.:Tolerant;SPVD: Tolerant; Uses: Chunk-Fried, Boiled/Steamed, fufu, crispy chips, French fries and varied flour-based products;	Guinea savannah, Forest-Savannah transition and coastal savannah	CIP 442162	2019	2019
CRI-Gavana	GH/lb/002/19	CSIR-CRI, Ghana	K. Adofo, E. Baafi, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Spreading; Vine pigment: Green with purple nodes; Vine tip pubescence: Absent; Foliage colour: Green; Petiole pigmentation: Green with purple throughout; Storage root shape: Obovate; Storage root skin colour: Cream; Storage root flesh colour: Dark yellow;	Potential root yield:28.0t/ha; Storage root Dry Matter content: 35.8%; Starch content (DWT):71.88%; Total sugars (raw): 17.48%; Sweetpotato weevil Tolerant; Alcidodes sp.: Tolerant; SPVD : Tolerant; Uses: Chunk-Fried, Boiled/ Steamed, fufu, crispy chips, French fries and varied flour-based products	Guinea savannah, Forest-Savannah transition and coastal savannah	AP 3A	2019	2019
SARI-Nyumingre	GH/lb/003/19	Landrace/ Ghana	K. Acheremu, J. Adjebeng-Danquah, I. A. Abukari, CSIR-SARI; K. Adofo, CSIR-CRI; E. Carey, CIP	CSIR-SARI	Plant type: Spreading; Matured leaf colour:Green; Young leaf colour: Green with purple veins on upper leaf surface; Petiole pigmentation: Green with purple at both ends; Storage root shape: Oblong; Storage root skin colour: White; Storage root flesh colour: White.	Potential root yield:16t/ha; Maturity period: 4-5months; Total carotenoids in leaves: 56.76 (mg/100g); Sweetness: Less sweet; Total sugars: 11.22%; SPVD : Tolerant; Storage root dry matter content: 36.0%; Starch content: 63%; Uses: Ampesi	Guinea and Sudan Savannahs	Not known	2019	2019
SARI-TU-Diedi	GH/lb/004/19	Tuskegee University, USA	K. Acheremu, J. Adjebeng-Danquah, I. A. Abukari, CSIR-SARI; K. Adofo, CSIR-CRI; E. Carey, CIP	CSIR-SARI	Plant type: Spreading; Matured leaf colour: Green with few purple spots; Young leaf colour: Greyish green (due to dense pubescence); Petiole pigmentation: Green with purple at both ends; Storage root shape:Obovate; Storage root skin colour: Purple-red; Storage root flesh colour: Purple;	Potential root yield:14t/ha; Maturity period: 4-5months; Total carotenoids in leaves: 63.50 (mg/100g); Sweetness: Less sweet; Total sugars: 12.93 %; Storage root Dry Matter: 34 % Sweetpotato weevil: Tolerant; SPVD - Tolerant; Starch content (DWT): 63%; Anthocyanin content: 171 (mg/100g) DWT; Uses: Ampesi.	Guinea and Sudan Savannahs	TU-2-12	2019	2019
SARI-Nan	GH/lb/005/19	Landrace/ Ghana	K. Acheremu, J. Adjebeng-Danquah, I. A. Abukari, CSIR-SARI; K. Adofo, CSIR-CRI; E. Carey, CIP	CSIR-SARI	Plant type: Semi-erect; Mature leaf colour: Green; Young leaf colour: Yellowish green; Petiole pigmentation: Green; Storage root shape: Long oblong; Storage root skin colour: Brownish orange; Storage root flesh colour: Pale orange;	Potential root yield: 24t/ha; Maturity period: 3-4months; Total carotenoids in leaves: 74.87 (mg/100g); Sweetness: Less sweet; Total sugars: 16.96 %; Storage root Dry Matter : 27.7 % Sweet Potato weevil :Tolerant ; SPVD: Tolerant; Beta-carotene content: 15.74 mg/100g. Starch content (DWT) : 60 %; Uses: Ampesi and chunk fries.	Guinea and Sudan Savannahs	Not known	2019	2019
CRI-Vern Gracen	GH/lb/006/19	CSIR-CRI, Ghana	E. Baafi, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Extremely spreading; Vine colour: Green; Vine tip pubescence:Moderate; Foliage colour: Green with purple edge immature leaves; Petiole pigmentation: Green with purple near leaves; Storage root shape:Obovate;Storage root skin colour:Brownish orange; Storage root flesh colour: Cream	Potential root yield:22.0 t/ ha; Sweetpotato weevil: Tolerant; SPVD: Tolerant; Alcidodes: Tolerant; Storage root Dry Matter : 42.4%; Starch content(DWT):76.6%; Total sugars (raw): 15.29%; Beta: carotene content : 7.25 (mg/100g) DW; Benefit-Cost Ratio : 6.79; Uses: Fufu flour, French fries,Chunk-fried, Boiled/Steamed, crispy chips, bread, pastries,Gluten-free noodles.	Forest, Forest-Transition, Coastal Savannah, Guinea Savannah, Sudan Savannah	Histarch x Ogyefo	2019	2019

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
CRI-AGRA SP09	GH/lb/007/19	CSIR-CRI, Ghana	E. Baafi, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Spreading; Vine colour: Green; Vine tip pubescence: Sparse; Foliage colour: Green; Petiole pigmentation: Green; Storage root shape: Oblong; Storage root skin colour: Pink; Storage root flesh colour: Cream	Potential root yield: 26.0t/ha; Sweetpotato weevil : Tolerant; SPVD : Tolerant; Alcidodes: Tolerant; Storage root DM : 40.3%; Starch content(DWT): 77.0%; Total sugars (raw): 14.47%; Beta-carotene content : 2.85 (mg/100g) DW; Benefit: Cost Ratio: 7.99; Uses: Fufu flour, French fries, Chunk-fried, Boiled/Steamed, crispy chips, Gluten-free noodles.	Forest, Forest-Transition, Coastal Savannah, Guinea Savannah, Sudan Savannah	Histarch x Ogyefo	2019	2019
CRI-AGRA SP13	GH/lb/008/19	CSIR-CRI, Ghana	E. Baafi, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Extremely Spreading; Vine colour: Totally dark purple; Vine tip pubescence: Sparse; Foliage colour: Green; Petiole pigmentation: Green with purple spots throughout; Storage root shape: Obovate; Storage root skin colour: Yellow; Storage root flesh colour: Dark yellow	Potential root yield: 39.0t/ha; Sweetpotato weevil : Tolerant; SPVD : Tolerant; Alcidodes: Tolerant; Storage root Dry Matter : 39.7%; Starch content (DWT) : 74.6%; Total sugars (raw): 16.56%; Beta: carotene content: 11.38 (mg/100g) DW; Benefit: Cost Ratio: 11.87; Uses: French fries, Chunk-fried, Boiled/Steamed, crispy chips, bread, pastries, Yoghurt, Baby foods, Juice, Potential enzyme source for breweries and other industries.	Forest, Forest-Transition, Coastal Savannah, Guinea Savannah, Sudan Savannah	CIP 443035 x Resisto	2019	2019
CRI-Kofi Annan	GH/lb/009/19	CSIR-CRI, Ghana	E. Baafi, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant type: Semi-erect; Vine colour: Green with few purple spots; Vine tip pubescence: Absent; Foliage colour: Green with purple veins on upper surface; Petiole pigmentation: Green with purple near leaf; Storage root shape: Long elliptic; Storage root skin colour: Orange; Storage root flesh colour: Dark orange	Potential root yield: 19.0t/ha; Sweetpotato weevil : Tolerant; SPVD : Tolerant; Alcidodes: Tolerant; Storage root Dry Matter: 35.5%; Starch content (DWT): 70.4%; Total sugars (raw): 18.12%; Beta: carotene content: 28.46 (mg/100g) DW; Benefit: Cost Ratio: 5.80; Uses: French fries, Chunk-fried, Boiled/Steamed, crispy chips, Yoghurt, Juice.	Forest, Forest-Transition, Coastal Savannah, Guinea Savannah, Sudan Savannah	CIP 443035 x Beauregard	2019	2019

TARO

SPECIES: *Colocasia esculenta* (L.) Schott

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
CRI-Huogbelor	GH/Ce/001/19	INEA	E. Baafi, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-CRI	Structure: erect; Petiole colour: Light green; Leaf colour: Light green; Upper leaf surface: Light green leaf veins; Lower surface of leaf: Light green leaf veins; Central lobe of leaf: purple triangular spot; Corm neck colour: Cream; Corm flesh colour: Cream; Maturity: Early maturing (6 -7 months after planting)	Potential Yield: 13.0 t/ha; TLBD: highly tolerant; Corm dry matter content: 33%; starch granule size: 1 - 3.5 μ , Peak viscosity: 2970; Peak Time: 5.13 mins; Pasting temperature: 85.65°C; Stability ratio: 0.65; Setback ratio: 1.47; Benefit-cost ratio: 2.95 – 5.91. Uses: Ampesi, chunk-fried.	Low lands (muddy areas) of Forest, Forest-Savannah Transition, Coastal Savannah, Guinea Savannah and Sudan Savannah	BL/SM 158	2019	2019
CRI-Asempa	GH/Ce/002/19	INEA	E. Baafi, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-CRI	Structure: erect; Petiole colour: Pale green; Leaf colour: Pale green; Upper leaf surface: Dark green leaf veins; Lower surface of leaf: Light green leaf veins; Central lobe of leaf: light purple spot; Corm neck colour: white; Corm flesh colour: White; Maturity: Late maturing (8 - 12 months after planting)	Potential Yield: 25.0 t/ha; TLBD: highly tolerant; Corm dry matter content: 37%; starch granule size: 3 - 10 μ , Peak viscosity: 1610; Peak Time: 5.07 mins; Pasting temperature: 87.20 °C; Stability ratio: 0.73; Setback ratio: 1.38; Benefit-cost ratio: 5.69 – 11.39. Varied uses: 'ampesi', fufu, chunk-fried, crispy chips, flour, starch, and varied bakery products.	Low lands (muddy areas) of Forest, Forest-Savannah Transition, Coastal Savannah, Guinea Savannah and Sudan Savannah	BL/SM 115	2019	2019
CRI-Agyenkwa	GH/Ce/003/19	INEA	E. Baafi, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-CRI	Structure: erect; Petiole colour: Greenish-purple base and upper purple colour; Leaf colour: Green; Upper leaf surface: Dark green leaf veins; Lower surface of leaf: Light green leaf veins with purple colouration; Central lobe of leaf: Purple circular spot; Corm neck colour: Cream; Corm flesh colour: Cream; Maturity: Late maturing (8 -12 months after planting)	Potential Yield: 12.0t/ha; TLBD: highly tolerant; Corm dry matter content: 42%; starch granule size: 2 - 5 μ , Peak viscosity: 1823; Peak Time: 5.20 mins; Pasting temperature: 87.30°C; Stability ratio: 0.72; Setback ratio: 1.46; Benefit-cost ratio: 2.74 – 5.49. Uses: Aampesi, fufu, chunk-fried, crispy chips, flour, starch, and varied bakery products.	Low lands (muddy areas) of Forest, Forest-Savannah Transition, Coastal Savannah, Guinea Savannah and Sudan Savannah	BL/SM 151	2019	2019
CRI-Yen anya woa	GH/Ce/003/19	INEA	E. Baafi, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-CRI	Structure: erect; Petiole colour: Green with greenish-purple margins and reddish-purple upper portion; Leaf colour: Glassy, shiny yellowish green; Upper leaf surface: Green leaf veins; Lower surface of leaf: Reddish-purple leaf veins; Central lobe of leaf: Reddish-purple radiating spot; Corm neck colour: White; Corm flesh colour: White with pink spots; Maturity: Late maturing (8 -12 months after planting)	Potential Yield: 16.0 t/ha; TLBD: highly tolerant; Corm dry matter content: 41%; starch granule size: 1 - 2.5 μ ; Peak viscosity: 1512; Peak Time: 5.20 mins; Pasting temperature: 86.45°C; Stability ratio: 0.80; Setback ratio: 1.45; Benefit-cost ratio: 3.54 – 7.09. Varied uses: 'ampesi', fufu, chunk-fried, crispy chips, flour, starch, and varied bakery products.	Low lands (muddy areas) of Forest, Forest-Savannah Transition, Coastal Savannah, Guinea Savannah and Sudan Savannah	BL/SM 16	2019	2019

YAM

SPECIES: *Dioscorea rotundata*
Dioscorea alata

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/Source	Breeder (s)/Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
CRI-Pona	GH/Dr/001/15	IITA, Ibadan	E. Otoo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Young Stem: young stem colour: Purplish Green; Mature leaf: colour: Dark Green; Mature leaf: tip colour: Dark Green; Mature leaf: petiole length(cm): 5; Petiole length in correlation to leaf blade: Medium; Mature leaf: petiole colour: All green with purple at both ends; Tuber corms: Present; Corm size: Small and easily separated from tuber; Cylindrical tuber shape; Roots on tuber surface : no; Spines on tuber : no	Potential yield 42t/ha; Dry matter content: 33 %; Crude ash: 3.37%; Crude Fibre 2.5%; Crude Protein: 9.39; Water binding capacity:140.7; Swelling capacity: 9.32; TTA: 0.45; pH: 7.05%; Solubility:13	Coastal savannah, Forest, Forest-savannah Transition and Guinea savannah	Landrace	2005	2015
Mankrong-pona	GH/Dr/002/15	IITA, Ibadan	E. Otoo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Young Stem: young stem colour: Brownish Green; Mature leaf: colour: Dark Green; Mature leaf: tip colour: Dark Green; mature leaf: distance between lobes: Intermediate; Mature leaf: petiole length(cm): 7; Petiole wing colour: Green With Purple Edges; Mature leaf-petiole colour: All green with purple at both ends; Tuber corms: Present; Corm size: Small and easily separated from tuber; Cylindrical tuber shape; no roots on tuber surface; no spines on tuber.	Potential yield 70t/ha; Dry Matter: 34.63%; Crude Ash: 3.01%; Crude Fibre: 2.15%; Crude Protein: 8.67%; Water Binding Capacity:140.74; Swelling capacity: 13.11 ; TTA: 0.45; pH: 6.49; Solubility: 11.33%	Coastal savanna, Forest, Forest-savannah Transition and Guinea savannah	TDr89/02665	2005	2015
CRI - Kukrupa	GH/Dr/003/15	Landrace/Ghana	E. Otoo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Young Stem: young stem colour: Green; Mature leaf:colour: Dark Green; Mature leaf: tip colour: Dark Green; mature leaf:distance between lobes: Intermediate; Mature leaf: petiole length(cm): 5.7; Petiole wing colour: Green With Purple Edges; Mature leaf: petiole colour: green; Tuber corms: Present; Corm size: Small and easily separated from tuber; Cylindrical tuber shape; Roots on tuber surface: no; Spines on tuber: no	Potential yield 50t/ha; Dry Matter: 33.42; Crude Ash: 3.37; Crude Fibre: 2.46; Crude Protein: 9.39; Water Binding Capacity: 140.73; Swelling capacity: 9.32; TTA: 0.45; pH 7.05; Solubility 13%	Coastal savanna, Forest, Forest-savannah Transition and Guinea savannah	Landrace	2005	2015
CRI Soanyinto	GH/Da/001/17	Landrace/Ghana	E. Otoo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Colour of young leaves: light green; Colour of older leaves: dark green; distance between lobes: wide; colour of petiole: all green; vine colour characteristics: green with green wings; folding of young leaves: mild; folding of older leaves: mild	Yield is 30.3t/ha; Virus: tolerant; nematode: tolerant; anthracnose: tolerant; Bacterial Leaf Blight : tolerant; Uses: Ampesi and fufu	Coastal Savanna, Forest Savannah Transition, Guinea Savannah	TDa_00/0003	2017	2017
CRI Afase Biri	GH/Da/002/17	Landrace/Ghana	E. Otoo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Colour of young leaves: purple; Colour of older leaves: Dark green with purple tinge; distance between lobes: wide; colour of petiole: Green with purple ends; vine colour characteristics: Light green with purple nodes and purple wings; folding of young leaves: upwards; folding of older leaves: upwards	Purple tuber flesh; Yield is 43.7t/ha; Virus: tolerant; nematode: tolerant; anthracnose: tolerant; Bacterial Leaf Blight : tolerant; Uses: Ampesi and fufu	Coastal Savannah, Forest Savannah Transition, Guinea Savannah	TDa_00/0046	2017	2017
CRI Afasepa	GH/Da/003/17	IITA, Ibadan	E. Otoo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Colour of young leaves: Greenish with purplish tinge; Colour of older leaves: green; distance between lobes: no distance; colour of petiole: all green; vine colour characteristics: Green with dark green wings; folding of young leaves: upwards; folding of older leaves: upwards	Yield is 32.3t/ha; taste good; Virus: tolerant; nematode: tolerant; anthracnose: tolerant; Bacterial Leaf Blight: tolerant; Uses: Ampesi and fufu	Coastal Savannah, Forest Savannah Transition, Guinea Savannah	TDa_00/0004	2017	2017
CRI Ahoodinfo	GH/Da/004/17	Landrace/Ghana	E. Otoo, CSIR-CRI	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Colour of young leaves: green; Colour of older leaves: green; distance between lobes: wide; colour of petiole: all green; vine colour characteristics: Green with green wings; folding of young leaves: downwards; folding of older leaves: downwards	Yield is 34.6t/ha; Virus: tolerant; nematode: tolerant; anthracnose: tolerant; Bacterial Leaf Blight: tolerant; Uses: Ampesi and fufu	Coastal Savannah, Forest Savannah Transition, Guinea Savannah	TDa_00/0029	2017	2017

VEGETABLES

PEPPER

SPECIES: *Capsicum annum*

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/ Source	Breeder (s)/ Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/ Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
CSIR-CRI shito adope	GH/Ca/001/15	Landrace/ Ghana	CSIR- Crops Research Institute	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant height: 48 cm; Plant Spread: 52 cm; Days to flowering: 60 days; Plant growth habit: Compact & flat at top; Immature fruit colour: green; Mature fruit colour: red; Av. length of fruit with pedicel: 8.31 cm; Av. Length of fruit without pedicel: 6.52 cm; Av. Fruit weight: 3.48 grams	Pungency: Very Hot; Yield-Fresh: 30 t/ha; Yield-Dry: 9.3 t/ha	Savannah areas	MI 2	2005	2015
CSIR-CRI MAKO NTOSE	GH/Ca/002/15	Landrace/ Ghana	CSIR- Crops Research Institute	CSIR-Crops Research Institute	Plant height: 54cm; Plant spread 48cm; Number of days to flowering : 63 days; Immature fruit colour: Light green; Mature fruit colour :Bright Red; Av. length of fruit with pedicel : 14.61; Av. length of fruit without pedicel: 11.52 cm; Av. Fruit weight grams: 10.88	Pungency: Mild; Ripe fruits can replace tomato in many food preparations; Yield: Fresh: 35 t/ha; Yield: Dry12.25 t/ha	Savannah areas	ICPN9 -14 (An introduction from AVRDC -Taiwan)	2005	2015

INDUSTRIAL CROPS

COTTON

SPECIES: *Gossypium hirsutum*

Name of Variety	National Code	Origin/Source	Breeder (s)/Institution	Applicant	Distinctness Uniformity and Stability (DUS)	Value for Cultivation and Use (VCU)	Preferred Ecology	Pedigree/Line	Year of Release	Year of Registry
SARCOT 1	GH/Gh/001/15	Landrace/Ghana	E. B. Chamba, M. S. Abdulai, A. V. Clotey, A.B. Salifu; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-SARI	First fruiting node: 7.3; leaf length: 12.5cm; Node/sympodium: 3.5; petal colour: pale yellow; boll shape: elongated; boll surface: dimpled; No. of locules per boll: 4.3; seeds per boll: 30.6; hairiness: pubescent; plant height: 104cm	Comparatively early maturing (less than 145 days) after planting. Excellent lint colour (white)	Guinea & Sudan savannahs, transitional zone	Pure line	2004	2015
SARCOT 5	GH/Gh/002/15	Landrace/Ghana	E. B. Chamba, M. S. Abdulai, A. V. Clotey, A.B. Salifu; CSIR-SARI	CSIR-SARI	First fruiting node: 7.0; leaf length: 12.8cm; Node/sympodium: 3.5; petal colour: pale yellow; boll shape: round; boll surface: dimpled; No. of locules per boll: 4.1; seeds per boll: 30.3; hairiness: pubescent; plant height: 110cm	Early maturing (less than 145 days) after planting. Excellent lint colour (white)	Guinea & Sudan savannahs, transitional zone	Pure line	2004	2015

FOR FURTHER INFORMATION, CONTACT:

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